

Universal Quantum-Computation

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Abstract

In this research notebook on universal quantum computation for quantum engineers, researchers, and scientists, we will explore quantum advantage, referred to as quantum supremacy. We will put into practice the dynamical decoupling and free evolution. We will also discuss requirements and strategies for the realization of large-scale quantum computation robust and resilient to errors. We begin with an introduction to the concepts of error detection and error correction in classical and quantum systems, and we will introduce several examples to build intuition. We will discuss in detail one quantum error correction code and its code parameters. Next, we will describe how reliable classical and quantum machines can be built from unreliable components, introduce the threshold theorem, and discuss fault tolerance principles. Furthermore, describe the conceptual role of fault-tolerance in realizing large-scale quantum and classical computation. After that, we will transition to quantum error suppression and error correction in practice, beginning with examples of composite pulses and dynamical decoupling sequences. We will then conclude with a detailed discussion on the surface code. We will discuss the scientific basis of families of quantum error correction codes. We will understand the different strategies for counteracting systematic versus random error in quantum computation. Next, we introduce computational complexity classes for classical and quantum computers and explore the meaning of quantum advantage, often referred to as “quantum supremacy.” Furthermore, in the end, we will implement dynamical error suppression protocols on the qubits of a real physical quantum computer, the IBM Quantum Experience.

1 Strategies for Mitigating and Correcting Errors in Quantum Computers: Introduction

We will discuss what is needed to operate larger-scale machines for longer periods of time and in a fault-tolerant manner, [1–14]. We will begin by introducing strategies for detecting and correcting errors in quantum systems. We will discuss several simple examples of quantum error-correcting codes and review the importance of parity measurements in the implementation of quantum error detection. Then, we will consider how reliable classical and quantum machines are built from unreliable components. We will discuss in detail at the threshold theorem and the principles of fault tolerance as applied to both classical and quantum circuits [15]. Then, we will discuss at quantum error mitigation [16,17] and quantum error correction in practice [18]. We will begin with examples of composite pulses and dynamical error suppression. We will then feature a study on realizing fault-tolerant quantum computation using the surface code [19]. Finally, we will address computational complexity topics and consider what it means to demonstrate a quantum computational advantage over classical computers. This milestone is often referred to as quantum supremacy [20,21]. In the end, we will implement dynamical error-mitigation protocols on the IBM quantum experience [22].

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2 Introduction to the Bit-Flip Code: Concept

In order to be useful, quantum computers like classical computers must be built from robust elements. Transistors are amazingly successful circuit elements, and this is in large part because they rarely fail. The failure rate of a transistor is around one part and say, 10 to the 20. In comparison, today's qubits are far more error-prone, with error rates as we have seen around one part in 10 to the 3 or 10 to the 4. It is a problem because algorithms that solve importantly, large scale problems will generally need to implement far more than 1,000 or 10,000 gates. So, what can be done? One thing that can be done, as we have discussed in section three, is to develop algorithms that provide a quantum advantage with the noisy devices we have today, working as a co-processor with a classical computer. That research is ongoing. However, for large scale, fault-tolerant quantum computing applications, we will need to make quantum devices more resilient to error. It is not just quantum systems. Most classical, electronic, and communication systems are also subject to errors at some level. Whether a classical system or quantum system, one means to improve system reliability is to use error correction protocols [23]. Conceptually, systems are built from devices, and devices can be faulty. Let us say we have an imperfect device that is somewhat insensitive to small input errors but becomes less resilient with larger errors. If they are individually good enough, such devices can often be made more resilient by adding additional resources. Say, by building in redundancy. So, we improve system reliability, but it is done at the expense of additional overhead. To see how this works, let us discuss at a specific example of an error-correcting code called the bit-flip code, which can be implemented on both classical and quantum bits. We will start with a single qubit—a physical qubit with a probability, p , of a single error. As it is around 10 to the minus 3 or 10 to the minus 4. let us say this qubit is in a superposition state, $\alpha(0) + \beta(1)$. we add redundancy by encoding the qubit state on to 3 qubits, $\alpha(0,0,0) + \beta(1,1,1)$. Using the code words “0, 0, 0” to represent the logical state 0, and “1,1,1” to represent logical state 1. As we will see, this encoding protects against a single bit flip error on one of the qubits [24]. That is, one of the qubits flips from 0 to 1 or from 1 to 0. If that error occurs on at most one of the qubits, we can detect that it happens and fix it. However, the error code will fail if there are two or more errors on the encoded qubits. The probability of getting two or more errors is $3p$ squared times 1 minus p plus p cubed. We will write this as a constant, c , times p squared to the leading order in the probability, p . Then the constant, c , conceptually, incorporates the number of ways these errors can occur, and the amount of overhead used in the code. So, does this encoding help us? Adding redundancy three qubits instead of one qubit is a net win if the encoded error probability, c times p squared, is less than the single-qubit error probability, p . conceptually, this sets a threshold condition to achieve a net win. The single-qubit error probability, p , must be less than $1/c$. It means that if the single-qubit error rate is low enough, then introducing redundancy by adding more such qubits would reduce the overall error rate. The cost we pay to achieve this improvement is the overhead required to implement the error correction. This turning point probability, where single qubit performance becomes good enough for error correction to work, is called the threshold probability, or just the threshold for short [25, 26]. Here, the conceptual threshold is $1/c$. We will discuss the formal definition of the threshold and its connection to extensible error correction protocols in future sections.

All realistic communication and computation schemes experience some form of noise. When noise induces errors in our system [27], we need tools that allow us to detect when an error occurred. One means for implementing error detection is based on a parity check. Parity checks are used in classical and quantum error correction schemes to determine the presence and location of an error. With that knowledge, one can go back and correct the error.

What is parity? Parity is the mathematical term which tells us if two things are the same,

or if they are different [28]. For example, if two data bits b_1 and b_2 are the same, we can say that they have a parity equal to 0. However, if the two data bits are different, we can say they have a parity of 1. In other words, we can describe the parity of two data bits using a third “parity bit” b_p , which stores value 0 when the data bits are the same, and it stores 1 when they are different:

$$\begin{aligned} b_1 b_2 = 00 &\rightarrow b_p = 0, \\ b_1 b_2 = 01 &\rightarrow b_p = 1, \\ b_1 b_2 = 10 &\rightarrow b_p = 1, \\ b_1 b_2 = 11 &\rightarrow b_p = 0 \end{aligned}$$

Defined in this way, the parity bit is the exclusive-OR (XOR) of the two data bits, $b_p = b_1 \oplus b_2$. Quantum mechanically, the XOR gate is implemented using a CNOT gate, for example, with qubit b_2 the target qubit.

Parity measurements can be generalized to larger numbers of bits, defined as the XOR sum of those bits. In general, the parity is 1 if there are an odd number of 1’s, and the parity is 0 if there are an even number of 1’s. The weight of the parity check corresponds to the number of bits. For example, the above example with two bits is a weight-two parity check. The surface code [29], a type of quantum error correction protocol, uses weight-four parity checks [30].

Parity-check operations enable us to detect errors in quantum systems without projecting and destroying quantum information. They are an example of a broader class of such operations called stabilizers [31]. In the next sections, we will discuss these concepts in more detail.

3 Introduction to the Bit-Flip Code: Detecting Single Errors

Before diving into error detection, let us first discuss at how the single-qubit state can be encoded quantum mechanically onto these code words. The idea is to start with three qubits. Qubit 1 is prepared in the superposition state $\alpha 0$ plus $\beta 1$. qubits 2 and 3 are initialized in state 0. As we have done in previous sections, we will show the mathematical steps as we step through the quantum circuit indicated by the vertical line [28]. The resulting logical qubit state is realized by implementing two CNOT gates, as shown, with qubits 2 and 3 being the target qubits conditioned on the state of qubit 1. The truth table for the CNOT gate is shown. the state of qubit J is flipped if qubit 1 is in state 1. Otherwise, it is left alone. This is essentially implementing an XOR operation. So, let us take them one gate at a time. we will start with a CNOT gate applied to qubits 1 and 2 with qubit 2 the target conditioned on the state of qubit 1. For the $\alpha 0$ component of qubit 1, qubit 2 remains in state 0. for the $\beta 1$ component of qubit 1, and qubit 2 will flip to state 1. we see that we have now associated state 0 of qubit 2 with the coefficient α and state 1 of qubit 2 with the coefficient β . Similarly, applying a CNOT gate to qubits 1 and 3 leads to the same result. The 0 and 1 states of qubit 3 are now associated with α and β , respectively. The result is an entangled state $\alpha 000$ plus $\beta 111$. we will drop the tensor products [32], remove the subscripts Q1, Q2, and Q3. instead, just use single kets for all three qubits to simplify the notation going forward. so, we have encoded the single-qubit state using a three-qubit code. Now, how can we detect if a bit-flip occurred on one of these three qubits? The answer is to implement a type of majority voting scheme using a set of measurements called parity checks between neighboring qubits. Qubits in the same state have the same parity, while those in different states have different parity. The outputs of the parity measurements are called a syndrome. the syndrome is used to tell us if and where a single error occurred. we will realize a parity check on qubits 1 and 2 using the XOR gate and store the answer on an ancilla qubit, SA. Similarly, we will apply the XOR gate to qubits 2 and 3 and store the result on a second ancilla

qubit, SB. we will then measure the ancilla qubits to get the values of SA and SB. For example, let us discuss at the parity measurement of qubits 1 and 2. The value SA is the exclusive OR of qubits 1 and 2. we can see that if both qubits are in state 0, or both are in state 1, then the value of SA is 0. That is, if the qubits are in the same state, meaning they have the same parity, then there is no error. However, if one of the qubits is in state 0, and the other is in state 1, it does not matter which is which then they have different parity. the value of SA is 1. we will do a similar XOR gate on qubits 2 and 3 to get the value of SB. SB takes on value 0 if qubits 2 and 3 have the same parity, indicating no error. Alternatively, SB will have value 1, indicating that qubits 2 and 3 have different parity, indicating that an error occurred on one of those two qubits. Now, we may have noticed something very interesting about performing parity measurements. this is very important to preserving quantum information [1, 33, 34]. When we measure parity, we never discuss anything about the specific states 0 or 1 or of the qubits 1, 2, or 3. The parity measurement never projects those qubits onto state 1 or state 0. Rather, we only discuss their parity. That is, whether the two qubits are in the same state, having the same parity. Alternatively, in different states, having different parity. Essentially, we have devised a measurement that indicates if an error occurred or not but never reveals, or projects out, the computational states of the qubits. That is really neat. it is the backbone of quantum error detection. So, we have a syndrome comprising two values SA and SB. Let us see how they are used to tell us where a single bit-flip error occurred. we will start with the encoded state α 000 plus β 111. Now, let us assume that we have a single bit-flip error on qubit 1. The encoded state becomes α 100 plus β 011. we perform a parity check on qubits 1 and 2. because they are in different states whether 10 or 01 SA equals 1. we then perform a parity check on qubits 2 and 3. because they are always in the same state either 00 or 11, we find SB equals 0. As before, the XOR operations are performed using sequential CNOT gates with the ancilla qubits SA and SB being the target qubits. For example, the state of SA is flipped conditioned on the state of qubit 1. then again on the state of qubit 2. similarly, for SB and qubits 2 and 3., we encourage us to work out the truth tables for SA and SB on our own. So, the syndrome SA equals 1 and SB equals 0 tells us that a single bit-flip error occurred on qubit 1. If instead, the error occurred on qubit 2, then we see that this error leads to having different parity for qubits 1 and 2, as well as for qubits 2 and 3. The resulting syndrome measurement then yields SA equals 1, and SB equals 1, indicating an error on qubit 2. an error on qubit 3 results from qubits 1 and 2 having the same parity, but qubits 2 and 3 having different parity. So, the syndrome, in this case, is SA equals 0, and SA equals 1, indicating an error on qubit 3. if no errors occurred, then both SA and SB equal 0. Thus, the syndrome measurement uniquely identifies if a single qubit error occurred. if so, on which qubit.

How are parity checks used in error correction? To give an example, Let us consider a simple protocol the “bit-flip code” that uses redundancy to encode information. That is, instead of encoding information in a single physical qubit [24], we encode this information onto a single logical qubit comprising several physical qubits [35]. For example, Let us consider a mapping of one qubit on to three qubits, $q_1, q_2,$ and q_3 :

$$|0\rangle \rightarrow |0\rangle_{q_1}|0\rangle_{q_2}|0\rangle_{q_3} \rightarrow |000\rangle \quad |1\rangle \rightarrow |1\rangle_{q_1}|1\rangle_{q_2}|1\rangle_{q_3} \rightarrow |111\rangle \quad (1)$$

Where we use a shorthand Dirac notation [36–41] for the 000 and 111 states, these states are called codewords, and they are both chosen to have parity 0. This type of encoding can be used to detect a specific type of error a “bit flip”. That is, if a single bit-flip error occurs, then the resulting state is no longer a codeword, and this can be detected.

To see how, Let us consider a single-qubit superposition state mapped onto the codewords of the three-qubit bit-flip code:

$$\alpha|0\rangle + \beta|1\rangle \rightarrow \alpha|000\rangle + \beta|111\rangle. \quad (2)$$

Suppose a quantum operation is executed on our encoded quantum state. Ideally, in the absence of errors, the operation may change the values of α and β , but it should not flip any of the bits within the codewords. However, in the presence of noise, an error may occur.

How can we use parity checks to detect if a single bit-flip error occurred? The concept is that single bit-flip errors will change the quantum states so that they are no longer codewords, and this is detectable through a change in parity. As we discuss in the accompanying section, in the case of the three-qubit bit-flip code, one can use two pairwise parity checks between qubits 1 and 2 ($q_1 \oplus q_2$), and between qubits 2 and 3 ($q_2 \oplus q_3$). We will store the results of the parity measurements on additional, ancillary qubits S_A and S_B :

$$S_A = q_1 \oplus q_2, \quad (3)$$

$$S_B = q_2 \oplus q_3. \quad (4)$$

Together, the measured values of S_A and S_B form a syndrome, which can uniquely identify if and where an error occurred, provided there is at most one bit-flip. Because of this, the ancillary qubits are sometimes called syndrome qubits.

Importantly, when we measure the syndrome qubits, we only discuss the syndrome values the parity of the data qubits without projecting the data qubits individually onto values 0 or 1. For example, when a bit flip occurs on q_1 , we never discuss if $|000\rangle \rightarrow |100\rangle$ or $|111\rangle \rightarrow |011\rangle$. We only become aware that the syndrome has changed. For both codewords, $(S_A, S_B) = (0, 0) \rightarrow (1, 0)$. The syndrome is then used to identify the presence and location (q_1) of the error. Because we never projected out 0 or 1 of the data qubits, the quantum information is preserved. Said another way, the syndrome measurements project the logical states onto the codeword states (no error), or onto one of the error states (error) outside the codeword space with measurement values, in this case, the parity that distinguishes the various cases.

Figure 1: Error detection with the three-qubit bit-flip code. The quantum state is encoded onto three qubits: q_1 , q_2 , and q_3 . Parity checks between neighboring qubits are made and stored on the ancilla (syndrome) qubits S_A and S_B . Measurements are then performed of the ancilla qubits, yielding the values s_A and s_B . Given an arbitrary superposition state $\alpha|000\rangle + \beta|111\rangle$, and assuming at most one bit-flip error (red text), the corresponding truth table for s_A and s_B is shown. Pairs of (s_A, s_B) values uniquely indicate the presence and location of a single error. Table of syndrome results for the three-qubit bit-flip error correction code with two additional ancilla qubits

Finally, note that there is more than one way to realize the bit-flip code, also called a repetition code. In section presentations later this section, we will discuss another version of the bit-flip code (and related codes) that uses, for example, qubits q_2 and q_3 to store the syndrome, rather than

using separate ancilla qubits. In that approach, the state of the physical qubit q_1 is corrected, rather than the logically encoded state. While that approach uses fewer qubits, one needs to re-encode the state of qubit q_1 onto the logical states after each syndrome measurement. Otherwise, many of the concepts and intuition are the same.

4 Introduction to the Bit-Flip Code: Correcting Single Errors

So, now that we have detected a single error, what can we do? Clearly, if the syndrome is 0-0, we infer that no error occurred, and we do nothing. However, what about the other syndromes? Since the code indicates single bit-flip errors, we can take the result of the syndrome measurement and perform an X gate on the errant qubit to flip it back to the correct state. For example, if the syndrome is 1-0 indicating an error on qubit one, we apply an X gate to qubit one, flipping it back. Again, we never knew if qubit one was erroneously in state 0 or state 1. We just know that it was in the wrong state, whatever it was, and it needed to be flipped back to be in the correct state. Again, this lack of state-specific information means the quantum information has been preserved. Before we can proceed, we need to reset the ancilla qubits. In this case, S-A is flipped back to state 0 using an X gate. S-B, already in state 0, does not need to be flipped back. Next, let us assume that a bit-flip error occurs on qubit two. Here, the syndrome measurement yields 1-1, indicating qubit two has an error. So, we apply an X gate to qubit two to flip it back to the correct state. We apply X gates to both S-A and S-B to reset them to state 0-0. Finally, a syndrome 0-1 indicates a bit-flip error on qubit three, and so, we apply an X gate to qubit three to correct that error. We apply an X gate to ancilla qubit S-B to reset it back to state 0. So, to summarize, the bit flip code, although very simple, captures many key concepts of error correction. We started with a single qubit with an error probability p . We then redundantly encoded that qubit's state onto three qubits. The three-qubit bit-flip code can detect and correct for, at most, one-bit flip error. So, the logically encoded state is preserved unless two or more errors occur. Two errors happen with a probability c times p squared. Thus, we can define a threshold for this code here, and it is one over c that tells us at least how good the single qubits must be in order to achieve a net win when adding more together. We discuss that errors can be detected using parity measurements, which are combined to form a syndrome that tells us if and where an error occurred, without ever revealing or projecting out the quantum information. Based on the syndrome, we can correct for single errors and maintain the logical state. However, when two or more errors occurred, the syndrome will lead us to the wrong conclusion, and the scheme breaks down. Finally, we note that we can handle more errors by adding more redundancy. For example, using five qubits and four ancillas will correct for up to two-bit flip errors. Alternatively, if we want to improve the logical error rate, we can add more levels of recursion. That is, take each qubit in the level one logical encoding and represent each with its own logical encoding, and so on. Bit flips are not the only kind of error. In the remainder of this section and throughout the section, we will see a related code that can correct for phase flips, as well as more sophisticated codes that can correct for both types of error simultaneously. We will discuss the fault tolerance of particular codes, that is, the ability to handle errors wherever they may occur during the error detection and correction protocols.

5 Quantum Error Correction Codes: The Three-Qubit Bit Flip Error Correction Code

Now, we are going to go back to quantum error-correcting codes. In this section, we are going to do a quantum version of the repetition code. So, 0 goes to 000. 1 goes to 111. Well, let us try to quantumize it, or quantize it. 0 goes to 000. 1 goes to 111. we can write a circuit diagram for that. So, we will already know that this is not quantum cloning, because quantum cloning is impossible. So, $\alpha 0$ plus $\beta 1$ goes to $\alpha 000$, plus $\beta 111$. So, can we correct errors? Well, first, let us try to correct bit errors. So, what did this channel do? It corrected the one-bit error. Or not channel. What did that code do? It corrected the one-bit error. So, if we flipped one bit, we can get it back. So, let us start out by trying the σ_x errors. σ_x . Well, we have three bits. we can apply σ_x on it. So, let us apply a σ_x error to the encoded psi on the second bit. So, psi encoded is equal to what? Is equal to $\alpha 010$ plus $\beta 101$. So, can we correct this? Well, we can correct it—measure which bit is different. Now, we would like to measure which bit is different without measuring all three of these bits. Because if we measure all three of these bits, we will put a superposition into the code, α zero plus β one. We would like the same superposition to come out of the code after we have decided it. So, how do we measure which bit is different? Well, actually, that is pretty easy. So, here is the encoded psi. We apply a control NOT from the first bit to the second bit, a control NOT from the first bit to the third bit. Back here, we apply a control NOT from the first to the second and control NOT to the first to the third. We get 0. So, $\alpha 000$, plus $\beta 111$ goes to $\alpha 000$ plus $\beta 100$. we measure two zeros. So, that is good. We can see that this decoding circuit is really the inverse of the encoding circuit. So, that is very good. Now, what happens if we made an error there? So, suppose we put $\alpha 010$, plus $\beta 101$ into that circuit. Psi error equals that. When we put it into that circuit, we get out $\alpha 010$ plus $\beta 110$. Because we are doing the control NOT from this guy to this guy, and from the first guy to the third guy. we measure 1, 0. our state is $\alpha 0$ plus $\beta 1$, because this is equal to $\alpha 0$ plus $\beta 1$ times 10. we measure these guys. So, what we measure tells us that our second bit is wrong, and we have recovered the first bit. So, suppose we put in $\alpha 100$ plus $\beta 011$. So, that is the error state. So, we got this by applying σ_x to the first qubit. After circuit, we get $\alpha 111$ plus $\beta 011$ is equal to $\alpha 1$ plus $\beta 0$ times 11. we measure 11. So, what do we need to do to the state to fix it? If these measurement results are both ones, we apply x here. We should draw a classical stop in green. So, that is how we decode the qubit code. But, not everything is a σ_x error. There are also σ_z errors. So, what happens if we apply a σ_z error to this code? Well, there are three things we can apply the σ_z to. The first, second, or third qubit. What do we get? Well, here we get $\alpha 000$ minus $\beta 111$. Here we get $\alpha 000$ minus well, it is the same thing, right? And here we get the same thing again. all of these are encoded $\alpha 0$ minus $\beta 1$. So, what have we done? Well, we will call this the bit error-correcting code. 3 qubit bit error correction. If we have σ_x , correct it. if we have a σ_z , we have applied σ_z to the encoded qubit.

The figure below shows the quantum circuit for an implementation of the bit-flip error correction code.

Figure 2: Bit-flip

1. The initial three-qubit state is

$$|\psi_0\rangle = |\psi\rangle |0\rangle |0\rangle, \quad (5)$$

where the state of the qubit of interest is

$$|\psi\rangle = \alpha |0\rangle + \beta |1\rangle. \quad (6)$$

2. The first and second controlled-NOT (CNOT) gates [42] transform the state to

$$|\psi_0\rangle \rightarrow |\psi_1\rangle = \alpha |0\rangle |0\rangle |0\rangle + \beta |1\rangle |1\rangle |1\rangle. \quad (7)$$

3. First, Let us note that operationally a bit-flip error corresponds to an X-gate. This gate performs the following operation:

$$X |0\rangle = |1\rangle, X |1\rangle = |0\rangle. \quad (8)$$

We will assume that the error occurs on at most one qubit. The error can occur on the first, second, or third qubit, or it may not occur at all. The evolution of the system in these four cases is:

- (a) There is no error on any of the qubits. In this case, the three-qubit state remains the same after E_{bit} ,

$$|\psi_1\rangle \rightarrow |\psi_2^a\rangle = \alpha |0\rangle |0\rangle |0\rangle + \beta |1\rangle |1\rangle |1\rangle. \quad (9)$$

- (b) A bit-flip error occurs on the third qubit. In this case, the state of the system becomes:

$$|\psi_1\rangle \rightarrow |\psi_2^b\rangle = \alpha |0\rangle |0\rangle |1\rangle + \beta |1\rangle |1\rangle |0\rangle. \quad (10)$$

- (c) A bit-flip error occurs on the second qubit. In this case, the state of the system becomes:

$$|\psi_1\rangle \rightarrow |\psi_2^c\rangle = \alpha |0\rangle |1\rangle |0\rangle + \beta |1\rangle |0\rangle |1\rangle. \quad (11)$$

- (d) A bit-flip error occurs on the first qubit. In this case, the state of the system becomes:

$$|\psi_1\rangle \rightarrow |\psi_2^d\rangle = \alpha |1\rangle |0\rangle |0\rangle + \beta |0\rangle |1\rangle |1\rangle. \quad (12)$$

The third and fourth CNOT gates leave the system in state:

$$\begin{aligned}
 |\psi_2^a\rangle &\rightarrow |\psi_3^a\rangle = \alpha |0\rangle |0\rangle |0\rangle + \beta |1\rangle |0\rangle |0\rangle \\
 |\psi_2^b\rangle &\rightarrow |\psi_3^b\rangle = \alpha |0\rangle |0\rangle |1\rangle + \beta |1\rangle |0\rangle |1\rangle \\
 |\psi_2^c\rangle &\rightarrow |\psi_3^c\rangle = \alpha |0\rangle |1\rangle |0\rangle + \beta |1\rangle |1\rangle |0\rangle \\
 |\psi_2^d\rangle &\rightarrow |\psi_3^d\rangle = \alpha |1\rangle |1\rangle |1\rangle + \beta |0\rangle |1\rangle |1\rangle
 \end{aligned} \tag{13}$$

Finally, the four possible states before measuring the two ancillary qubits are:

$$\begin{aligned}
 |\psi_3^a\rangle &= (\alpha |0\rangle + \beta |1\rangle) |0\rangle |0\rangle \\
 |\psi_3^b\rangle &= (\alpha |0\rangle + \beta |1\rangle) |0\rangle |1\rangle \\
 |\psi_3^c\rangle &= (\alpha |0\rangle + \beta |1\rangle) |1\rangle |0\rangle \\
 |\psi_3^d\rangle &= (\alpha |1\rangle + \beta |0\rangle) |1\rangle |1\rangle.
 \end{aligned} \tag{14}$$

1. Bit-Flip Code I: Recovering the State; In which case(s) should a σ_X gate be applied to the first qubit to recover the initial state of qubit 1, $|\psi_0\rangle$?

- When the ancillary qubits are measured in $|0\rangle |0\rangle$
- When the ancillary qubits are measured in $|0\rangle |1\rangle$
- When the ancillary qubits are measured in $|1\rangle |0\rangle$
- When the ancillary qubits are measured in $|1\rangle |1\rangle$

Solution:

If the ancillary qubits (qubits 2 and 3) are projected to $|0\rangle |0\rangle$ (case a), then there was no error in any of the three qubits. If the ancillary qubits are projected to $|0\rangle |1\rangle$ (case b), then there was bit-flip error in the third qubit. If the ancillary qubits are projected to $|1\rangle |0\rangle$ (case c), then there was an error in the second qubit. In these three cases, there is no need to apply an extra operation to recover the initial state of the qubit of interest $|\psi\rangle$. If the ancillary qubits are projected to $|1\rangle |1\rangle$, then there was an error in the first qubit; and to recover the state $|\psi\rangle$, an X gate has to be applied in the first qubit. Note that this implementation is predicated on the assumption of at most one error.

6 Quantum Error Correction Codes: The Three-Qubit Phase Flip Error Correction Code

Suppose we have a dephasing channel and let us say that is 1 minus q, we apply a σ_Z , probability Q, 1 minus q we apply nothing, probability Q we apply to σ_Z . The probability of error is we get an error if we apply a σ_Z to any qubit. We do not get an error if we apply σ_Z to an even number of qubits. So, it is 3 Q, 1 minus Q squared plus Q cubed. We want to say this is three times the chance of σ_Z error on an uncoded qubit. However, if we have a de-bidding channel, if we have a channel 1 minus Q σ_X 1 minus Q identity, and Q σ_X probability of error, well, we need at least two of these qubits to be wrong, to have an error in the originally encoded qubit. So, the probability of error is Q, 3 Q squared, 1 minus Q plus Q cubed. So, this is quadratically small if Q is small, and this is 3 times 3Q if Q is small. So, we have corrected the bit errors, and we made the phase errors even worse. Now, we probably know that Hadamard's interchange phase errors bit errors. So, intuitively this should mean that we can take this code and Hadamard it

and get a code that corrects the bit phase errors but makes bit errors three times as worse. So, let us do it. The bit code, or the bit correcting code, was 0 goes to 0 0 0. 1 goes to 1 1 1. So, let us say this is the phase code. It is going to take H 0 to H cubed 0 0 0. H 1 to H cubed 1 1 1. this is just 0 plus 1, 1 over 2 goes to 1 over root 8, 0 0 0 plus 0 0 1 plus dot dot dot plus 1 1 1, and 1 over root 2 0 minus 1 goes to 1 over root 8 0 0 0 minus 0 0 1 through minus 1 1 1. this is minus 1, the number of 1's in this state. So, we worked this out for Simon's algorithm. This is what Hadamard cubed does. It takes up puts a minus 1 on any state with an odd number of ones. We can add these, and we can subtract these to get what the code does to 0 and 1. So, phase code 0 goes to 0 0 0 plus 0 1 1 plus 1 0 1 plus 1 1 0. 1 goes to 1/2 0 0 1 plus 0 1 0 plus 1 0 0 minus 1 1 plus 1 1. So, we take zero to the superposition of states with an even number of zeros, even the number of ones, and one to a superposition state with an odd number of ones. Because when we subtract this from this, we only get states with an odd number of ones. When we add these, we only get states with an even number of ones. So, we can correct this, and actually, it should be obvious that we can correct this because all we did was, we put a Hadamard in front of everything. So, just take our old correction circuit and add a whole bunch of Hadamard's, and we get the new correction circuit with a phase code. However, we want to explain it in a different way. So, let us call this, let us call this a logical 0, and this a logical 1. Logical 0, logical 1, σZ on the first qubit, a logical 0, σZ on the first qubit, logical 1, σZ on the second qubit, logical 0, are all orthogonal. Well, we can see that up here. We mean, we can note first clearly 0 and 1 are orthogonal because none of these basis states in the superposition of 1 appears in a superposition of 0. when we apply a σZ to any of the bits, this is still true. So, any σZ error on one is orthogonal to any other σZ error on 0. further, if we apply σZ error to 0, so, σZ on first qubit of 0 logical 0 is equal to 1 over 2 0 0 0 plus 0 1 1 minus 1 0 1 minus 1 1 0. So, half the terms here are plus, half the terms here are minus, so, this is orthogonal to that. It is easy to check that all of these are orthogonal. So, project onto subspaces 0 L 1 L 0 σZ 1 0 L σZ 1 1 L. So, these are four orthogonal subspaces. So, there is a measurement that projects the state onto one of these four subspaces. In this case, if we get this subspace, we do nothing. If we get this subspace, we apply σZ for the first qubit, and we get the next subspace, we apply σZ to the second qubit. So, this shows us how to correct these errors.

2. Phase-Flip Code I: Recovering the State; The figure below shows the quantum circuit for the implementation of the phase-flip error correction code.

Figure 3: Phase-Flip Code

The initial three-qubit state is

$$|\psi_0\rangle = |\psi\rangle |0\rangle |0\rangle, \tag{15}$$

where the state of the qubit of interest is

$$|\psi\rangle = \alpha |0\rangle + \beta |1\rangle. \quad (16)$$

The first and second CNOT gates transform the state to

$$|\psi_0\rangle \rightarrow |\psi_1\rangle = \alpha |0\rangle |0\rangle |0\rangle + \beta |1\rangle |1\rangle |1\rangle. \quad (17)$$

After a Hadamard gate in each of the qubits, the state becomes

$$|\psi_1\rangle \rightarrow |\psi_2\rangle = \alpha |+\rangle |+\rangle |+\rangle + \beta |-\rangle |-\rangle |-\rangle, \quad (18)$$

where

$$|\pm\rangle = \frac{|0\rangle \pm |1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}}. \quad (19)$$

Then, the phase error occurs on at most one qubit. Note that a phase flip corresponds operationally to a σ_Z gate. This gate implements the following transformation:

$$\sigma_Z |+\rangle = \frac{|0\rangle - |1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}}, \sigma_Z |-\rangle = \frac{|0\rangle + |1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}}. \quad (20)$$

There would be four possible error cases depending on which qubit the error occurred if an error occurred at all.

(a) There is no error on any of the qubits. In this case, the three-qubit state remains the same,

$$|\psi_2\rangle \rightarrow |\psi_3^a\rangle = \alpha |+\rangle |+\rangle |+\rangle + \beta |-\rangle |-\rangle |-\rangle. \quad (21)$$

(b) A phase error occurs on the third qubit. In this case, the state of the system is transformed as:

$$|\psi_2\rangle \rightarrow |\psi_3^b\rangle = \alpha |+\rangle |+\rangle |-\rangle + \beta |-\rangle |-\rangle |+\rangle. \quad (22)$$

(c) A phase error occurs on the second qubit. In this case, the state of the system is transformed as:

$$|\psi_2\rangle \rightarrow |\psi_3^c\rangle = \alpha |+\rangle |-\rangle |+\rangle + \beta |-\rangle |+\rangle |-\rangle. \quad (23)$$

(d) A phase error occurs on the first qubit. In this case, the state of the system is transformed as:

$$|\psi_2\rangle \rightarrow |\psi_3^d\rangle = \alpha |-\rangle |+\rangle |+\rangle + \beta |+\rangle |-\rangle |-\rangle. \quad (24)$$

After applying a second set of Hadamard gate in each of the qubits, the state becomes:

$$\begin{aligned} |\psi_3^a\rangle &\rightarrow |\psi_4^a\rangle = \alpha |0\rangle |0\rangle |0\rangle + \beta |1\rangle |1\rangle |1\rangle \\ |\psi_3^b\rangle &\rightarrow |\psi_4^b\rangle = \alpha |0\rangle |0\rangle |1\rangle + \beta |1\rangle |1\rangle |0\rangle \\ |\psi_3^c\rangle &\rightarrow |\psi_4^c\rangle = \alpha |0\rangle |1\rangle |0\rangle + \beta |1\rangle |0\rangle |1\rangle \\ |\psi_3^d\rangle &\rightarrow |\psi_4^d\rangle = \alpha |1\rangle |0\rangle |0\rangle + \beta |0\rangle |1\rangle |1\rangle \end{aligned} \quad (25)$$

The third and fourth CNOT gates transform the state to:

$$\begin{aligned}
|\psi_4^a\rangle &\rightarrow |\psi_5^a\rangle = \alpha |0\rangle |0\rangle |0\rangle + \beta |1\rangle |0\rangle |0\rangle \\
|\psi_4^b\rangle &\rightarrow |\psi_5^b\rangle = \alpha |0\rangle |0\rangle |1\rangle + \beta |1\rangle |0\rangle |1\rangle \\
|\psi_4^c\rangle &\rightarrow |\psi_5^c\rangle = \alpha |0\rangle |1\rangle |0\rangle + \beta |1\rangle |1\rangle |0\rangle \\
|\psi_4^d\rangle &\rightarrow |\psi_5^d\rangle = \alpha |1\rangle |1\rangle |1\rangle + \beta |0\rangle |1\rangle |1\rangle
\end{aligned} \tag{26}$$

Finally, the four possible states before measuring the two ancillary qubits are:

$$\begin{aligned}
|\psi_5^a\rangle &= (\alpha |0\rangle + \beta |1\rangle) |0\rangle |0\rangle \\
|\psi_5^b\rangle &= (\alpha |0\rangle + \beta |1\rangle) |0\rangle |1\rangle \\
|\psi_5^c\rangle &= (\alpha |0\rangle + \beta |1\rangle) |1\rangle |0\rangle \\
|\psi_5^d\rangle &= (\alpha |1\rangle + \beta |0\rangle) |1\rangle |1\rangle
\end{aligned} \tag{27}$$

3. When should a σ_X gate be applied to qubit 1 to recover the initial state of qubit 1? $|\psi\rangle$?

- When the ancillary qubits are measured in $|0\rangle |0\rangle$
- When the ancillary qubits are measured in $|0\rangle |1\rangle$
- When the ancillary qubits are measured in $|1\rangle |0\rangle$
- When the ancillary qubits are measured in $|1\rangle |1\rangle$

Solution:

From the four final conditional states

$$\begin{aligned}
|\psi_5^a\rangle &= (\alpha |0\rangle + \beta |1\rangle) |0\rangle |0\rangle, \\
|\psi_5^b\rangle &= (\alpha |0\rangle + \beta |1\rangle) |0\rangle |1\rangle, \\
|\psi_5^c\rangle &= (\alpha |0\rangle + \beta |1\rangle) |1\rangle |0\rangle, \\
|\psi_5^d\rangle &= (\alpha |1\rangle + \beta |0\rangle) |1\rangle |1\rangle,
\end{aligned}$$

we can see that if the ancillary qubits are projected to $|0\rangle |0\rangle$ (case a), then there was no error in any of the three qubits. If the ancillary qubits are projected to $|0\rangle |1\rangle$ (case b), then there was a phase-flip error in the third qubit. If the ancillary qubits are projected to $|1\rangle |0\rangle$ (case c), then there was an error in the second qubit. In these first-three cases, there is no need to apply an extra operation to recover the initial state $|\psi\rangle$ of qubit 1. However, if the ancillary qubits are projected to $|1\rangle |1\rangle$, then there was an error on the first qubit. To recover state $|\psi\rangle$, a σ_X gate has to be applied in the first qubit.

7 Quantum Error Correction Codes: The Nine-Qubit Quantum Error Correction Code

we have a code that corrects bit errors, corrects that σ_x errors, and makes σ_z errors three times as likely. we have a code that corrects σ_z errors and makes σ_x errors three times as likely. we can easily check if we have a σ_x error, it takes a logical 0 to logical 1 and vice versa. So, a σ_x error on any of the three-bit qubits flips the logical 0 and logical 1. So, we apply a σ_x to the logical qubit. So, we mean, this is we squeeze on the phase errors, we squeeze on the bit errors, the phase errors blow up. So, how do we fix this? Well, what we do is what is called

concatenation. Well, what we do is combine the two codes. So, that they fix both bit errors and phases errors. in classical coding theory, it is called concatenating the two codes. So, first, what we do is we encode the code with one of these codes. then, we encode each of the qubits in the remaining code with the other. So, a zero we will just write it down goes to $1/2$ to the $9/2$ 000 plus 111. Is $9/2$ the wrong $9/2$ is the wrong number. 1 over square root of 8 000 plus 111 000 plus 111. So, we are encoding one qubit into nine qubits. 1 goes to 1 over root 8 000 minus 111 000 minus 111 000 minus 111. So, to correct, first correct inner code. The inner code is just the bit error-correcting code, which means if there is a bit error, we correct it. Let us say we have a σ_x error, what happens on, let us say, the fifth qubit? we know we had 000, we had the first of these. Then 010 plus or minus 101 and then the third of these, depending on whether the plus or minus depending on whether we have a logical 0 or logical 1. we know how to correct this. we asked which bit is different, and then we flip that bit. σ_z error 5 error, 000 plus 111, so, these are we want to say that the fourth, fifth, and sixth bits go to 000 minus 111 on the fourth, fifth, sixth bits. Well, this is a logical 0, and this is a logical 1. So, really it is a logical error in the code. Well, not really, but we mean let us say this is 0_x and this is 1_x . So, we can think of a code that encodes a 0 like this and encodes a 1 like this. Now, what we have done is we have x goes to 0_x , 1_x , 0_x . Because we took the middle of these three triplets of qubits and we took it to its other thing, and if we call this 0_x and 1_x , this is just a bit error on the middle qubit. So, we can correct it. we correct it exactly the same way. we compare this state, this state, and this state and take the majority of them whether they have a plus or minus. we can write down a circuit for that, but we are not going to. Because it is rather complicated, and we not entirely sure how illuminating it is. However, we will make us do it on the homework. So, that is the nine-qubit code. So, so, far we have shown that the nine-qubit code can correct a σ_x error, and it can correct the σ_z error., in fact, it can correct a σ_y error, because a σ_y error is just a simultaneous σ_x error and σ_z error. the σ_x error-correcting the σ_x error here does not interfere with the σ_z error, so, we can correct that later. So, the nine-qubit code corrects one error of any well, if σ_x , σ_y , σ_z . But, there is lots and lots of errors that are not σ_x , σ_y , or σ_z . we mean, we could apply a Hadamard gate to one of the qubits. Does it correct that as well? Well, there is a theorem. we do not want to get rid of the base code, so, let us erase this. If we can correct identity any code had better be able to correct the no error σ_x , σ_y , σ_z on any qubit. Actually, we should not say the identity that is it is the identity of all the qubits. If we can σ_x , σ_y , or σ_z on any single qubit, we can correct anyone qubit error. we mean, we can take our qubit and just remove it and add a 1 in its place, and that gets corrected. Alternatively, we can make a Hadamard gate on it, or a rotation of any kind, or measure it, and they all get corrected. So, we only need to correct σ_x , σ_y , sigma z errors. we are going to demonstrate this for the phase code where it is basically it is if we can correct the identity or if we can correct no errors, and if we can correct a phase error on any qubit, we can correct any phase error. we mean, if we can correct σ_z on any qubit, we can correct any phase error on any qubit. this is very much related to the fact that this dephasing channel could also be done by making a small phase having a small phase error with probability $1/2$ and opposite phase error with probability $1/2$.

4. The Shor Code I: Implementation; The figure below shows the quantum circuit for the implementation of the Shor error correction code. This code is composed from the bit-flip (orange boxes), σ_X , and phase-flip (blue boxes), σ_Z , error correction codes. The quantum gate in each red box is called a Toffoli gate. This conditional gate applies a σ_X on the target qubit (\oplus) when both control qubits (solid black dots) are in the $|1\rangle$ state, and it leaves the state the same otherwise.

Figure 4: Shor code

Regarding the Shor quantum error correction code.

- The code can correct at most one bit-flip error.
- The code can correct a bit-flip and a phase-flip error, even if they occur on different qubits.
- The circuit at the left of the error encodes $|0\rangle_1$ into

$$|0_L\rangle = (|000\rangle_{123} + |111\rangle_{123}) (|000\rangle_{456} + |111\rangle_{456}) (|000\rangle_{789} + |111\rangle_{789}) / \sqrt{8}$$

- Although the code can correct for single bit-flip errors occurring simultaneously on different blocks, [1,2,3], [4,5,6], and [7,8,9], it cannot correct simultaneous phase-flip errors on different blocks.

Solution:

The Shor code can correct both bit-flip and phase-flip errors. In fact, it can correct one bit-flip error in each one of the three blocks [1,2,3], [4,5,6], and [7,8,9].

8 Computational Capacity: Communication Over Noise Wires

This computational capacity idea that we will describe sets the stage for describing how we can build a classical computer out of noisy components. We will describe that in terms of a concept known as a threshold. Then we will describe the principles which make this possible for classical computation. Then we will try to generalize that to the quantum case. We want to begin this journey with us by describing a computational capacity. The first idea we want to share with us is capacity, which came out in the field of communication. This is about communication channels. It is a seminal result by Shannon, Claude Shannon, from the 1940s. The scenario was that one had a communication link between two parties, but the communication link was noisy. So, the question to ask is, what is the maximum rate at which the two parties can communicate with each other despite the noise on this communication channel? Moreover, it is a fascinating idea of this wire plus noise. We ask ourselves, at what rate can we communicate? So, let us

think of this as the probability of error. It goes from 0 to 1 as a function of the rate at which we communicate over this wire. Think of this as being bits per second. We can use any other kind of measure of rate. We can imagine that if we start to speak faster and faster and faster and faster, then we probably cannot understand. Except we cannot talk very fast. However, we can still understand this way, yes? All right. However, there are others here who can speak much faster. The idea is that as we speak faster, the probability error goes up. We can believe that. We know, that means that if we speak at an intermediate rate, some of us will understand, and some of us will not. There will be a growing probability of error. This is quite reasonable, right? Moreover, what Shannon proved and showed the community that actually we can do much better than this. We can actually obtain asymptotically exponentially close to zero error for some rate of communication until we reach some magical point, called the capacity of the channel. This location reaching here is exponentially close to zero. This idea is one of the channel capacity. The reason we are able to do this is because of error correction codes. So, as long as the error rate is sufficiently low, we can, for example, repeat a message three times, repeat a message three times, repeat a message three times. As long as we do not speak too fast, if we caught it one of those or two of those three times, we could use, for example, majority voting to figure out what in the heck we meant, even though we were speaking fast. So, this is an idea about a discrete jump in the rate of a channel despite the error. So, this is pre-Shannon. This is Shannon.

9 Computational Capacity: Computation with Noisy Gates

Jon von Neumann asked, what would happen if we ask the same kind of question, not about communication, but now about computation? What if we have gates plus noise? Moreover, von Neumann asked this in the 1950s. He has this beautiful paper that we really find amazing. We recommend that we read this article by him titled Probabilistic Logics and the Synthesis of. This is fascinating because von Neumann, at this time, he was working with vacuum tube classical computers. People did not yet know if he could build a large-scale computer, classical computer. So, his model for all of this was not the fact that we had computers, but rather the fact that we had biology. Biological organisms like ourselves, who are composed of, we know rather fallible pieces. We know we are, at least. However, we can largely talk and walk and communicate with us fairly reliably despite being built out of unreliable parts. So, von Neumann asked about the probabilistic logics and the Synthesis of reliable organisms from unreliable components. Could we use whatever biology does to make reliability emerge out of unreliable parts and do the same out of, in his case, unreliable vacuum tubes? Furthermore, we think this is a fascinating question? We can draw the same kind of graph. Now, this is the probability of error of a circuit as a function of the probability of error of a component. As the probability of error of the components grows, and we are not going to give us any reliable components, for example. We would like us, nevertheless, to build a reliable system despite everything in it being unreliable—the gates, even the wires, but at least the gates. Every single gate in this construct, we are only allowed to use it with some failure probability. What von Neumann showed and argued is that we can have the same kind of capacity argument that we see over here. So, without doing any kind of strategic work, like error correction, we get a probability of error of a circuit, which grows as the probability of error of the component grows. However, if we construct our system appropriately, we can actually have something similar to Shannon's capacity. However, here we get a capacity, which is the computational capacity. This is the capacity of a set of noisy gates that compute some function with essentially no noise. It is fascinating. We do not use these ideas in today's computers because, largely, the semiconductors work with too much reliability. So, we do not need to assemble personal computers out of fallible personal computers. Although, we do at

the largest scales of cloud computing synthesize reliable systems out of unreliable networks of computers [43]. This is, for example, how Amazon Web Services and the Google Cloud Platform build their infrastructure out [44]. They assume that any a piece of it can fail and thus need to make the system reliable despite the system's components being unreliable. However, biology does this at a microscopic scale. Von Neumann asked the same question of the microscopic scale. It turns out that this is an essential idea to quantum computation because of the prevalence of noise at the level of gates in quantum computers. So, this is why we ask this question about fault tolerance. Let us give us a basic idea that von Neumann used. His basic idea was to assume that we have some circuit with the probability of error, and then we repeat it three times, for example. Then we correct. For example, we are using a majority voting gate. For now, let us assume that that is a perfect majority voting gate that does not fail. We can immediately see that the probability of error of this whole circuit is now something along the lines of 1 minus P error square. There are three choose two ways that we could fail and have the majority voting fail. So, this is very reasonable. This only communicates some of the principles behind it, however, because that is a flawed construction. We are not going to allow us a perfect component like a majority voting gate. Nevertheless, it gives us the idea that by using triple modular redundancy, we can start to increase the reliability of a system. So, issues, single-point failures like this one, we have to deal with that. We cannot allow such things to happen. This scheme also has no threshold. That is, there is not a single probability of failure of the gates, which we can say, would allow the system to scale to an arbitrary size. The idea here is that we might say that we want 1 minus P error square times 3 to be less than P error. Then we might say that this means something like P error is less than one third. That is a failure probability. Not 1 minus. So, this means that we have a reduction in error as long as the gate error probability is less than one third. However, then if we want to increase the size, it seems like that amount, that boundary continues to change. So, we are going to ask for something more. That thing will be what we will call a threshold.

5. Bit-Flip Code II: Before the Error; The figure below shows the quantum circuit for the implementation of the bit-flip quantum error correction code. What is the role of the controlled-NOT (CNOT) gates to the left of the error box (before the error occurs)?

Figure 5: Quantum circuit for a three-qubit bit-flip error correction code

- To entangle the first qubit with the second and third qubit.
- To encode the single-qubit state $|0\rangle$ in the three-qubit state $|0\rangle|0\rangle|0\rangle$.
- To encode the single-qubit state $|1\rangle$ in the three-qubit state $|1\rangle|1\rangle|1\rangle$.
- All of the above

6. Phase-Flip Code II: Before the error; The figure below shows the quantum circuit for implementation of the phase-flip quantum error correction code. What is the role of the three Hadamard gates to the left of the error box?

Figure 6: Quantum circuit for a three-qubit phase-flip error correction code

- To entangle the first qubit with the second and third qubit.
- To encode the single qubit state $|\psi\rangle$ in the three-qubit state $|0\rangle|0\rangle|0\rangle$.
- To encode the single qubit state $|\psi\rangle$ in the three-qubit state $|1\rangle|1\rangle|1\rangle$.
- To change the basis of each qubit from $\{|0\rangle, |1\rangle\}$ to $\{(|0\rangle + |1\rangle)/\sqrt{2}, (|0\rangle - |1\rangle)/\sqrt{2}\}$.

Solution:

A Hadamard gate is a single-qubit gate and therefore does not entangle two qubits. This also means that it can't encode a single-qubit state into a three-qubit entangled state.

Rather, the Hadamard gates perform a basis transformation. This transformation, in conjunction with the Hadamard gates that follow the error block and transform back to the original basis, enables phase flip errors to be treated in the same way as bit-flip errors.

7. Relationship Between Bit-Flips and Phase-Flips; The bit-flip and phase-flip error correction codes require coupling two ancillary qubits to the system. Given the state of interest

$$|\psi\rangle = \alpha |0\rangle + \beta |1\rangle, \quad (28)$$

the ancillary qubits are initialized in the $|0\rangle$ state, such that the initial three-qubit state is given by

$$|\psi_0\rangle = |\psi\rangle |0\rangle |0\rangle, = \alpha |0\rangle |0\rangle |0\rangle + \beta |1\rangle |0\rangle |0\rangle \quad (29)$$

This is done to find a possible error in the first qubit, given the measurement results in the ancillary qubits. Depending on the results of the measurement, one can know if there was an

error and how to correct it without losing the quantum information represented by state $|\psi\rangle$. These error correction codes can be divided into three sections.

Figure 7: Relation

The figure shows the general quantum circuit for the bit-flip (a) and phase-flip (b) error correction codes. In figure (a), the encoding is performed using the first-two CNOT gates. The error box corresponds to a σ_X (bit-flip) error., and the recovery is made using two CNOT gates to achieve decoding, followed by ancilla measurement.

In figure (b), the encoding is performed using a combination of CNOT gates and a Hadamard gate on each qubit. The error box corresponds to a σ_Z (phase-flip) error., and the recovery is also made using Hadamard and CNOT gates to achieve decoding, followed by ancilla measurement.

A bit-flip error can be mathematically described by

$$\sigma_X |0\rangle = |1\rangle, \sigma_X |1\rangle = |0\rangle, \quad (30)$$

with $\langle 0 | 1\rangle = 0$. The encoding takes the state $|0\rangle$ to $|0_L\rangle \equiv |0\rangle |0\rangle |0\rangle$ and $|1\rangle$ to $|1_L\rangle \equiv |1\rangle |1\rangle |1\rangle$.

A phase-flip error can be mathematically described by

$$\sigma_Z |+\rangle = |-\rangle, \sigma_Z |-\rangle = |+\rangle, \quad (31)$$

with

$$|\pm\rangle = \frac{|+\rangle \pm |-\rangle}{\sqrt{2}}, \quad (32)$$

and $\langle + | - \rangle = 0$. The encoding takes the state $|0\rangle$ to $|0_L\rangle \equiv |+\rangle |+\rangle |+\rangle$ and $|1\rangle$ to $|1_L\rangle \equiv |-\rangle |-\rangle |-\rangle$.

What is the relation between the bit-flip and phase-flip error correction codes?

- The phase-flip code is equivalent to the bit-flip code, since they both correct σ_X type of errors.
- The phase-flip code is equivalent to the bit-flip code since they both correct σ_Z type of errors.
- The phase-flip code is equivalent to the bit-flip code, since they both map

$$\begin{aligned} |0\rangle &\rightarrow |0_L\rangle \equiv |0\rangle |0\rangle |0\rangle \\ |1\rangle &\rightarrow |1_L\rangle \equiv |1\rangle |1\rangle |1\rangle \end{aligned}$$

- The phase-flip code is equivalent to the bit-flip code, since they both map

$$\begin{aligned} |0\rangle &\rightarrow |0_L\rangle \equiv |e_0\rangle |e_0\rangle |e_0\rangle \\ |1\rangle &\rightarrow |1_L\rangle \equiv |e_1\rangle |e_1\rangle |e_1\rangle \end{aligned}$$

where $\{|e_0\rangle, |e_1\rangle\}$ is a single-qubit basis $\langle e_0 | e_1 \rangle = 0$, where the basis is orthogonal to the direction of the error.

Solution:

The bit-flip and phase-flip codes map the $|0\rangle$ and $|1\rangle$ components of $|\psi\rangle$ in a similar manner. Specifically, in both codes, the encoding part of the circuits maps the single qubit states $|0\rangle$ and $|1\rangle$ to a three-qubit logical $|0_L\rangle$ and $|1_L\rangle$,

$$\begin{aligned} |0\rangle &\rightarrow |0_L\rangle \\ |1\rangle &\rightarrow |1_L\rangle \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, the difference between both codes is given by the basis in which the logical states $|0_L\rangle$ and $|1_L\rangle$ are defined. This is summarized on the table below.

Table 1: The phase-flip code equivalence to the bit-flip code

Error type	Initial State	Encoding Basis	Encoded State
σ_X	$ \psi\rangle 0\rangle 0\rangle$	$\{ 0\rangle, 1\rangle\}$	$\alpha 0\rangle 0\rangle 0\rangle + \beta 1\rangle 0\rangle 0\rangle$
σ_Z	$ \psi\rangle 0\rangle 0\rangle$	$\{ +\rangle, -\rangle\}$	$\alpha +\rangle +\rangle +\rangle + \beta -\rangle -\rangle -\rangle$

Note that the direction of the error (X and Z) is orthogonal to the basis for the encoded state: 0/1 (Z-axis) and +/- (X-axis), respectively.

8. The Shor Code II: Implementation; The Shor quantum error correction code can correct

- Single-qubit errors of the type σ_X
- Single-qubit errors of the type σ_Y
- Single-qubit errors of the type σ_Z
- All of the above

Solution:

The Shor quantum error correction code is a combination of the bit-flip (σ_X) and phase-flip (σ_Z) error-correction codes. Since $\sigma_Y = \sigma_Z\sigma_X$, the Shor code can correct any single-qubit error, provided there is at most one error.

9. The Shor Code III: The Role of Each Qubit; The figure below shows the quantum circuit for the implementation of the Shor error correction code. This code is composed from the bit-flip (σ_X) and phase-flip (σ_Z) codes. The “double wires” inside the red boxes represent the classical communication of the measurement results. The σ_X gate only is applied when both measurements give 1 as a result.

Figure 8: Quantum circuit for a nine-qubit Shor error correction code

How many measurements need to be done to correct an arbitrary error (X, Y, or Z) on state $|\psi\rangle$?

- Two measurements, qubits four and seven.
- Three measurements, qubits one, four, and seven.
- Six measurements, qubits two, three, five, six, eight, and nine.
- Eight measurements, qubits two, three, four, five, six, seven, eight, and nine.

Solution:

Qubits four and seven are measured to detect if there was a phase-flip error in the first qubit. Qubits two and three, five and six, and eight and nine are measured to detect if there was a bit-flip error in the first qubit. To detect an arbitrary single-qubit error in the first qubit, all the ancillary qubits have to measure.

10 How Can Reliable Classical and Quantum Machines be Built from Unreliable Components? Introduction

In order to be useful, large-scale computers, whether classical computers or quantum computers need to operate reliably for extended periods of time in the presence of noise. However, we know that quantum computers are built from qubits and that qubits are highly susceptible to noise. Now in section three, we considered noisy intermediate-scale quantum algorithms that would operate on uncorrected systems of qubits, basically until too many qubits fail. Although many factors will contribute to the realizable circuit depth for such algorithms, ultimately, uncorrected quantum computers will be limited by the quality of the individual qubits from which they are built. This means their coherence times, the rate at which gates can be applied, and, most importantly, their gate fidelity. In contrast, for large-scale quantum computers addressing larger-scale problems, we will need to run algorithms for much longer than the lifetimes of any individual physical qubits. To extend the operational time of quantum computers built from such intrinsically faulty devices, we will need to implement quantum error correction. In section one, we discussed at several simple examples of error-correcting codes that can improve quantum system reliability through the introduction of qubit redundancy and overhead. We discuss that if qubits individually are good enough, then one can improve the overall system performance by encoding quantum information in larger numbers of such qubits. That is, by adding more qubits that are good enough, the overall error rate can be decreased. The question is, how do we determine the threshold for good enough? Furthermore, once we have such qubits, how can we devise an error-correcting code that can handle errors that will certainly at some point occur, no matter where or when they occur, even when those errors might happen during the error detection protocol itself? In this section, we will begin to address these and related questions by discussing at the threshold theorem and the principles of fault tolerance for both classical and quantum computers.

11 Threshold Theorem for Fault-Tolerant Computation, Threshold Theorem: Introduction

What we are going to do first is to describe to us the threshold for classical computation. We will take von Neumann's core idea over here and try to explicitly tease out the ingredients that go into the fault tolerance of a classical computing system. Let us begin this journey by describing to us a theorem, which is going to define what we mean by a threshold for fault tolerance. This is a modern version of what von Neumann had described, and it will characterize what we wish the threshold to behave like in contrast to that argument given up there with the majority voting. What we will begin with is a family of circuits. For technical reasons, we will call this a uniform family. We will begin with a circuit that we wish to simulate. This circuit will have size n , so it will have error-free gates constructed in any which way we want. This describes the goal of the construction. So, we have a size, and we know that it is error-free. The theorem will state that we may simulate this error-free goal circuit with a certain probability of error bounded above by ϵ . Then, we need to say what it takes to simulate this, with what properties, what constraints. First, we will tell us how many gates are needed. That will be the order of $\log N$ over ϵ times N . This is an expression which means that the size of the simulating circuit and these are going to be gates which have some error, which we will describe in a moment must grow only logarithmically as 1 over the error desired. It must grow as the size of the circuit N . So, and this is very reasonable, this is actually a very aggressive scaling. This is very reasonable

that it is proportional to N . then, the main idea of this threshold theorem is that the simulation is done with this number of gates. They are error-prone gates. They fail with some probability, P . the theorem only holds as long as this error probability P is less than some other value p threshold, P_{th} . We ask that this threshold is independent of N and ϵ . So, we want a capacity here that works for arbitrary-sized circuits. That is the independence of N ., And we want it not to be a function of the error goal that we are discussing for. So, that means it is arbitrarily accurate in this sense.

10. Threshold Theorem I; Given a uniform circuit composed of N error-free gates, the Threshold Theorem stipulates that this circuit can be simulated by with an error probability less than ϵ and using

$$\mathcal{O} \left(\text{poly} \left(\log \frac{N}{\epsilon} \right) N \right) \quad (33)$$

gates, with each gate having the same error probability P . This is valid as long as the probability P is smaller than a threshold probability P_{th} .

The threshold probability P_{th} is a function that depends on:

- The number of gates that composed the circuit, N .
- The maximum error probability to simulate the error-free circuit, ϵ .
- The error probability of the gates, P .

Solution:

The threshold probability P_{th} is independent of the size of the circuit, implying that the circuit is scalable. It is also independent of the maximum error ϵ for which the error-free circuit can be simulated. Since the threshold probability sets a bound on how large the error probability P can be, while still being able to simulate the ideal circuit, it should not be a function of P .

12 Threshold Theorem: Proof Sketch

This is a sketch of the proof. We are not going to prove it rigorously. However, we will get the main idea here. We will do this on classical circuits and classical gates. The main idea is to compute on encoded data. Do not decode the data as we are going along. How do we do that? Well, we give us a bit of an idea over here with this triple modular redundancy. Let us formalize that a little bit by constructing this notation. This would be a NAND gate where the output will be x and y , barred, inverted. Then another gate, which we will call the majority voting gate. The output of this will be the majority of the inputs. Each one of these gates fails with probability P . we will assume, for simplicity, that they are all identical probabilities. We can clearly work this out in the case where there are non-identical probabilities of failure. The idea for the construction is to encode zero as three zeroes and one as three ones. So, we have this notion of the physical states and the logical states. Logical zero and logical one will be just the triple redundancy code. Now we want to perform a NAND gate operation on the logical states. However, what we will actually have coming in we are going to switch to A and B from x and y so that we can use x and y for some other things later is that we will have three wires representing A coming in and three wires representing B coming in. We will have three NAND gates. Each one of the NAND gates takes two inputs. We will route them like this. The output of this, unfortunately, may have an error because there may be errors in the input. The way we correct for them is instead of doing a single majority voting gate as we have up there, we will have three majority voting gates. These three let us assume that we can now copy information

from one wire to another. We will take inputs copied from each of the outputs of the NAND gates. Then we will have three outputs at the end. We claim that this output will be A and B inverted, where if there had been a single error in any of the inputs or if there had been a single gate failure, then we would have corrected that because of the majority voting. We can guarantee that there is, at most, one error in the output. Thus, the probability of failure of the output is going to be lower than P. What we have is a construction that has two parts. This first part is like a logical gate, a gate acting on the encoded data. The second part here is the error correction. We want to compute the probability of failure. We want to compute the probability of failure of this whole circuit construction. So, the output is incorrect only if two or more of the gates, the Ns and Ms fail. For simplicity, we are going to omit the discussion about the input errors from this. However, that also can be done. Let us assume what happens to analyze what happens when gates fail. So, if two or more gates fail, we can see, and this is a bound. So, if two gates happen to be good gates that fail, adding the same error, then the output is not going to be wrong. However, we can see that there are many ways in which, if two gates fail, the output definitely is wrong. Thus, let us bound that. The number of ways that two gates can fail is 6 choose 2 because there are six gates in this circuit. This is the number of possibilities. This is 6 times 5 divided by 2, which is 15. Thus, the probability of failure of a circuit is going to go like 15 P-squared. if the goal is to make this less than P, then we find that we could say that the threshold probability is 1 over 15. that is kind of remarkable because 1 over 15 is already better than, for example, one third. Now, there are some concerns about this. Again, we have to show us that we can make an arbitrarily sized circuit. Thus, far, we have done what we will call a level 1 encoding. So, the main idea that we are going to show we next is how we can recurse on this encoding and build a fault-tolerant circuit of arbitrary size. However, keep in mind that this argument about recursion is just one use for the proof. There are many other techniques by which we, in principle, could get to fault tolerance and to prove the theorem.

11. Failure Probabilities; Consider a circuit comprising four faulty gates, each with a probability P of an error. The failure probability of the circuit will depend on the number of fault paths and the number of gate errors. Calculate the failure probability to leading order in P for each of the following cases: (a) Exactly one of the four gates has an error. (b) Exactly two of the four gates have an error. (c) Exactly three of the four gates have an error. The answers below are listed in order (a), (b), and (c).

- Case (a): P, case (b): P^2 , and case (c) P^3 .
- Case (a): P, case (b): $15P^2$, case (c) and $20P^3$.
- Case (a): $4P$, case (b): $6P^2$, and case (c): $4P^3$.
- Case (a): $4P$, case (b): $15P^2$, and case (c): $20P^3$.

Solution:

Given a circuit composed of N gates, each with an error probability P, the probability that exactly j gates fail to leading order in P is given by:

$$P_{\text{fail}} = (\text{number of fault paths}) \times P^j,$$

where $p^j(1 - P)^{N-j} \approx P^j$ is the leading-order probability that exactly j gates fail, and the number of fault paths is

$$\binom{N}{j} = \frac{N!}{j!(N-j)!}.$$

If the circuit has exactly one gate error, $j = 1$, its failure probability is

$$P_{\text{fail}} = \frac{4!}{1!(4-1)!} \times P^1 = 4P. \text{ If the circuit has exactly two gate errors, } j = 2, \text{ its failure probability is}$$

$$P_{\text{fail}} = \frac{4!}{2!(4-2)!} \times P^2 = 6P^2.$$

If the circuit has exactly three gate errors, $j=3$, its failure probability is $P_{\text{fail}} = \frac{4!}{3!(4-3)!} \times P^3 = 4P^3$.

13 Threshold Theorem: Recursion

So, let us recurse and see what happens if we do the same thing now recursively. What we want to do is to repeat the encoding now and let 0 be mapped to 000 000 000 and 1 be mapped to nine 1's. There are three groups in this. So, we can actually see what we have done is repeat and encode 000 by repeating that three times. Thus, this recursive step that we about to show we could be repeated again and again. Thus, we will get a system, which shows what happens when we scale to a large number of gates. This construction is very simple to imagine and is a little tedious to draw. So, what we will have is this will be A, and this will be B coming in. We will have three big blocks here. In each one of these three big blocks, we are going to have the same construction with six gates that we just showed us on the other board. Each one of these will output three wires and take six wires in. So, the way this works is we get part of A coming in over here, over here, over here, over here, over here, and so, forth. now, this is the encoded gate. We will subsequently also perform this is three blocks of Ms., And this is the error correction step. So, just like the construction that we discuss over there, what we are now going to do is to copy these three over in the appropriate ways. So, this one goes here, and it also goes here, it also goes here. This one goes here, and it also goes here. It also goes here, and so, on and so forth. Here is where we start to scribble. However, we get the idea. What we are going to get out is 123456789. these nine outputs are going to give we, in total, A and B negated. Good. Thus, this is a recursive structure. What we want to do is to calculate the probability of failure of this recursive structure. We want to write this formula out in a nice way for us. So, we can see that the output is incorrect only if two blocks of gates fail. So, this is the identical language that we used in the previous construction. There are 6 choose 2 ways of having blocks fail. Thus, the probability of failure goes as 15 times 15 P-squared quantity squared. However, let us write that in a nicer way. Let us get, now, a recursive formula for the error probability of this cascaded, concatenated data sequence. What we have up there is that Pfail goes as 15 P-squared squared. It is nice to write this as 15P to the fourth power, divide by 15. Because we claim that if we continue this recursion, then we can expand on this pattern that we have. At level one, we had that Pfail times C and if we define C as being the number of fault paths. In this case, above, it is 15. So, we have C times Pfail. This is the number C, which we moved over to the left-hand side is equal to C times P-squared. At level two, C Pfail is equal to CP to the 2 to the 2. At level three, if we kept on doing the same thing, we would find that CPfail is equal to C times P to the 2 to the 3. So, it would go square, fourth power, and eighth power, and then 16, 64. the nice thing about this is that we can write down a formula for the extent of how this goes at the case-level recursion. C times Pfail will be C P to the two to the k power. The idea of fault tolerance is that this is growing exponentially, or doubly exponentially, and thus, as long as P is less than 1 over C, then this probability of failure goes to 0 very rapidly as we increase the level of recursion doubly exponentially rapidly. This is part of the idea of this computational capacity that it goes so rapidly to zero.

12. $k=1$ Level of Recursion; Consider an encoded circuit with only one level of recursion ($k=1$) that is composed of N faulty gates, each with a probability P . The circuit can correct for one error, and it will fail for two or more errors. To leading order in P , we are therefore concerned with the probability that exactly two gate errors occur. If C is the number of fault paths, and P_{th} is the threshold probability of the circuit, then

- The number of fault paths is at least $C = \binom{N}{2} = \frac{N!}{2!(N-2)!}$.
- The threshold probability is proportional to the number of fault paths.
- If P is less than P_{th} , then the net failure probability of the circuit is less than P .
- The failure probability of the circuit is approximately given by the product of C and P^2

14 Threshold Theorem: Reliable Classical Computation

Let us draw the probability of failure that we get from this formula as a function of the probability of failure of the gates. So, what we have is P_{fail} of the circuit as a function of the P error probability of the individual gates. If there is no error correction, it is just a straight line. If we have one level of recursion, it is this parabola that we are $15p$ -squared. then we get a quartic and then the fourth power and so forth. So, it gets steeper and steeper as we reach this point. That is the threshold, P_{th} . So, remember, this is going as 1 over C ., And this is a threshold which is independent of N and ϵ , exactly as we desire in the theorem that is given above here. This is really a remarkable property to be able to have. So, we have been describing this for classical circuits. We can actually go and make these classical circuit constructions. Let us give us some actual numbers. From von Neumann and his works in the 1950s, we have that the threshold probability is at least 0.073 . there is a catch to this because von Neumann used three-input gates. His construction did not quite use all of the same kinds of strong assumptions that we require, such as no gates with zero error probability. However, this is what it largely translates into. Following that, it was quite a long time between then and the next result. This is from Hajek and Weller, from about 1991. they found a different construction, giving 0.167 about one over six. Again, there is a caveat to this. This was also using three in gates. We can see what we have done here is with NAND gates. It would be nice to know what the threshold for NAND gates is because NAND gates are universal for classical computation. We figure that if we are asking this question using three input gates, we are making a larger assumption about it because we have more capability with three input gates. So, in 1998, Evans and Pippenger, they came up with an interesting bound, which is approximately 0.089 . Notice how this is worse than the three-input case bound here. However, this was for two input gates. Then similar to that, Evans and Pippenger again, in 2008, proved an interesting upper bound on P_{th} . This is fascinating. It is on k input. Their expression is one-half minus one over two square roots of k , like this. We can imagine why there is a one half in that expression immediately because we can just guess what the answer is. So, ideally, we would like this to be as high as possible, as low as possible because we would like to be able to have the lowest threshold to have to cross to be, we would like the highest possible error failure rate. Thus, we would like that. Would it not be great if we could compute everything with gates that failed with 75% probability? So, that is not going to happen. Thus, we can imagine, well, how about a gate that fails with a 50% probability? Well, then it is going just to output noise all the time. How about 0.499 probability? Well, it is close as k gets large here. So, but nobody can show that this is realizable. All right, so, this is a story with classical fault tolerance. What we want to take away from this message is that there is a process with a set of principles for fault tolerance. We would like to try now to abstract away those principles and try to apply them to quantum computation.

15 Principles of Fault Tolerance: Summary

What are the principles under which we were able to construct a theorem about fault tolerance? We want to abstract a series of ideas from this construction so that we can see if we can apply them to the quantum circuit case. We contend that one of the main ideas behind this theorem and construction is that we have arrived at this expression for a threshold, which reads as 1 over the number of fault paths. Here, we are defining the ideal fault paths as being the number of ways by which we can combine failure probabilities to make the circuit system fail. We are not defining it formally, but we have gotten the idea. However, one of the key things is that this is the number of fault paths in a universal gate construction. For example, we could not have made just an inverter and then expected to extrapolate and get a threshold probability, because the inverter by itself is not universal. So, we use a NAND gate. We know from classical Boolean algebra that any Boolean function can be constructed out of NAND gates, composed appropriately. So, we need to consider a family of universal gates or at least one gate from which any circuit can be constructed. The second idea is that this has to be in a fault-tolerant procedure [18, 45–47]. The concept of a fault-tolerant procedure is something that we now want to be able to describe. Let us define this. This is essentially going to be the concept of how we control error propagation and minimize the number of fault paths. Let us reverse this logic. We are going to say a procedure is fault-tolerant if a single component failure, like one of the NAND gates or one of the majority voting gates, must not cascade and cause more errors that we cannot correct. So, we will say that a procedure is fault-tolerant if a single component failure causes at most one error in each encoded block of bits in the output. There are two main ideas here. First, the reason we are focusing on one error is that we are discussing only currently in the discussion at codes correcting one error. We can choose other higher rate codes that can correct for more errors, and then generalize this theorem. The reason we are thinking about each encoded block is that each one of the data blocks is a separate code right now. We could also conceive of encoding all of the data with multiple bits inside one code. That also changes this definition, but we can generalize it again fairly easily. So, for example, in the construction up here, this has one output block. However, we might have a different construction with two output blocks, and we would only want a maximum of one error in each one of those blocks separately. So, this is all about error propagation.

13. Fault-Tolerant Procedure; According to the section above, a procedure is a fault-tolerant if:

- It controls error propagation and minimizes the number of fault paths.
- A failure causes at most one error in each encoded block of bits.
- There is at most one fault path in which two gates can fail, meaning that the error-correcting code fails.
- When a failure occurs, it does not cascade into more errors as the calculation continues.

Solution:

A procedure is a fault-tolerant if a single component (such as a majority gate) failure causes at most one error in each encoded block of bits in the output. In other words, if a failure occurs, it should not cascade into more errors as the calculation continues. The number of fault path sets the threshold probability, but it does not determine if a procedure is fault-tolerant or not.

16 Principles of Fault Tolerance: Fault-Tolerance and Non-Fault-Tolerant Procedures

Let us describe some examples of fault-tolerant procedures and what are non-fault-tolerant procedures. Suppose we want to compute a NOT function. These will be poor ways of doing them, and these will be good or fault-tolerant ways of doing that. So, again, let us imagine that we encode in the triple redundancy code. So, we have a number, A, that comes in, and then, we perform three NOT gates. If we run through a single majority voting gate and then copy the output three times, this is no good because there is a single point of failure. This violates the idea here that a single component failure causes at most one error in the output. So, we found, as we discuss an example, that a good way of doing this fault-tolerantly is to have three majority voting gates, like so, and this, then, is a fault-tolerant procedure. If we have multiple bits do something and now let us start to use some of the quantum computing circuit terminology, and we want to compute a controlled-NOT gate, classically still, but using quantum circuit drawing, this is either 000 or 111 when it is encoded. So, clearly, if we wanted to, we could just perform a controlled-NOT gate by using the top bit because they are all supposed to be the same. Thus, if there were no errors, this would be the perfectly fine controlled-NOT gate between two blocks. However, clearly, if this wire failed, we would have another single-point failure, so it is not a fault-tolerant procedure. Instead, one of the canonical ideas behind fault tolerance is to separate gates off into different bits. This construction is called transversal gate constructions. It just means do our gates bitwise in parallel. This, then, allows errors only to propagate between the bits that are interacting together. We will use the same idea for the quantum circuit constructions that are fault-tolerant.

14. Single Point of Failure; Which of the following sentences are correct about a “single point of failure”?

- It is a part of the circuit that, when a failure occurs, causes the entire process to fail.
- It is challenging but possible to create a fault-tolerant procedure with a single point of failure.
- When designing a fault-tolerant procedure, single-point failures must be avoided.

Solution:

It is impossible to have a fault-tolerant procedure with a single point of failure, since one error in such a part of the circuit cascades to more errors, causing the process to fail.

17 Circuit Size of Fault-Tolerant Procedures

One of the key things we have not shown we yet are the cost of fault tolerance. So, remember that the fault tolerance theorem has this order of $\text{polylog } N$ over ϵ times N in the expression for the cost of the fault tolerance. Let us try to prove that now. How many erroneous error-prone gates do we require to construct an error-free circuit system? we want the overhead of this construction to be very low $\text{polylog } 1$ over ϵ . we have not shown that yet, but now we can do so, So, we discuss that if we have a circuit size d for the fault-free construction, using this recursive construction that we had to increase the size of the circuit. it goes approximately it has d to the k -th power. So, the circuit size, when we make it a fault-tolerant procedure, grows to d to the k , where k is the number of levels of recursion. Remember we showed we instead of

1 NAND gate, we went to 3, and then from 3 to 9. then after that, it would be 81, and so forth. So, this is the increase in that size that grows exponentially. So, what we need to do is to be able to compute the size of the number of levels of recursion needed. So, if the goal is to simulate an N gate circuit with the probability of failure bounded above by some epsilon remember that is the statement of the theorem then each gate we would like to simulate with the probability of failure N over epsilon divided by N . So, we can split this error probability up and proportion it to each one of the gates so, they will add up at worst using the triangle inequality. thus, if we have, again, let C be the number of fault paths, then we find that the equation we have is C times P fail is CP to the 2 to the k , as the scaling formula for the recursive construction. let us define P_{th} as 1 over C . Then, we can rewrite this equation in a really neat way. This is the way we like to remember the threshold theorem. P fail over P_{th} that is just this 1 over C over here is equal to P over P_{th} to the 2 to the k . think of this as the central equation of fault tolerance, at least using the recursive construction. this allows us to solve for k . So, the plugin that we would like P fail of a gate to be, well, less than epsilon divided by N . then we can plug this in here and solve for k , and we would get that k is equal to let us write this as an exponential 2 to the k is equal to the log of epsilon divided by $N P_{th}$ divided by the log of P divided by P_{th} . So, this is fairly straightforward. we do not want through the algebra right here, but we want to show we the implication of having solved the formula here. By the way, there is a reason this is going to work out. The reason is that the circuit size is growing exponentially, but the failure probability of the circuit is going down doubly exponentially. So, this goes down much faster than this grows, even though this exponential cost looks very worrisome. So, we only need a very few levels of recursion, k , in order to be able to kill this error probability sufficiently rapidly with a small-sized circuit. So, the number of levels the recursion required is going to be fairly small. See all these logarithms over here. thus, we can solve and find the circuit size. So, lets actually work out that formula for we. we said it is d to the k . d to the k is the same thing as 2 to the k , just changing the base of the exponential. So, this is how we are going to rewrite this in a little better way by factoring out some things. By the way, the circuit size is actually N times d to the k . So, it is going to be N times log of N over epsilon P_{th} divided by log of P_{th} divided by P . we have inverted the top and bottom logarithm functions by using a minus sign it cancels to the log of base 2 of d . although this looks like a rather complex formula, this is actually N times a polynomial in the logarithm of 1 over epsilon N over epsilon. Because this is the key term here N over epsilon to some power. Everything else in there is not going to scale with N or epsilon. thus, this proves the theorem that we had set out to do. we have a logarithmically sized circuit required to become fault-tolerant as long as the probability of error is less than this threshold probability. This is really phenomenal., by the way, we believe we should probably build all of the future classical systems using this kind of idea. we really should be building the classical logic circuits out of very cheap, low threshold, deep subthreshold silicon chips which are built out of cheap fabrication facilities instead of billion-dollar, GDP size, large, perfect. So, instead of zero defect as a philosophy, allow there to be some probability of failure. just design the system in a clever way so that we get fault tolerance. Now, in the world of quantum computation [48], this is not just a desirable philosophy. It is a necessary philosophy. Because we do not know any other way to reduce errors in quantum systems until they are tolerable. So, we now want to tell us about the story for fault tolerance for quantum computation.

18 Threshold for Quantum Computation: Fault-Tolerant Quantum Procedures

we would like to know what is the maximum error that we can tolerate in the quantum gates and still build an arbitrarily sized, arbitrary low error quantum circuit out of those noisy gates. The ideas that we have seen for the principles of fault-tolerance here are going to apply almost directly to the quantum case, but there are some challenges. So, what we want to be able to do is to say that we have some threshold for quantum, which is one over the number of fault paths. However, again, this has to be in a universal gate, and we want to do this in a fault-tolerant procedure, which means that we want to compute on encoded data, which is now quantum. This idea of computing on encoded quantum data means, in this case, we will use stabilizer codes [31], and the gates are normalizer operations, as we have seen in the last few sections. However, because we need this to be a universal gate, this means more than just Clifford gates because of the Gottesman-Knill theorem, which says that all stabilizer circuits and Clifford gates can be efficiently simulated on a classical computer. They are not universal for quantum computation. So, we will need a gate that is outside of the Clifford set, and so, we can remind ourselves that the normalizer of a stabilizer is a set of all gates in the set that we are starting out with. For example, polys let us denote that as g such that ghg dagger is in the stabilizer for all h in the stabilizer set. This is the polys for this first discussion, but we may also generalize this and define some normalizer on some unitaries instead, where this becomes some arbitrary unitary instead. So, there are codes that have generalized normalizers that are outside of the poly group and outside of the Clifford group.

The stabilizer formalism is a method used to design and implement quantum error detection and correction. A stabilizer is composed of a set of gates that leave a particular group of quantum states unaffected, and then the group is said to be “stabilized”. A stabilizer applied to a quantum state that is not part of this group, for example, due to a single-qubit error in a logical qubit, is left altered and, hence, no longer “stabilized”. This principle can be used to detect unwanted modifications of the stabilized group of quantum states.

The 3-qubit bit-flip code we introduced previously and, in particular, the parity measurements can be described within the stabilizer formalism. As we discussed previously, the logical encoding uses three physical qubits to form the codeword states $|000\rangle$ and $|111\rangle$. These can then be used to form a logically encoded superposition state.

$$|0\rangle_L = |000\rangle \quad |1\rangle_L = |111\rangle \quad \rightarrow \quad \alpha|0\rangle_L + \beta|1\rangle_L. \quad (34)$$

Recall that the 3-qubit bit-flip code is composed of two sequential parity measurements. The parity operations are performed on qubits 1 and 2, and then on qubits 2 and 3. The results are stored on two ancilla qubits. Measuring the ancilla qubits provides two classical bits, the parity of each qubit pair, and these together form a syndrome. The syndrome values indicate the presence and location of up to one bit-flip error. Recall that a parity operation and measurement has the special property that it only indicates whether the two qubits are in the same state or in different states. It, therefore, does not destroy the quantum information.

Let us consider the ancilla qubit measurements in more detail. The ancilla qubit corresponding to qubits 1 and 2, for example, stores the parity of qubits 1 and 2., measuring the ancilla yields the parity, as described above. Is there another way we can think about this in the context of qubits 1 and 2?

In general, a qubit measured in the computational basis that is, along the Bloch sphere’s z-axis, will output eigenvalues ± 1 of the observable Z , depending on the state of the qubit. If

the qubit is projected on the positive z-axis, a +1 results are indicating state $|0\rangle$. In contrast, if the qubit is projected on the negative z-axis, a -1 results indicating $|1\rangle$.

Now, let us consider the observable Z_1Z_2 on qubits 1 and 2. Note, this does not represent two independent measurements of Z_1 and Z_2 ; that would clearly project out the qubit states. Rather, we can think of it as one measurement of a new observable comprising both Z_1 and Z_2 . If both qubits are in-state $|0\rangle$, the measurement output is $(+1)(+1) = 1$. And, if both qubits are in-state $|1\rangle$, the measurement output is $(-1)(-1) = 1$. Similarly, we see that if the qubits are in different states, we get a measurement output of -1. Thus, we see that Z_1Z_2 is essentially the parity operation. Implementing an ancilla parity measurement is essentially equivalent to measuring the observable Z_1Z_2 . Moreover, the same is true for Z_2Z_3 . Consequently, the “stabilizers” of the 3-qubit bit-flip code are Z_1Z_2 and Z_2Z_3 . These operations “stabilize” the logical qubit $\alpha|0\rangle_L + \beta|1\rangle_L$.

The following table summarizes the expectation values of the stabilizers and shows that they are equivalent to the measurement of the ancilla qubits.

Table 2: The expectation values of the stabilizers

logical qubit	$\langle Z_1Z_2 \rangle$	$\langle Z_2Z_3 \rangle$	ancillas	Measurement
$ \psi\rangle_0 = \alpha 000\rangle + \beta 111\rangle$	${}_0\langle\psi Z_1Z_2 \psi\rangle_0 = 1$	${}_0\langle\psi Z_2Z_3 \psi\rangle_0 = 1$	$ 00\rangle_A$	1 1
$ \psi\rangle_1 = \alpha 100\rangle + \beta 011\rangle$	${}_1\langle\psi Z_1Z_2 \psi\rangle_1 = -1$	${}_1\langle\psi Z_2Z_3 \psi\rangle_1 = 1$	$ 10\rangle_A$	-1 1
$ \psi\rangle_2 = \alpha 010\rangle + \beta 101\rangle$	${}_2\langle\psi Z_1Z_2 \psi\rangle_2 = -1$	${}_2\langle\psi Z_2Z_3 \psi\rangle_2 = -1$	$ 11\rangle_A$	-1 -1
$ \psi\rangle_3 = \alpha 001\rangle + \beta 110\rangle$	${}_3\langle\psi Z_1Z_2 \psi\rangle_3 = 1$	${}_3\langle\psi Z_2Z_3 \psi\rangle_3 = -1$	$ 01\rangle_A$	1 -1

The working principles of the 3-qubit bit-flip code can be captured with the stabilizers Z_1Z_2 and Z_2Z_3 . Similarly, the 3-qubit phase-flip code is described with its two stabilizers X_1X_2 and X_2X_3 . The reader is encouraged to show that these two stabilizers are an equivalent description of the 3-qubit phase-flip quantum error detection mechanism presented in an earlier text unit.

The utility of the stabilizer formalism becomes clearer for more complicated error correction codes. One example is the 5-qubit code, proposed by Raymond Laflamme, Cesar Miquel, Juan Pablo Paz, and Wojciech Zurek. The 5-qubit quantum error correction code requires the minimum number of physical qubits to correct one single arbitrary Pauli error (either a bit-flip, a phase-flip, or their combination) [49].

The stabilizers referred to as “generators” of the 5-qubit code are:

$$\begin{aligned}
g_1 &= XZZXI \\
g_2 &= IXZZX \\
g_3 &= XIXZZ \\
g_4 &= ZXIXZ.
\end{aligned}$$

The stabilized quantum state representing the logical qubits $|0\rangle_L$ and $|1\rangle_L$, also referred to as logical code words $|0\rangle_L$ and $|1\rangle_L$, are then.

$$\begin{aligned}
|0\rangle_L &= \frac{1}{4}(|00000\rangle + |10010\rangle + |01001\rangle + |10100\rangle \\
&\quad + |01010\rangle - |11011\rangle - |00110\rangle - |11000\rangle \\
&\quad - |11101\rangle - |00011\rangle - |11110\rangle - |01111\rangle \\
&\quad - |10001\rangle - |01100\rangle - |10111\rangle + |00101\rangle)
\end{aligned} \tag{35}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
|1\rangle_L &= \frac{1}{4}(|11111\rangle + |01101\rangle + |10110\rangle + |01011\rangle \\
&\quad + |10101\rangle - |00100\rangle - |11001\rangle - |00111\rangle \\
&\quad - |00010\rangle - |11100\rangle - |00001\rangle - |10000\rangle \\
&\quad - |01110\rangle - |10011\rangle - |01000\rangle + |11010\rangle)
\end{aligned} \tag{36}$$

Suppose the first qubit of quantum state $|0\rangle_L$ experiences a bit flip on the first qubit, $X_1I_2I_3I_4I_5$. The “generator” g_4 anti-commutes with the erroneous quantum operation and yields a -1 for the error state.

$$\begin{aligned}
|0\rangle_f = X_1I_2I_3I_4I_5|0\rangle_L &= \frac{1}{4}(|10000\rangle + |00010\rangle + |11001\rangle + |00100\rangle \\
&\quad + |11010\rangle - |01011\rangle - |10110\rangle - |01000\rangle \\
&\quad - |01101\rangle - |10011\rangle - |01110\rangle - |11111\rangle \\
&\quad - |00001\rangle - |11100\rangle - |00111\rangle + |10101\rangle)
\end{aligned} \tag{37}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
g_1 : (XZZXI)(XIII)|0\rangle_L &= (XIII)(XZZXI)|0\rangle_L \rightarrow_f \langle 0|XZZXI|0\rangle_f \\
&= +1
\end{aligned} \tag{38}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
g_2 : (IXZZX)(XIII)|0\rangle_L &= (XIII)(IXZZX)|0\rangle_L \rightarrow_f \langle 0|IXZZX|0\rangle_f \\
&= +1
\end{aligned} \tag{39}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
g_3 : (XIXZZ)(XIII)|0\rangle_L &= (XIII)(XIXZZ)|0\rangle_L \rightarrow_f \langle 0|XIXZZ|0\rangle_f \\
&= +1
\end{aligned} \tag{40}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
g_4 : (ZXIXZ)(XIII)|0\rangle_L &= -(XIII)(ZXIXZ)|0\rangle_L \rightarrow_f \langle 0|ZXIXZ|0\rangle_f \\
&= -1
\end{aligned} \tag{41}$$

Classical processing of the generator measurements the error syndrome reveals the erroneous physical qubit. Subsequently, the error can be corrected with a feed-forward counteracting quantum operation. The reader is encouraged to explore the working principles of the 5-qubit quantum error correction code in case of a phase-flip.

The stabilizer formalism enables the description and comparison of many quantum error correction codes beyond the 3-qubit bit-flip, 3-qubit phase flip, and 5-qubit codes referred to as stabilizer codes. The interested reader may read the following section on the stabilizer formalism and a more mathematical discussion of it [50].

19 Stabilizers (Advanced)

Stabilizer codes are an important class of quantum error correction codes based on the stabilizer formalism. The stabilizer formalism provides a general method for designing and implementing quantum error detection in support of error correction. A stabilizer is a configuration of operators that leave a particular group of quantum states untouched. However, for quantum states that are not part of this group, the stabilizer will effectively apply a “label” that identifies the state as being outside of the original set. This principle can be used to detect when changes, i.e., errors occur to codeword quantum states.

The stabilizer formalism is based on the Pauli group G_n for n qubits. The Pauli group for a single qubit can be expressed as $G_1 \equiv \{\pm I, \pm iI, \pm X, \pm iX, \pm Y, \pm iY, \pm Z, \pm iZ\}$. G_n is composed of all n -fold tensor products of the Pauli matrices forming G_1 .

To give an example, Let us consider the Bell state $|\Phi^+\rangle = 1/\sqrt{2}(|00\rangle + |11\rangle)$. Note that this may be viewed as qubits 1 and 2 from the discussion of the three-qubit bit-flip code. As we discuss previously, applying the operators X_1X_2 and Z_1Z_2 will leave the state $|\Phi^+\rangle$ unchanged:

$$\begin{aligned} X_1X_2|\Phi^+\rangle &= X_1X_2 \frac{|00\rangle + |11\rangle}{\sqrt{2}} = \frac{|00\rangle + |11\rangle}{\sqrt{2}} = |\Phi^+\rangle \\ Z_1Z_2|\Phi^+\rangle &= Z_1Z_2 \frac{|00\rangle + |11\rangle}{\sqrt{2}} = \frac{|00\rangle + |11\rangle}{\sqrt{2}} = |\Phi^+\rangle \end{aligned} \quad (42)$$

The operators are thus said to “stabilize” the state.

Suppose S is a subspace of G_2 with $S \equiv \{I_1I_2, X_1X_2, Z_1Z_2\}$. Then, the vector space V_S stabilized by S consists of $|\Phi^+\rangle$. The subspace S can be expressed in terms of its generators, a reduced set of operators that can be used to generate the elements of S . For example, the generators of S are $\langle X_1X_2, Z_1Z_2 \rangle$, since $I_1I_2 = (X_1X_2)(X_1X_2)$ or $I_1I_2 = (Z_1Z_2)(Z_1Z_2)$. Thus, it is sufficient to define S solely by its generators, $S \equiv \langle X_1X_2, Z_1Z_2 \rangle$, where we now use the $\langle \dots \rangle$ symbol to indicate that this lists only the generators of S . If a quantum state is stabilized by all generators of a group S , then all elements of group S including those derived from the generators will also stabilize this particular state.

There are two conditions for S to stabilize a non-trivial vector space, that is, a vector space spanned by non-zero vectors. First, $-I$ cannot be an element of S , due to the fact that $-I|\psi\rangle = -|\psi\rangle$ is only valid for the trivial case, $|\psi\rangle = 0$. And, second is that the elements of S commute. Two operators (or, sets of operators) commute if their order of operation does not affect the outcome. For example, the stabilizers g_1 and g_2 commute if $g_1g_2 - g_2g_1 = 0 \rightarrow g_1g_2 = g_2g_1$. To see why stabilizers must commute, consider an alternative case in which the two stabilizers happen to anti-commute, that is $g_1g_2 + g_2g_1 = 0 \rightarrow g_1g_2 = -g_2g_1$. In this case, $g_1g_2|\psi\rangle = -g_2g_1|\psi\rangle$, and so the stabilizers would label the state $|\psi\rangle$ depending on the order in which they were applied, and this should not happen; the result of applying stabilizers should depend on the state, and not on the order of operation. If g_1 and g_2 were anti-commuting stabilizers, it would follow that $-|\psi\rangle = |\psi\rangle$, which again can only be true for the trivial case.

Now, consider a bit-flip error I_1X_2 , which leaves qubit 1 alone and flips the state of qubit 2. I_1X_2 commutes with stabilizer X_1X_2 , but it anti-commutes with Z_1Z_2 :

$$\begin{aligned} (X_1X_2)(I_1X_2) \frac{|00\rangle + |11\rangle}{\sqrt{2}} &= \frac{|01\rangle + |10\rangle}{\sqrt{2}} \\ \& (I_1X_2)(X_1X_2) \frac{|00\rangle + |11\rangle}{\sqrt{2}} &= \frac{|01\rangle + |10\rangle}{\sqrt{2}} \\ (Z_1Z_2)(I_1X_2) \frac{|00\rangle + |11\rangle}{\sqrt{2}} &= -\frac{|01\rangle + |10\rangle}{\sqrt{2}} \\ \& (I_1X_2)(Z_1Z_2) \frac{|00\rangle + |11\rangle}{\sqrt{2}} &= \frac{|01\rangle + |10\rangle}{\sqrt{2}} \end{aligned} \quad (43)$$

Thus, we see that applying the unitary bit-flip operator, an operation that takes a state within V_S , and puts it outside V_S , affects the results when applying the stabilizers of V_S (as we

would expect). More generally, applying a unitary gate U on a state vector $|\psi\rangle$ consequently affects the generators of the associated stabilizer group. The new state $U|\psi\rangle$ is an element in a new vector space UV_S , and it is stabilized by the generator UgU^\dagger , which follows from $U|\psi\rangle = Ug|\psi\rangle = UgU^\dagger U|\psi\rangle$.

The dynamics of a quantum state can be described by the evolution of the generators of the stabilizer group for a specific set of unitary quantum gates. Unitary gates mapping stabilizers to stabilizers are referred to as normalizers of G_n and form the Clifford group. It can be shown that the CNOT, Hadamard, and phase gate can compose all examples of gates that are able to map elements of G_n to G_n . The set of gates U complying with $UG_nU^\dagger = G_n$ are called the normalizer gates $N(G_n)$.

$$U_{CNOT} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad U_{Hadamard} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 \\ 1 & -1 \end{pmatrix} \quad U_{phase} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & i \end{pmatrix} \quad (44)$$

For example a CNOT gate applied to $|\Phi^+\rangle$ and to the generator X_1X_2 alter the generators in the following way:

$$U_{CNOT} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix} = U_{CNOT}^\dagger \quad (45)$$

$$X_1X_2 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \rightarrow U_{CNOT} X_1X_2 U_{CNOT}^\dagger = X_1I_2$$

Not all unitary gates are normalizers of G_n . For example, the T gate, a gate often added to the Clifford gates to form universal quantum gate sets, is not a normalizer of G_n . Relatedly, the Gottesman-Knill theorem states that quantum circuits can be classically efficiently simulated if the three following conditions are true:

1. Quantum states are prepared in the computational basis. For example a single qubit in $|0\rangle$.
2. Quantum operations are composed of elements of the Pauli group, CNOT, Hadamard, and phase gate.
3. Only measurements of Pauli observables are required. For example, a measurement in the computational basis for a single qubit and, thus, the observable Z with $\langle 0|Z|0\rangle \rightarrow 1$ and $\langle 1|Z|1\rangle \rightarrow -1$, is in this category.

The stabilizer formalism can entirely describe quantum circuits complying with the three conditions. A single quantum operation acting on an n-qubit state represented by an n-element stabilizer requires n^2 classical computational steps (due to conjugation). Consequently, a classical simulation of a quantum circuit with n qubits and m quantum operations requires $\mathcal{O}(n^2m)$ classical computational steps. Note, since the stabilizer formalism does not fully describe universal gate sets, it cannot be used as a method to simulate universal quantum computation [51] with a classical computer efficiently. Nevertheless, the description of many quantum error correction and detection codes can be accomplished using the stabilizer formalism and, in particular, the normalizer gates.

Now, let us introduce the concept of how the stabilizer formalism can be used to describe quantum error detection and correction codes. Stabilizer codes are classified by the number of involved qubits n and generators $n-k$, abbreviated as $[n,k]$ stabilizer codes. An $[n,k]$ stabilizer code is composed of a vector space V_S , which represents the code space. In turn, the code space is stabilized by S and generated by $S = \langle g_1, \dots, g_{n-k} \rangle$.

Error detection is initiated by acquiring an error syndrome. The error syndrome is the summary of the measurements of all generators g_1, \dots, g_{n-k} of the underlying stabilizer S . The error syndrome is subsequently classically processed to determine if an error occurred and, if so, on which qubit.

There are three possible outcomes of a stabilizer measurement applied to a code space that is corrupted by an error E represented as a quantum operation $E \in G_n$:

1. E is an element of S and maps one element to another element in the code space: the operation does not cause an actual error, and no recovery is necessary.
2. E anti-commutes with an element of the stabilizer S : the error E projects the quantum state to a subspace that is outside (orthogonal to) the code space. This is a detectable and potentially correctable error.
3. E commutes with all elements of S , but it is not an element of S : the error is not detectable, and hence recovery is not possible.

The third scenario is the most problematic one since error E goes undetected. The set of $E \in G_n$, such that E and g commute ($Eg = gE$) for all $g \in S$, is referred to as the centralizer $Z(S)$ of S in G_n and identical to the normalizers $N(S)$ of S .

The stabilizer formalism enables the description of a wide variety of quantum error correction codes, the stabilizer codes. A stabilizer code is able to detect errors $E \in G_n$ that are not part of the centralizer $Z(S)$ or the stabilizer S itself. In the next section, we will introduce another important quantum error correction code, the 7-qubit Steane code, in detail, and we will see how efficient the stabilizer formalism captures the working principles of this more complex protocol.

20 Fault-Tolerant Quantum Gates: 5-qubit and 7-qubit Codes

Let us give some explicit examples so that we know what we are discussing in the context of quantum computation and all these gates. So, the 5-qubit code has these normalizers $XZZXI, IXZZX, XIXZZ, ZXIXZ$. All we did is memorize this pattern, and then we cyclically shifted them to get the other three here. These are the stabilizers that generate the 5-qubit code, and there are some very useful normalizers. For example, we may define logical X on a code word of the 5-qubit code as being X five times. That is XXX , five X 's, one X on each qubit. We can quite easily see that this commutes with every single generator, so that means that it is normalizable of this stabilizer group. Another case is, for example, Z . So, the Z bar on this is also equal to something simple. However, H , the Hadamard gate, cannot be done by just repeating H 5 times. This is fairly straightforward to see, because if we conjugate this it, turns X into Z s and Z s into X s. Then, the pattern is different, and it does not commute with each of these five. So, the five-qubit code does not admit a simple way of doing universal gates on the data encoded inside it. We can also see this for the CNOT gate if we try to make that construction. On the other hand, there is another code in which we have seen the 7-qubit code, which has the stabilizers we, we, X, we, X, we . We are writing them in a funny way because it is easiest to remember this way. These are just binary numbers going from 1 through 7. So, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7. the generators of the 7-qubit code are these, plus the same with X replaced with Z . this is a CSS code, Calderbank-Shor-Steane code. It has the following beautiful properties. First, logical X is

7 Xs. Same thing for Z. However, we also have this nice thing, which is that a Hadamard is 7 Hadamard's. That is obvious because the seven Hadamard's just change these Xs to Zs. So, it flips this with this, and therefore, it stabilizes the code. In addition to this, if we want to do a controlled-NOT between two 7-qubit coded blocks, we can do it bitwise. This we are not going to show us, but we are going to make an assertion about it. All the way down to the last one over here. So, we say that the CNOT is transversal. A bitwise performance of controlled NOTs between each pair of bits in two different 7-qubit codeword blocks performs a controlled-NOT gate. This is such a beautiful feature that, in fact, we will make this assertion. It turns out that every CSS code has a transversal CNOT. Every code with a transversal CNOT is a CSS code. We encourage us to go and prove that for ourselves. It is a fun fact. Now, a catch. We cannot perform universal computation with Clifford H and X and Z., in fact, and we can also look at a logical S. Go work that out. Clifford is generated by H, S, and CNOT. There is an important theorem that has been proven, which is that, of all these quantum codes, the stabilizer codes are the most useful to work with, because they are the analog of classical linear codes. They have wonderful properties which give us large families. Unfortunately, there is this theorem from 2007 Eastin Knill, we think? That was also 2007. No stabilizer's code has a universal set of transversal gates. This is horrible. This means that we cannot get universal quantum computation by staying inside a single stabilizer code. This has meant that one has to use a variety of tricks to go in and out of the code to perform the computation or something else. in much of what we are going to discuss in the next few sections, we are going to find a series of tricks to be able to do that. Complicated and interesting codes that have multiple families together. Alternatively, using an idea called teleportation of gates [52]. However, we are going to just stick with the assumption that we can look at the controlled-NOT gate, and then use that one assumption to derive a first-cut estimate of the threshold for quantum computation. So, there is this very strong caveat. Just keep that in mind.

The 7-qubit Steane code [53] is best understood from the perspective of the Hamming codes. Hamming codes are a family of classical error-correcting codes introduced by Richard Hamming in 1950 to deal with errors in punch card readers. Specifically, we will elaborate on the [7,4] Hamming code, which indicates that seven bits are used to communicate a four-bit message. The extra three bits in each logical codeword serve the purpose of redundancy and allow for any single-bit error to be detected and corrected.

With four bits of information, there need to be 2^4 distinct strings of length seven that can be used as logical codewords. These logical codewords can be found by multiplying any of the four-bit messages in the form of a binary column vector by the code generation matrix G given by:

$$G = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 & 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 & 1 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}$$

which will result in a column vector of length seven.

Once an encoded message is transmitted, and potentially incurs errors, it can be analyzed by multiplying the seven-bit vector by the so-called parity-check matrix, given by:

$$H = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \end{pmatrix}$$

which results in a three-bit vector, referred to as the syndrome vector. The syndrome vector can be used to determine which of the seven bits in the logical codeword have been flipped. Note that if the logical codeword is not corrupted, then the syndrome vector will be the zero vector for all logical codewords. It is important to remember that we are only considering bits, and so all matrix multiplication is modulo 2.

As an example, we can consider encoding (0 0 1 0) to find the seven-bit logical codeword.

$$\begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 & 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 & 1 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 1 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \\ 0 \\ 1 \\ 0 \\ 1 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix}.$$

We can first verify that multiplying the parity-check matrix into this logical codeword results in the zero vector.

$$H = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \\ 0 \\ 1 \\ 0 \\ 1 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 \text{ mod } 2 \\ 2 \text{ mod } 2 \\ 2 \text{ mod } 2 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix}.$$

If instead, during transmission the first bit of the logical codeword is flipped from 0 \rightarrow 1, then the syndrome vector would become

$$H = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 1 \\ 0 \\ 1 \\ 0 \\ 1 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 \text{ mod } 2 \\ 2 \text{ mod } 2 \\ 2 \text{ mod } 2 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix},$$

which uniquely determines in which element of the length-seven logical codeword the error occurred (in this case, the first element). As we move to the quantum case, it is important to recognize that the syndrome vector only reveals which bit was flipped, and not the value of that bit.

The 7-qubit Steane code was introduced in 1996 by Andrew Steane of Oxford University and extended the Hamming code to the quantum realm. Since errors in quantum systems are more complicated than in classical systems, due to the existence of phase errors, the 7-qubit Steane code uses seven qubits to store a single qubit, rather than seven classical bits to store four classical bits as in the Hamming code. Similar to the classical notation for error correction

codes such as the [7,4] Hamming code with seven bits encoding the information of four bits, there exists a quantum notation to summarize quantum codes. For example, the 7-qubit Steane code is written $[[7,1,3]]$ (the double brackets indicate a quantum error correction code). The first value indicates the number of physical qubits, the second the number of encoded logical qubits, and the third the number of qubits containing information on the errors.

The Steane code is capable of correcting for a single arbitrary error, and it is based on a logical encoding with the following seven-qubit states:

$$\begin{aligned}
|0\rangle_L &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{8}}(|0000000\rangle + |0001111\rangle + |0110011\rangle + |0111100\rangle \\
&\quad + |1010101\rangle + |1011010\rangle + |1100110\rangle + |1110100\rangle) \\
|1\rangle_L &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{8}}(|1111111\rangle + |1110000\rangle + |1001100\rangle + |1000011\rangle \\
&\quad + |0101010\rangle + |0100101\rangle + |0011001\rangle + |0001011\rangle)
\end{aligned} \tag{46}$$

Where the subscript L stands for logical codeword state. Each of these seven-qubit states corresponds to the form of the logical codeword in the [7,4] Hamming code, and hence it is possible to perform a quantum computation over the entire superposition to determine the syndrome vector and to correct a bit-flip error in this basis.

In the stabilizer formalism the 7-qubit Steane code can be expressed with 6 generators as:

$$\begin{aligned}
g_1 &= IIIXXX \\
g_2 &= IXXIIX \\
g_3 &= XIXIXIX \\
g_4 &= IIIZZZZ \\
g_5 &= IZZIIZZ \\
g_6 &= ZIZIZIZ
\end{aligned} \tag{47}$$

To represent the code space. We encourage the reader to check a few qubit states and experience the “stabilizing” effects of the generators or combinations of them.

7 qubit Steane Code

Figure 9: Steane code

The figure illustrates a possible implementation of the 7-qubit Steane code. The required logical qubit spans the code space, and a potential error is subsequently detected through a stabilizer measurement and corrected. The 7-qubit Steane code can, at most correct, a single bit-flip and phase-flip error, encoded in n and m , respectively, if the bit-flip and phase-flip errors happened to two different qubits.

So that this procedure can be used within a larger quantum computation, it is important that the detection and correction operations should not reveal any information about the encoded qubit. The seven qubits are therefore augmented with three ancilla qubits into which the syndrome will be encoded. As we noted above, the syndrome vector itself only indicates which qubit is faulty and not its value, and hence no quantum information is revealed.

So far we have only corrected bit-flip errors in the qubit basis. However, we also need to characterize and correct any phase-flip errors. This can be achieved simply by rotating the basis of each qubit, such that phase-flip errors become bit-flip errors, and repeating the same process. More specifically, consider that a phase flip, which takes $|+\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|0\rangle + |1\rangle)$ to $|-\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|0\rangle - |1\rangle)$, is equivalent to a bit flip error in the $\{+, -\}$ basis.

As an instructive example, we will consider the case of a bit-flip error in the first qubit of the states used to encode $|\psi\rangle = a|0\rangle_L + b|1\rangle_L$, where $|a|^2 + |b|^2 = 1$. After the bit-flip error the state becomes $|\psi'\rangle = E_{b_1}|\psi\rangle$, where E_{b_1} is an error operator that flips the first bit of the encoding states.

The system is now combined with three ancilla qubits in the $|000\rangle$ state, and an execution of the Steane code circuit results in:

$$|\psi'\rangle|000\rangle \rightarrow |\psi'\rangle|S(\psi')\rangle$$

where $S(\psi')$ represents the syndrome vector of ψ' .

As we discuss in the classical example above, the syndrome vector corresponding to a bit flip on the first bit of a Hamming code is given by

$$S(\psi') = \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix}.$$

From this, we know that $|\psi\rangle$ can be recovered by applying a bit flip to the first qubit. Note that no information about a and b is revealed throughout this process.

15. 7-qubit Codes; Consider the seven-qubit code described in the section above. Which of the following statements are correct?

- Three generators of the stabilizers of this code are $IIZZZZ$, $IZZIIZZ$, and $ZIZIZIZ$.
- It is possible to define the transversal Hadamard gate $\bar{H} = HHHHHHH$.
- The transversal Controlled-NOT (CNOT) gate is given by the combination of seven controlled gates between qubits 1 and 8, 2 and 9, 3, and 10.
- The gate $\bar{Z} = ZZZZZZZ$ cannot be considered a normalizer.

Solution:

The logical gate $\bar{Z} = ZZZZZZZ$ can be considered a normalizer since it commutes with all generators of the stabilizer group.

21 Fault-Tolerant Quantum Measurement of Error Syndromes

Probably the most complicated part of the threshold for fault tolerance is for quantum computation, the methods that one has to use to perform the fault-tolerant measurement. We want to illustrate this challenge for us, and then we will see why this ends up dominating the cost for fault-tolerance and the threshold argument. So, the problem with fault-tolerant measurement is that in order to perform quantum error correction, we have to measure the stabilizers. So, recall that the quantum error correction procedure is to measure stabilizers the generators and then perform the recovery operation classically conditioned on these stabilizer measurement results. However, how do we measure stabilizers? Well, for example, if we look at this seven-qubit code up here, we have a number of generators that have Z 's in them. In fact, we have four Z s, just like we have four X 's here. So, we need to do four Control- Z gates, and the construction looks something like this. We start out with a single qubit. We perform a Hadamard, and then we have the seven-qubit data down here, and we perform controlled Z 's on those qubits for which the generator has a Z . This is just an example, and they move around. Depending on where the Z 's are in the generator, one then performs a Hadamard and a measurement. Clearly, this is not a good construction, because we have a single point of failure. If this qubit has an error in it, suddenly that error might propagate to four of the qubits down here. So, we need some fault-tolerant procedure for the measurement of the syndromes of the quantum error correction code. This is one of the largest hurdles for fault tolerance. So, let us tell us a story. Peter Shor invented the quantum factoring algorithm [54]. There was a lot of criticism that the algorithm

would never be realistic because it relied on the perfect functioning of quantum computers. So, Peter Shor went away, and he wrote a second paper in which he largely invented the field of quantum error correction. This is a nine-qubit code, and what we have just discussed about in the last few sections. Then the community rallied again and said, but despite error correction, there is no plausible way we can realize Shor's algorithm [54] because errors will propagate too fast, and there is no way to build a fault-tolerant quantum computer. Error correction alone is not good enough. We need a code on which we can compute. So, Peter Shor went away, and then he came up with a fault-tolerant construction for quantum computation, at which point he got hired by MIT. So, he had three major results. Now we are essentially going to tell us about that third result. If we want, this is like the third Shor theorem. That is that we can perform this measurement procedure fault-tolerantly using a trick. This is a trick that Peter Shor invented. We measure this syndrome fault-tolerantly by first constructing something else which helps us an ancilla state. What we will do is we will construct using a quantum circuit. For example, this circuit. A four-qubit cat state. This is 0000 plus 1111 divided by root 2. we will construct this painstakingly well. We will explain more in a moment if we have time. Then we have the data qubits down here. We then perform the desired controlled Z measurements. We are just going to use a dot here to represent Z on whatever qubits we need to measure the stabilizers of. Just imagine that these are the four qubits. This is the ancilla. These are the data qubits. Notice how now this is transversal. They have split apart. However, because we have guaranteed that we are either all zero or all one, they actually do the same thing. So, that the effect of this measurement bumps a phase back up here, and it changes the parity once we perform the decoding of this cat state. So, we can decode by reversing that initial circuit, and then measure. We will measure all four of these and then look at those properties. What will it turn out is that the parity of the output over here will tell us the measurement result we want, while not causing a single error to propagate over here. Now, this is not very fault-tolerant, and this is not very fault-tolerant. However, we can do this part and then check those results. That is the key idea behind the fault tolerance.

22 Crude Estimate of the Threshold for Reliable Quantum Computation

Putting together everything we have seen to give us one final thing, which is an estimate of the fault tolerance. We had PTH for classical circuits, something like 1 over 6 or 0.089. What is it for a quantum computer? If we use this qubit code, we can discuss at the number of gates we need and their purpose. We will discuss at the gates required of the basic fault procedure, let us say for a controlled-NOT gate. So, here, we are going to need seven CNOTs for the gate. Then we need to do quantum error correction. Each of the steps of the quantum error correction has six syndrome operations. If we look up there, we have three X's and three Z's. So, add them up. That gives us 6. then we are going to have to measure four; each one has four gates, four non-zero syndrome qubits. then, we have to repeat this measurement three times because the measurement procedure itself is faulty. So, we have to be able to majority vote classically on the output of that. So, we multiply all these things up together. This gives us 72. we can see that the error correction far outweighs the actual steps we need for the gate. then we sum all of these, and this is going to give us 77 gates. We can tolerate 77 choose two, and therefore, if we take this as the number of fault paths possible, then we get something like around 3,081. So, the threshold is something like 01 over 3,081, which is something around 10 to the minus 4. And so, we say this is something around the threshold for fault-tolerant quantum computation.

Questions? 79. Thank we. Other questions? Thank we for the fault-tolerant check.

In this section, we provide a table comparing several simple codes. It is important to note here that there are many more quantum error correction codes and configurations than are summarized here.

For a quantum error correction code to be effective, it is important that its implementation is “fault-tolerant” to prevent error propagation. To this end, the ancillas assisting the quantum error detection can be implemented such that errors are unable to propagate and further corrupt the logical qubit. After implementing the classical processing to interpret the error syndrome and any subsequent error correction, the logical qubit is ideally free of errors. Such implementations are referred to as fault-tolerant since they enable the successful completion of a computational task even in the presence of errors.

code (QB=qubit)	# physical data qubits	# stabilizers (weight)	typical error threshold range	arbitrary Pauli error?
3-QB bit-flip	3	2 (2)	N/A	no
3-QB phase-flip	3	2 (2)	N/A	no
5-QB Laflamme	5	4 (4)	N/A	yes
7-QB Steane	7	6 (4)	10^{-4} to 10^{-6}	yes
9-QB Shor	9	6 (2) & 2 (6)	10^{-4} to 10^{-6}	yes
17-QB Surface	17	4 (4) & 4 (2)	10^{-2} to 10^{-3}	yes

Figure 10: Table: A basic comparison of quantum error correction codes. The stabilizers and weights provide an estimate on the number of ancilla qubits required to achieve fault-tolerance. The estimated error threshold is an indicative range and depends on the architecture used [55]. Thresholds are not provided (N/A) for the first three codes.

The stabilizers describing a quantum error correction code can help to estimate the number of required ancilla qubits to achieve a fault-tolerant implementation. The number of stabilizers and their number of non-identity gates referred to as the stabilizer’s weight, provide an estimate on how many interactions between the physical qubits and ancilla qubits are required to generate the error syndrome. Therefore, the number of ancilla qubits required for a fault-tolerant implementation of a quantum error correction code can be approximated by multiplying the number of stabilizers by their respective weights.

To compare the different fault-tolerant quantum error detection and correction methods, an important figure of merit is the physical qubit error rate. A quantum processor with an individual physical qubit error rate below a certain error threshold can, in principle, achieve fault-tolerance using quantum error correction codes. In general, the exact threshold depends on the architectural implementation of quantum error correction code, for example, the arrangement and connectivity of the qubits, the available gate set.

The table is organized to reflect an approximation of the classical effort required to detect errors. The complexity of the classical scheme increases from the top of the table to the bottom. In the next section, we will discuss the surface code in detail. Although it requires only nearest-neighbor couplings between qubits and has a relatively lenient threshold, making it a leading

candidate for implementing error correction with today's available qubits, it requires a relatively large classical-computing overhead to interpret the syndrome measurements.

16. Fault-Tolerant Procedure for a CNOT Gate; In a seven-qubit code, the procedure for a fault-tolerant CNOT gate requires:

- Seven Controlled-NOT (CNOT) gates to generate a transversal CNOT.
- Six syndrome operations for quantum error correction.
- Four measurements per syndrome for quantum error correction.
- Only two repetitions of each measurement to apply a majority gate.

Solution:

Since the measurement procedure is faulty, it is necessary to perform a majority vote, which needs three inputs and returns one output. This means that each measurement has to be repeated three times.

17. Threshold Theorem II; A circuit constructed of unreliable gates can still simulate a uniform circuit composed of error-free gates. However, this simulation has to accept an error within a specified error tolerance. Which of the following statements is correct about the number of gates required to simulate the ideal circuit:

- It grows with the number of gates of the ideal circuit.
- It decreases with the threshold probability.
- It scales as the logarithm of the inverse of the desired error tolerance.
- It is greater than the number of error-free gates in the ideal circuit.

Solution:

If the ideal circuit is composed of N error-free gates, and the error tolerance is given by a number ϵ , the simulation circuit will be composed of $\mathcal{O}(\text{poly}(\log \frac{N}{\epsilon}) N)$ gates.

The larger the ideal circuit, the more gates it takes to simulate it. The smaller the error tolerance ϵ , the more gates it takes to reach such a level of precision. The threshold probability does not provide any information about how many gates are necessary to simulate the ideal circuit.

18. Comparing Error-Correcting Circuits; Consider a given error correcting circuit A with a threshold probability larger than the threshold probability of another error correcting circuit B. Which of the following sentences is correct?

- A can tolerate working with gates with a larger error probability than B.
- A can operate with gates with lower error probabilities than B. Those gates would not work on B.
- There is no way that B can achieve the same level of error tolerance as A.

Solution:

A can tolerate working with gates with a larger error probability than B. However, both A and B can operate with arbitrarily low error probabilities. Provided that the single gate error probability is smaller than the threshold probability of B, A and B can simulate an ideal error-free circuit with the same level of precision.

19. Threshold Theorem Equation; The threshold theorem can be summarized by the following equation,

$$\frac{P_{fail}}{P_{th}} = \left(\frac{P}{P_{th}} \right)^{2^k}. \quad (48)$$

Which of the definitions below is correct?

- P_{fail} is the probability of failure of the fault-tolerant procedure for a single gate.
- P is the failure probability of an individual gate.
- P_{th} is the threshold probability that sets the maximum value of the individual-gate failure probability for which the procedure can simulate, with arbitrary precision and error-free circuit.
- k is the maximum number of times that the entire procedure can be performed.

Solution:

The term k is the level of recursions, that is, the number of times that a set of blocks is made into one larger block. For example, if a circuit is composed of eight gates, then the first level of recursion, $k = 1$, is given by the same circuit, the second level, $k = 2$, is given by eight blocks of eight gates each, the third level of recursion, $k = 3$, is given by eight blocks each block composed of eight blocks composed of eight gates, and so for.

20. 5-qubit and 7-qubit Codes; Consider the section “5-qubit and 7-qubit Codes”. Which of the following statements are correct?

- The Hadamard (H) gate, the S gate, and the Controlled-NOT (CNOT) gate are all examples of Clifford gates.
- It is not possible to do universal quantum computation by operating solely within a single stabilizer code.
- A transversal gate that commutes with every generator of the stabilizer group S is an element of the normalizer of S.
- It is not possible to define a transversal Controlled-NOT (CNOT) gate for 5-qubit codes.

21. Fault-Tolerance Elements; Which of the following are not required to realize fault-tolerant computation?

- Fault-tolerant state preparation.
- Fault-tolerant gates.
- Fault-tolerant measurements.
- They are all necessary elements of fault-tolerant computation.

Solution:

Initialization, operation, and measurement must all be fault-tolerant.

23 Quantum Computation vs Analog Computation

In the early days of quantum computing, after Shor’s factoring algorithm came out, there were arguments on this, but there is something called Usenet, which was like an early Twitter. There were arguments on Usenet about whether quantum computers could ever be realized, because

of noise. They said, well, these look very powerful, but we have already known that in theory, analog computers are very powerful. These amplitudes of quantum computers, they just look like the real numbers that we see in analog quantum computers. Thus, we should not be surprised that this model is more powerful, but we know that analog computers cannot be realized, at least not to very high precision, because if the voltage if all of the voltages are legal values right, in a digital computer, it is either 0 volts or 5 volts. Everything else is illegal. So, if the computer sees 4.9, it knows it should bump it up to 5. However, in an analog computer, if 3.7 is a legal voltage, and 3.70001 is also a legal voltage, there is nothing the computer can do to know if there is a little drift of voltage, if that was supposed to happen, or if it was something that should be corrected. So, analog computing is fundamentally not error correctable. In some cases, that is fine. We know, if our stereo does not produce exactly the right sound, then that is fine. However, if we want to use these real numbers for some complicated math calculations, it is not so good. Thus, there was that argument given that quantum computers suffered the same limitation as analog computers; namely, we cannot error correct amplitudes. Indeed, if we have some error that looks like e to the $i \theta z$, and just as a notation, by the way, we going to write x equals σx , y equals σy . From now on, we are going to use this kind of quantum computing notation for the poly matrices. So, we have this error, in the e to the $i \theta z$, θ can continuously vary. It could be very, very small. We know, we cannot distinguish all those different errors. So, how can we correct them? That was a compelling argument against quantum computers before quantum error-correcting codes came along. We think that it was this Usenet discussion that was part of what pushed Peter Shor and others to develop quantum error-correcting codes. The answer we have is that e to the $i \theta z$ is a linear combination of i and z . So, if we have a code that can correct i and z , then we can also correct at no extra cost, all linear combinations of them. So, we can correct e to the $i \theta z$, for all values of z . So, it is a remarkable and crucial feature of quantum error correction that the space of errors they correct is a linear subspace.

We have discussed several examples of quantum error correction protocols. These protocols generally use syndrome measurements to detect if and where an error occurred. Detected errors can then be corrected using a “feed-forward” approach, in which pulses are applied to the errant qubits to correct the error. Because these protocols actively look for and correct errors, this approach is referred to as active error correction.

Implementing active error correction, particularly in a fault-tolerant manner, is resource-intensive, requiring significant overhead in terms of ancilla qubits, quantum operations, and measurements. The number of overhead decreases as the physical qubit error rates are reduced, and so it behooves us to use every tool available to mitigate errors in physical qubits before using them in logical qubits.

Passive error mitigation is one means to reduce physical qubit error rates [18]. In this case, specific pulse sequences are designed to either mitigate systematic qubit errors (e.g., under-rotation or over-rotation of the Bloch vector due to a systematic miscalibration), or to dynamically “undo” coherent errors (e.g., coherent dephasing errors). The pulses used are generally of the same type, e.g., π -pulses, like those used in the execution of quantum algorithms [56]. However, their purpose is to counteract typical or likely errors. It is “passive” in the sense that we take preventative measures to counteract certain systematic or stochastic noise that we know are likely to exist in our system. However, it is not “active,” because we do not identify and correct specific errors.

Note that passive error mitigation can only address certain types of systematic and coherent stochastic errors; it will not mitigate all errors., for those errors that do remain, active error correction is required to fix them. However, by implementing passive error mitigation protocols, we can reduce the physical qubit error rate, and this translates to reduced overhead requirements

when implementing active error correction protocols.

24 Correcting Systematic Control Errors

A remarkable fact about quantum systems is that errors can be corrected simply by changing the control sequence as long as the errors are systematic, instead of random [57]. How this works can be illustrated by recalling the dynamics of single qubits. For example, coherent light applied to a two-level ion causes evolution under this Hamiltonian [58], where two degrees of freedom stand out, the laser amplitude and the laser phase, ϕ . Combined with the time applied, we get the angle of rotation affected by the laser pulse θ . Illustrated on the block sphere, a pulse with θ equal to π and ϕ equal to 0 gives this quantum NOT gate. The problem is that these physical control prime may have systematic errors. Specifically, it is typical that the amplitude and phase may have some fixed offset error ϵ in all pulses applied. Let us consider just amplitude errors, which result in qubit over or under rotation. Denote the actual rotations implemented as M . Without this error, this would be the ideal rotation R of θ , but the error ϵ indicates an extra rotation that is undesired. So, the implemented gate has an overall error of order ϵ . Keep in mind that this error is unknown, but fixed. The effect of this error can be quantified with a quantum response function, which we represent here as the transition probability between 0 and 1 for the π pulse as implemented. Plotting this response as a function of ϵ , we see that it is just a cosine squared function. Here is a short animation sequence illustrating the error. These pulses are like driving a car on a sphere. On the left is Schrodinger, who controls his velocity very accurately. On the right is his cousin, Guido, who has a lead foot, and always pushes his pedal 15% more than he should, although we do not know that it is 15% versus 17%. Starting the animation, we see Schrodinger drive precisely from start to the South Pole, whereas Guido overshoots by quite a bit. This error could possibly be compensated by calibration, but there is a more robust procedure, which can remove the error without knowing how large it is. This solution is known as composite pulse sequences or composite quantum gates, and it replaces a single pulse with multiple rotation pulses about different axes of rotation. For example, one of the most famous early pulses from nuclear magnetic resonance pioneer, Malcolm Levitt, is these three pulses 90, 180, 90 sequences about axes x, y, and x, which effects a robust π pulse with error ϵ^2 instead of ϵ . Its quantum response function has this flat region for small ϵ , indicating its leading order insensitivity to error, which compares favorably to the single pulse case. Let us return to Schrodinger and Guido driving on the block sphere and see what happens with this 90, 180, 90 sequence. We see Schrodinger reaches the y-axis exactly after the first 90, but Guido overshoots. Due to the overshoot, Guido rotates backward when applying the middle 180-degree pulse. Whereas Schrodinger just rotates in place. The final 90 brings Schrodinger exactly to the South Pole, and this time, Guido gets very close because of the backtracking. Can one do better? Here is a 90, 360, 90 sequence, which involves rotations about some unusual axis, x and then an axis at 120 degrees in the XY plane, and then x, which is the desired π rotation up to ϵ^3 . This sequence has a quantum response function shown here in red, much flatter with respect to error than the 90, 180, 90, and the single pulse. On the block sphere, here are Schrodinger and Guido driving the 90, 360, 90 sequences. First, we have the 90, which Guido overshoots, but Schrodinger does not. The 360 takes Schrodinger back to the y-axis, but causes Guido to backtrack, compensating for his overshoot. Finally, the third pulse, a 90, brings both to the South Pole. Can one do even better? Here is a four-pulse sequence, known as BB1 with three unusual axes of rotation defined by this arc cosine expression, which has even less error. Indeed, its quantum response, shown here in green, is even flatter than all previous pulse sequences we have discussed at BB1 is also notable in that it performs a high-

fidelity π pulse no matter what the initial state is [59–62], whereas some other sequences only work when the initial state is at the North Pole. We have seen three examples of how sequences of pulses can correct amplitude errors without knowing the error. With fidelity, which increases with pulse sequence length, the ability to correct systematic errors using gate sequences is very useful in practical quantum computation.

22. Composite Pulse Sequences; The use of composite pulse sequences can help reduce the system response to systematic errors in single quantum gates without specific information about how large the errors are. In this procedure, a single pulse is replaced with multiple pulses with different axes of rotation, in general.

Let us recall that an ideal qubit rotation about the \hat{n} -axis at an angle θ is given by

$$R_{\hat{n}}(\theta) = \exp\left(-i\frac{\theta}{2}\hat{n}\cdot\vec{\sigma}\right), \quad (49)$$

with $\hat{n}\cdot\vec{\sigma} = n_xX + n_yY + n_zZ$, where n_x , n_y , and n_z , are the x, y, and z components of \hat{n} .

Similarly, a non-ideal qubit rotation about the \hat{n} -axis at an angle θ is given by

$$M_{\hat{n}}(\theta) = \exp\left(-i\frac{\theta(1+\epsilon)}{2}\hat{n}\cdot\vec{\sigma}\right), \quad (50)$$

Where ϵ is a systematic rotation error.

According to the section above, which of the following pulse sequences implements a π -pulse about the x-axis with the smallest net error in the system response?

- The sequence of two pulses, 90-180, implemented as one rotation about the x-axis and one about the y-axis,

$$T = M_y\left(\frac{\pi}{2}\right)M_x(\pi).$$

- The sequence of three pulses, 90-180-90, implemented as two rotations about the x-axis and one about the y-axis,

$$U = M_x\left(\frac{\pi}{2}\right)M_y(\pi)M_x\left(\frac{\pi}{2}\right).$$

- The sequence of three pulses, 90-360-90, implemented as two rotations about the x-axis and one about the an unusual axis represented by $\frac{2\pi}{3}$,

$$V = M_x\left(\frac{\pi}{2}\right)M_{\frac{2\pi}{3}}(2\pi)M_x\left(\frac{\pi}{2}\right).$$

- The sequence of four pulses called “ $BB1''$ ” given by

$$B(\pi) = M_{\hat{n}_\phi}(\pi)M_{n_{3\phi}}(2\pi)M_{\hat{n}_\phi}(\pi)M_x(\pi),$$

where $\hat{n}_\phi = (\cos\phi, \sin\phi, 0)$ with $\phi = \cos^{-1}\left(-\frac{1}{4}\right)$.

Solution:

The sequence of pulses

$$U = M_x\left(\frac{\pi}{2}\right)M_y(\pi)M_x\left(\frac{\pi}{2}\right)$$

implements $R_x(\pi)$ with error $O(\epsilon^2)$. The sequence

$$V = M_x(\frac{\pi}{2})M_{\frac{2\pi}{3}}(2\pi)M_x(\frac{\pi}{2})$$

is better, as it implements $R_x(\pi)$ with error $O(\epsilon^3)$. The sequence

$$B(\pi) = M_{\hat{n}_\phi}(\pi)M_{n_{\hat{s}_\phi}}(2\pi)M_{\hat{n}_\phi}(\pi)M_x(\pi)$$

is the best, as it implements $R_x(\pi)$ with error $O(\epsilon^4)$.

25 Dynamical Decoupling: Introduction

In section three, we discuss that noise could be categorized into two primary types systematic noise and stochastic noise. In this section, we will focus on error mitigation strategies that address stochastic noise. Recall that stochastic noise is the random fluctuation of a parameter that is coupled to the qubit, and it can cause decoherence in a couple of different ways. As we may remember from earlier sections, a qubit in state 1 can relax to the ground state by losing energy to its environment with a rate of γ 1, which is 1 over the relaxation time, T1. we will assume here that the qubit only relaxes to its ground state, and that it is rarely excited out of the ground state by its environment. Then, there is also decoherence of the block vector on the equator, as characterized by the decoherence rate γ 2, which is 1 over the T2 time. On the equator, two things can go wrong. First, the qubit could simply relax back to the ground state via a T1 process. clearly, this is a phase-breaking event, since once the block vector has relaxed to the North Pole, there is no way to tell which direction it had been pointing when it was on the equator. second, the block vector can diffuse around the equator, and this is called dephasing. The decoherence time, T2, is a combination of both the dephasing time, T ϕ , and the relaxation time, T1. note that if there is no dephasing, such that T ϕ becomes very large, then T2 equals twice T1 and is completely limited by relaxation. While energy relaxation processes are generally irreversible, dephasing processes may, in fact, be coherent, and therefore reversible. as we will see, coherent dephasing errors can be mitigated using dynamical decoupling pulse sequences, a type of passive error suppression [63]. To gain an intuition for dynamical decoupling, let us first consider a lacrosse player. If we have ever played lacrosse or watched a lacrosse game, we know that we need to run down the lacrosse field with a lacrosse ball in a basket that is at the end of our lacrosse stick. as we run, our body moves up and down, left and right, and this shakes the stick. This is the noise. Now, if we just hold the stick in front of us as we run, then we will find that the ball will very easily fall out of the basket due to the noise associated with our running. So, lacrosse players do not do that. Instead, they cradle the stick as they run down the field, back and forth, back and forth. this keeps the ball in the basket. importantly, they do this out of habit, without even thinking about it. They are not reacting to something specific. They are just continuously cradling the ball. by doing this, they decouple the ball from the noise generated by their running. this is an example of dynamical error suppression. Now, cradling addresses running noise, but it does not prevent a defender from running up behind us and knocking the ball out of our basket and onto the ground. Those kinds of errors still occur. when that happens, we have to stop, find out where the ball went, go over, and physically pick it up again. that would be analogous to active error correction. so, lacrosse cradling is one classic example of dynamical error suppression. Let us now see how it works with a qubit. we will take as an example a superconducting flux qubit [64]. The flux qubit shown here is a superconducting loop interrupted by 4 Josephson junctions [?,65–67]. Threading a magnetic flux through the loop

sets the qubit energy level E_0 . However, due to local magnetic field fluctuations in the qubit's environment, the energy levels also fluctuate, and this leads to qubit dephasing. To see this, let us take a qubit to be in a superposition state $\alpha|0\rangle + \beta|1\rangle$. Because state 1 is at higher energy than state 0, it accrues phase at a faster rate. We can write this as $\alpha|0\rangle + \beta e^{i\phi} |1\rangle$, where ϕ is equal to the qubit energy E_0 divided by the reduced Planck's constant, \hbar , times the time, t . This is called free evolution because the phase of the qubit evolves solely due to the energy level difference and not due to any external driving. Now, in the absence of noise, E_0 is fixed, and so, the phase accrual is deterministic, meaning that at any time t in the future, we can tell precisely the value of the phase. However, in the presence of noise, such as low-frequency flux noise due to the local magnetic environment of the qubit, the energy level separation will fluctuate. There is now an average value of the energy, \bar{E}_0 , corresponding to an average phase, $\bar{\phi}$. However, due to the stochastic noise, there is also fluctuating energy, E_0 , which fluctuates in time. This corresponds to a fluctuating phase, ϕ . It is this stochastic phase which leads to dephasing. We can write an expression for the resulting dephasing in an intuitive form by looking at the ensemble average of the dephasing. Phase accrues in an exponent, as $e^{i\phi}$, and the phase at time t is the time integral of the energy fluctuation, E_0 . In taking the ensemble average, we will assume that the noise is Gaussian-distributed, that is, arising from a large number of weakly coupled magnetic noise sources, and this leads to the following intuitive result. First off, we have the change in energy due to the fluctuations, which we will assume here are fluctuations in the magnetic flux, ϕ . This is the sensitivity of the qubit energy to fluctuations in magnetic flux, and it is squared. Next is the strength of the magnetic flux noise that drives the energy fluctuations. This is the integral over frequency of the noise power spectral density, and it has units of ϕ squared. By itself, this would simply be the variance of the noise process. Importantly, the noise power spectral density is shaped by a term called the filter function. The filter function depends on the pulse sequence that we apply to the qubit, and it serves to filter, or window, the noise. So, to summarize, the noise seen by a qubit will drive fluctuations in the energy levels, and this leads to dephasing. However, the noise spectrum itself can be shaped by a filter function related to the pulses we apply to the qubit. In the next section, we will discuss at a few specific pulse sequences, their corresponding filter functions, and how they dynamically decouple the qubit from its noisy environment.

23. Stochastic Noise; Noise can be categorized into two primary types: systemic noise and stochastic noise. Regarding stochastic noise, which of the following statements is correct?

- Stochastic noise is given by a fixed and unknown offset error ϵ .
- A qubit in the excited state $|1\rangle$ may spontaneously relax to the ground state $|0\rangle$ by stochastically emitting energy to its environment.
- When the Bloch vector of a qubit diffuses around the equator, this is called dephasing.
- Dephasing processes are always irreversible.

Solution:

Stochastic noise is given by the random fluctuation of a parameter that is coupled to a qubit. Dephasing processes can be coherent and, therefore, reversible.

26 Dynamical Decoupling: Free Evolution

In the last section, we considered a superconducting flux qubit [68,69], in the presence of magnetic flux noise, and asked how we could potentially dynamically mitigate the resulting qubit

dephasing. To gain some intuition, we consider dynamical decoupling in the context of lacrosse. Where a lacrosse player can use cradling to effectively decouple the lacrosse ball, in the basket of a lacrosse stick, from noise due to running down the field. we then discussed at how environmental noise drives fluctuations in the qubit energy levels and calculated the resulting phase decay function. In doing so, we discuss that the power spectrum of the noise that drives these fluctuations could be shaped by a filter function that is related to the pulses we intentionally apply to the qubit. To see how this works in practice, let us discuss at a few examples. we will start with a Ramsey experiment. Here a $\pi/2$ pulse along the y-axis of the Bloch sphere brings the qubit Bloch vector down to the equator, pointed along the x-axis. we then wait, while the qubit undergoes free evolution. The simulation shown here represents an ensemble of instances of the qubit in the presence of low frequency $1/f$ noise, taken to be quasi-static. That is, the noise is essentially fixed for any given instance, and it is different for different instances according to the sum probability distribution. we also operate in a rotating frame, such that the average phase, in the absence of noise, always points along the x-axis. However, in the presence of noise, the Bloch vector rotates clockwise or counterclockwise around the equator. at different speeds, depending on the specific size of the noise offset for each instance. we then use a second $\pi/2$ pulse to rotate back to the z-axis. ideally, in the absence of noise, the qubit should now align with state one at the south pole. However, clearly, due to the noise, the Bloch vector is largely depolarized. The way to understand this is as follows. The magnetic flux noise spectral density is a $1/f$ -type noise, which is large at low frequencies and decreases as $1/f$. During the free evolution period, we do nothing. we do not apply any external control pulses, which we represent here as n equals 0 where n will count the number of pulses we apply. However, here, n equals 0, and the qubit it evolves in the gray region, for a time τ . During this period of time, since we assume the noise is quasi-static, the qubit energy levels are essentially fixed for each instance and vary from instance to instance. For a given instance, the gray region represents the energy versus time. it is a rectangle. the Fourier transform of a rectangle is a sinc function centered at zero frequency. Which is to say, applying no pulses leads to a filter function that is highly peaked at zero frequency. That is, the filter passes noise at low frequencies. for $1/f$ noise, this is where the noise is the strongest. Thus, this is the worst strategy for noise suppression of $1/f$ -type noise. Referring back to the lacrosse example, this is analogous to running down the field without cradling the ball. However, we could improve the situation by performing a spin-echo experiment. In a spin echo, a π pulse is applied during the free evolution period. The π pulse inverts the phase diffusion along the equator, such that spins that were moving away from the x-axis before the pulse are now moving towards it after the pulse. for a pulse that is located precisely in the middle at the free evolution period, the Bloch vector refocuses and coalesces right when the second $\pi/2$ pulse occurs, taking the Bloch vector down to the south pole, and state 1. clearly, the polarization is significantly improved by adding this single refocusing pulse. So, what did we do? Well, adding the π pulse now divides the evolution into half periods of free evolution. The first is represented by the gray rectangle, with a plus sign. the second with a minus sign, due to the inversion of the system by the π pulse. The filter function corresponding to these two rectangle functions is shown in green. we see that its passband is now peaked at a higher frequency. Since the $1/f$ noise decreases with frequency, the spin-echo filter function effectively lets through less noise. Thus, the dephasing is reduced. Adding the π pulse is an example of dynamically decoupling the qubit from its flux noise environment. In the context of the lacrosse example, this is cradling while running. as we might expect, the situation is further improved with an additional π pulses. Adding two π pulses break the free evolution into three distinct periods, raising the filter passband to even higher frequencies and further reducing the dephasing due to $1/f$ noise. Adding equally spaced π pulses is called a CPMG sequence, named after Carr, Purcell, Meiboom, and Gill, who collectively developed it. As the number of

π pulses, n , is increased, the filter function has shifted to higher and higher frequencies. this reduces the dephasing rate more and more. as the dephasing is improved, the decoherence here in the time, t_2 , approaches the ideal value of twice t_1 . Finally, one can use pulse sequences and their corresponding narrow bandpass filters to sample an unknown noise power spectral density, as seen by the qubit. This is called noise spectroscopy. it essentially uses the qubit and the applied pulses as a noise spectrometer. Changing the number of pulses shifts the narrow filter around in frequency. by measuring the dephasing response of the qubit, one can reconstruct the noise spectral density causing the dephasing. Then, with knowledge of the specific form of the noise spectral density, one can, in turn, design a pulse sequence that corresponds to a noise filter that is optimal within certain specified constraints.

24. CPMG Sequences; The effect of certain types of stochastic noise during free evolution can be reduced by applying π pulses about the x-axis (or y-axis). In particular, adding equally spaced π -pulses is called a CP or CPMG sequence, depending on the rotation axis relative to the orientation of the Bloch vector on the equator (or, similarly, of the initial $\pi/2$ pulse used to reach the equator). Which of the following statements describes the effect of this pulse sequence on the system?

- It results in a filter function that windows the noise power spectral density.
- It reduces the amplitude of the noise in the environment.
- It generally reduces dephasing for environments with noise power spectra that decrease as frequency increases.

Solution:

Applying pulses to the qubit does not generally reduce the amplitude of the noise in the environment. Rather, the pulse sequences correspond to filter functions in the frequency domain that will window the environmental noise spectral density. For noise power spectra that reduce with frequency, for example, the $1/f$ noise discussed, adding more pulses will push the filter centroid to higher frequencies and, therefore, result in less noise as seen by the qubit.

27 Dynamical Decoupling: Driven Evolution

In the last section, we discussed at several examples of qubit dephasing during free evolution. We discuss that by applying π pulses during the free evolution period, we could effectively decouple the qubit from its noisy environment. In this section, we will discuss at dynamical error suppression during driven evolution and, in particular, a rotary echo, the driven evolution analog to the spin echo. To begin, let us discuss at a typical example of driven evolution called a rabi oscillation. The qubit starts in its ground state, and we then apply a continuous pulse to the qubit along the x-axis. Now ideally, the qubit would oscillate sinusoidal from the North Pole to the South Pole and back again, rotating around the driving field represented by the red arrow. The oscillation frequency is proportional to the driving field amplitude. Thus, in the absence of noise, the rotation occurs at a fixed frequency. However, as we discuss in section three, if the amplitude of the driving field is noisy, the qubit oscillation amplitude decays with time. This is illustrated on the block sphere by an ensemble of instances of the Rabi oscillations, assuming quasi-static noise on the driving field amplitude. For a given instantiation, the driving amplitude is fixed, but that amplitude changes with the noise for each different instance. The result is an ensemble of frequencies, which, as we showed in section three, leads to a decay of the resulting Rabi oscillation. This situation can be mitigated by using a rotary echo. In a

rotary echo experiment, the driving field is reversed halfway through the driven evolution period. Again, assuming quasi-static noise, each instance drives the qubit at a given rate. Reversing the drive, no matter what amplitude the instances, will undo the unwanted over or under rotation, and this leads to a refocusing or revival of the Bloch vector back at the North Pole. Just as dynamical decoupling during free evolution could be improved by moving from a single pulse spin echo to a multi-pulse CPMG protocol, for noise that decreases with frequency, a single reversal rotary echo can be extended to a multiple field reversal analog to CPMG. As the number of reversals increases, the corresponding filter function moves to higher and higher frequencies. In this case, the filter function shapes the noise spectral density of the driving field amplitude fluctuations. Dynamical decoupling during free evolution and driven evolution are examples of error suppression techniques that are called open loop. That is, they do not feed-forward to apply certain pulses based on measurement inputs, as is done with error correction. Rather, these are pulses or pulse sequences that are simply added to or built into the gates used to implement quantum logic. In doing so, the error rates due to coherent reversible errors are reduced. This, in turn, is quite useful. By using the same types of pulses that we already use to implement quantum logic, such as π pulses, we can reduce the effective error rates of physical qubits and thereby help to reduce the overhead required to implement full-blown error correction.

Quantum systems interacting with their environment are referred to as open quantum systems. We need open systems in order to apply external control pulses that enable us to implement quantum control. However, the environment also introduces noise that acts to decohere the quantum system. Ideally, we would like a means to faithfully apply the control pulses we want to reach our qubit, while, at the same time, decouple the qubit to the extent possible from the noisy environment. Although errors can be corrected with active quantum error correction protocols, as we have discussed, active error correction is relatively expensive. Dynamical decoupling pulse sequences act to decoupling the qubit from its noisy environment and thereby mitigate errors. Although these pulse sequences cannot mitigate every type of error, they do reduce the physical qubit error rate, and this, in turn, reduces the level of overhead required to implement active error correction for those errors that remain.

In a previous section, we were introduced to the spin echo, also known as the Hahn echo, proposed by Erwin Hahn in 1950. A spin-echo comprises a single π -pulse applied to the qubit, and it mitigates dephasing noise. As introduced, the pulse sequence for a spin echo is $(\pi/2)_y \xrightarrow{\tau/2} \pi_y \xrightarrow{\tau/2} (\pi/2)_y$, where the $\pi/2$ -pulses are used to bring the qubit Bloch vector from the z-axis to the equator where dephasing during free evolution occurs for a duration of time τ and back again to project the resulting dephasing of the Bloch vector back onto the measurement axis (z-axis). The π -pulse is used to refocus the Bloch vector dephasing during the free evolution period. Note that in this example, and in the absence of noise, the π -pulse is applied to an axis perpendicular to the Bloch vector on the equator.

The extension of the above spin-echo sequence from a single π -pulse to multiple π -pulses is called a CP pulse sequence, named after Herman Carr and Edward Purcell. If we count the number N of π pulses, the above spin-echo sequence is identical to a CP pulse sequence with $N=1$. However, with the CP sequence, the number N can, in general, be larger, and as we have seen, adding more π -pulses tends to reduce dephasing due to environmental noise spectra that decrease with frequency. As with the spin-echo above, the CP sequence applies the π -pulses to an axis perpendicular to the Bloch vector, effectively toggling the Bloch vector between opposite sides of the Bloch sphere. It turns out that this approach is relatively sensitive to pulse errors, and these errors accumulate over the course of the pulse sequence.

In the section, we discussed a more robust gate sequence called the CPMG sequence, named

after Herman Carr, Edward Purcell, Saul Meiboom, and David Gill. Meiboom and Gill pointed out that applying the π pulses co-aligned with the Bloch vector rather than perpendicular to it has the advantage that the overall approach becomes less sensitive to pulse errors. For example, a CPMG sequence with two π -pulses would be $(\pi/2)_y \xrightarrow{\tau/4} \pi_x \xrightarrow{\tau/2} \pi_x \xrightarrow{\tau/4} (\pi/2)_y$. The CPMG sequence is still employed today, due to the simplicity and robustness of its pulse sequence.

The CP and CPMG sequences are examples of a broader class of sequences called dynamical decoupling sequences. These sequences serve to mitigate coherent errors by effectively decoupling the system from its noisy environment. As we discussed, these pulse sequences in the time domain can be viewed as noise filters in the frequency domain. The shape and frequency passband of the filter depends on the number of pulses and the duration of the sequence. Provided the noise-induced dephasing dynamics are slow over the duration of the pulse sequence, dynamical decoupling can mitigate errors by “refocusing” the errant dynamics. The primary limitation of dynamical decoupling sequences is the accumulation of pulse-related errors. The pulses themselves are not perfect, and this leads to imperfections in the implementation of the sequence. As we discussed above with the CP and CPMG example, different sequences can have different levels of sensitivity to pulse errors.

To close, we will give two more examples of pulses sequences that are an extension of CPMG. The first sequence, XY-4, comprises four π -rotations alternating between the x and y-axes. The combination of rotations around two orthogonal axis reduces the sensitivity to pulse imperfections, and it is particularly useful in cases where the Bloch vector orientation is not known. XY-4 can be further improved by adding an additional 4 π -rotations, but in the reverse order. The resulting decoupling sequence is referred to as XY-8.

$$XY - 4 \equiv (\pi/2)_y \xrightarrow{\tau/8} \pi_y \xrightarrow{\tau/4} \pi_x \xrightarrow{\tau/4} \pi_y \xrightarrow{\tau/4} \pi_x \xrightarrow{\tau/8} (\pi/2)_y \quad (51)$$

$$\begin{aligned} XY - 8 \equiv & (\pi/2)_y \xrightarrow{\tau/16} \pi_y \xrightarrow{\tau/8} \pi_x \xrightarrow{\tau/8} \pi_y \xrightarrow{\tau/8} \pi_x \xrightarrow{\tau/8} \pi_x \\ & \xrightarrow{\tau/8} \pi_y \xrightarrow{\tau/8} \pi_x \xrightarrow{\tau/8} \pi_y \xrightarrow{\tau/16} (\pi/2)_y \end{aligned} \quad (52)$$

The advantage of XY-4 over CPMG and CP is its robustness to pulse related errors. Suppose a qubit is initialized in its ground state, pointing to the Bloch sphere’s north pole. Then, the first $\pi/2$ pulse rotates the qubit around the y-axis. The resulting qubit orientation is ideally aligned with the x-axis. Now, suppose there is a constant over-rotation of each pulse. For a simple CP sequence, the over-rotation of each pulse accumulates and thus may induce more errors than mitigated. In contrast, the CPMG sequence is able to counteract the over-rotation of the $\pi/2_y$ pulse due to the π_x rotation. The π_x rotation causes the over-rotation of the initial and final $\pi/2_y$ rotation to compensate almost entirely. Nevertheless, the over-rotation of the π_x remains. Therefore, the CPMG sequence is more robust than the CP sequence but is not entirely free of any pulse related errors. The XY-4 pulse sequence can help compensate constant imperfect rotations around the x-axis as well. We encourage we to review the rotations comprising the XY-4 pulse sequence and show that a constant over or under-rotation can be largely mitigated. XY-8 and more complicated sequences can reduce pulse related errors even further and are hence even more robust to pulse related errors. The trade-off is that more pulses within a fixed amount of time push the pulses closer together. At some point, increasing the duration of the sequence may be required to accommodate all of the pulses. In turn, longer pulse sequences take more time, and the system is still susceptible to incoherent errors that dynamical decoupling cannot protect against; these errors will still occur and will become more likely as the overall pulse length increases.

Figure 11: Dynamical decoupling sequences: Shown are CP with four π pulses, CPMG with four π pulses, XY-4, and XY-8. All dynamical decoupling sequences start with the qubit in the ground-state, indicated with the yellow arrow pointing to the north pole on the Bloch sphere. The red arrow indicates the applied field used to implement the pulses. The blue arrow represents the Bloch vector as it rotates around the Bloch sphere.

25. Rabi Oscillations; A Rabi oscillation is a driven rotation of the Bloch vector. It is the driven-evolution analog to the oscillations observed during the free evolution of a frequency-detuned Ramsey experiment. Consider a Rabi experiment and a Ramsey experiment, where all pulses are applied along the x-axis. For the Ramsey experiment, the frequency detuning is defined as the difference between the driving frequency of the $\pi/2$ pulses and the qubit frequency. Assume we observe the experiments in a reference frame rotating at the qubit frequency. What are the similarities and differences between these two types of experiments?

- The Rabi frequency is proportional to the driving amplitude, whereas the Ramsey frequency is proportional to the frequency detuning.

- The Bloch vector in both cases rotates around the z-axis of the Bloch sphere.
- Decay of the oscillations in both cases can be caused by stochastic noise.

Solution:

During Rabi oscillation, the state of the qubit rotates around the driving-field axis, in this case, the x-axis of the Bloch sphere.

28 Fault-Tolerant Quantum Computation with Superconducting Qubits: The Surface Code and How it Works

Let us say we want to build a reliable quantum computer. We are going to need a way to detect and handle errors. The circuit churn is a generic way to do this, test the parity of a set of qubits, and note when the value of the parity changes. A change in value is called a detection event. Detection events indicate the nearby presence of errors. The surface code uses this idea in two dimensions [70]. The corners of every square correspond to data qubits we wish to protect. The squares and half-circles correspond to measure qubits that perform parity checks on the data qubits they touch. Every data qubit is touched by at least one white shape. If we perform parity checks on just these white shapes, we can detect all bit-flip errors. Quantum computers can also suffer phase flips, and a simple way of coping with this is to apply Hadamard gates to data qubits to convert phase flips into bit flips. One can then perform parity checks on the dark shapes to detect these, then finish with Hadamard gates on all data qubits again. This, when repeated, is the surface code approach to error detection. To first order, these checks are sufficient to detect all errors. Other effects such as leakage, dynamic loss of gate calibration [71, 72], and power outages can and must be handled using other techniques, such as periodic resetting, continuous calibration, and batteries and backup generators. So, why detect errors in this manner? Firstly, only nearest-neighbor interactions are required making this approach well-suited to many solid site technologies. Secondly, only about a half dozen gates are required to generate a bit of information about local errors. This means these bits are very likely to be reliable. This means a high error rate of order 1% is, in principle, tolerable. No other error detection scheme tolerates as much error when restricted to nearest-neighbor interactions. In practice, the lower the error rate of physical quantum gates, the better error detection works. For the surface code, a gate error right around 10 to the minus 3 leads to rapid suppression of error as the size of the code is increased. While this low level of error has not been achieved in a scalable system yet, it seems tantalizingly within reach. Multiple groups around the world are racing towards this goal.

29 Fault-Tolerant Quantum Computation with Superconducting Qubits: Implementing Gates on the Surface Code

In the first two of the previous three sections, we introduced surface code logical qubits measuring multi-body logical operators and constructing both simple quantum gates and more complex computations, such as state distillation. The previous section presented a discussion of the challenges of implementing the surface code, using superconducting quantum devices. Ultimately, all of these challenges boiled down to the simple fact that we cannot currently execute physical gates with sufficiently low error to successfully implement the server's code. No meaningful scale-up can occur until error rates can be made sufficiently low to do this and kept sufficiently low as the system is scaled. In this section, we turn the attention to the classical processing

associated with a quantum computer using the surface code. It is reasonable to expect that a superconducting quantum computer could execute a single round of surface code error detection in approximately one microsecond. Approximately half of the qubits in the quantum computer will be measured every round, each generating a classical bit of data. A large-scale superconducting computer with 100,000 to one million physical qubits, enough to perform quantum chemistry calculations [73–75] that would be intractable on a classical supercomputer, would, therefore, generate of order 100 billion to one trillion classical bits of information post-second. At a physical layer rate of approximately 0.1%, roughly 1 in 20 of these bits will indicate the detection of nearby quantum errors. The most widely studied method of handling these detection events is to approximate quantum errors as only forming chains that can lie along with certain space-time directions [76], as shown on the screen. This image is intended to represent 2D hardware in the horizontal plane and time running vertically. Each layer of the structure represents a round of error detection. Each great cylinder is a directional long which a chain of errors can form. Red dots represent detection events, generated from the classical input bits. The 3D cylinder structure can be pre-computed classically. We call this structure a lattice. Given a lattice with detection events, we can choose paths connecting detection events in pairs or connecting them to the nearest boundary such that the total path length is minimal. The algorithm that does this is called minimum weight perfect matching. Choosing which pairs of detection events to match can be done by treating the cylinders like water pipes with water flowing more quickly along fatter pipes. Pouring water into a detection event creates an exploratory region. When two exploratory regions touch only each other, the associated detection events can be matched. This relatively simple operation is well-suited to implementation in an FPGA [77]. More complicated cases with multiple colliding regions would be handled in CPUs. We have found that a single core of a modern CPU is sufficient to handle the output of approximately 100 physical qubits. This still leaves one planning a 1,000 to 10,000 core machine just to handle the error correction. It is not enough to use a standard operating system, which can pause processing on any core for multiple milliseconds. Instead, a custom real-time operating system is required and very likely custom hardware for CPU to CPU communication, to achieve very low latency processing. Going back to state distillation and recalling that time runs vertically, processing must be low latency. Ideally, sub 10 micro-second as every green box in the structure is included or not based on decisions made on corrective measurement results. If classical processing were high latency, the quantum computation itself would need to be slowed down by inserting additional rounds of quantum error detection. In summary, an error correction system for a large-scale quantum computer, one capable of performing classically intractable quantum chemistry calculations [74, 75, 78–82], is envisaged to consist of thousands of CPUs and FPGAs connected in a custom manner to achieve sub-10-microsecond latency processing. This level of performance is required to avoid significant additional error detection overhead. Research towards such a system is underway.

30 Fault-Tolerant Quantum Computation with Superconducting Qubits: Challenges with Large-Scale Systems

we have discussed detecting bit-flip errors using the white shapes of the surface code and phase flip errors using the dark shapes. Long chains of bit flip, as shown in red, or phase flips, as shown in green, are, however, undetectable. Studying the red line, we can see that there are two-bit flips touching each adjacent white shape, so, no local parity change and no detection. This gives us the opportunity to store and protect data. If we start all data qubits in zero then start detecting errors, we will create and protect a logical zero state. If instead, after starting

all data qubits in zero, we bit flip those along the red line then start detecting errors, we will create and protect a logical one state. Logical plus and minus can be prepared similarly, starting with old data qubits in plus and phase flipping along the green line. With logical initialization out of the way, we move on to a logical measurement. A logical measurement in the z basis corresponds to measuring each individual qubit in the z basis. After the many results of this transversal measurement are corrected, the overall logical measurement will be the parity of the measurements along the green line. Similarly, logical x -basis measurement is implemented using transversal x -basis measurements. we are not restricted to measuring individual logical qubits in the x or z basis. we can also measure multi-logical qubit operators such as logical zz , as shown. Logical zz corresponds to the parity of the two logical qubits. The large-scale fault-tolerant version of what one of the white half circles does to a pair of physical qubits. Indeed, the logical parity is measured by combining the parity of many white shapes. The parity of all the white shapes marked with blue dots gives us the parity of the two green lines. With a bit of extra effort, we can also measure logical operators like x , xz . we will notice that some shapes are half white and half dark. This just means the conversion from bit flip detection to phase flip detection using Hadamard gates is done at different times on different qubits around the shape. Again, the multi-logical measurement reduces to taking the parity of a large number of local parities indicated with blue dots. What can we do with multi-body logical measurements? It turns out a lot. Take, for example, the familiar CNOT gate. This can be broken into four gates, initialization to 0, measure xx , measure zz , then measure in the x -basis. All of these gates touch the central ancilla qubit with the CNOT control and target, top and bottom, respectively. Three additional single qubits can be seen, but these would be implemented in classical software [83]. The logical upright measurement approach can also be readily extended to give single control multi-target CNOT gates. For most of the remainder of this section, we will focus on explaining how to implement a logical T gate. T gates consume T states. So, really, we need to explain how to repair T states. The first stage of preparing a T state is an injection, which, using a method invented by Ying Li, involves starting with a single physical qubit and then turning on error detection in a particular way. If errors are detected early on, which happens about 50% of the time at gate error rates around 10 to the minus 3, the injection fails and must be repeated. This means that to have a high probability of success of injecting a T state at a particular place in a quantum computer at a particular time during an algorithm, we need enough space and time for multiple injection attempts. To keep images as simple as possible, an injection attempt will be represented by a red cuboid. The displayed image covers enough space and time up to 20 attempts. When an attempt succeeds, that logical qubit would be expanded to the full available space for more robust storage. Even when successful, the error rate of the logical T state is approximately the error rate of a single two cubic gate, so, not good enough for fault-tolerant quantum computation. Injected T states must be distilled to lower the error rate. There are many ways to distill T states. we will focus on 15 to 1 state distillation, meaning 15 injected T states are required to produce a single better T state. The circuit achieving this at first glance consists of many single controlled multi-target CNOT gates, which is great since we know how to do these with low overhead. However, the situation is really even better than this. The combination of plus state initialization followed by single control multi-target CNOT is equivalent to multi-qubit logical measurement. That is, we can replace every plus initialization with zero initialization, and each of the five columns of CNOTs with an 8-bodied logical x measurement. we are probably wondering what these five strange 3D objects are. Each one represents an 8-body logical x measurement. They are ordered left to right in exactly the same manner as the five columns of CNOT gates in the previous image. The central rectangle in each represents an ancilla patch performing the 8-body logical x measurement. The 16 cubes in each represent the 16 logical qubits in the quantum circuit. Those on the left represent the bottom eight qubits. Those on the right, the top eight in reverse

order. So, the top qubit in the circuit is the bottom right cube. we should notice that not all of the cubes are interacting with anything in the left-most 3D object. Essentially, this means we are initializing logical qubits before we actually need them, which is pointless since it just provides extra time for errors to occur. Stacking these five objects one on top of another to represent time running vertically and removing unnecessary cubes and adding in state injection and a few extra pieces to perform the actual T gates at the end of the circuit, we get a nice engine-like picture of essentially 3D quantum assembly code designed to produce distilled T states. The distilled output of this engine would have an error rate of approximately $35P$ cubed, where P is the two-qubit physical gate error rate. For many algorithms, a single level of distillation would be insufficient. we would need to pipe the output of one level into a second level. While this might look very complicated, note that it is really just a bunch of multi-qubit x measurements and T gates that collectively output two low error T states. The two outputs correspond to the two white cubes closest to the front of the image. To give a sense of the scale of the image, if two-qubit gates had an error rate of 10 to the minus 3 , approximately 150,000 physical qubits would be required. if a single round of error detection took one microsecond, the two outputs would be space around 200 microseconds apart. The quantum equivalent of an end gate requires four T states, so, nearly a millisecond to execute. Think about that the next time we hear someone say that quantum computers are fast. Fortunately, problems that exist with quantum computers have an exponential advantage. So, even this huge constant factor disadvantage can be overcome. Note also that if we can get the two-qubit gate error rate down to 10 to the minus 4 , fewer than 15,000 qubits would be required, and the rate of distillation will be doubled. Given many qubits, we could also use many T state factories to achieve whatever distillation rate we desired to achieve faster quantum computation. To finish with a less complicated figure, what we see now is an example of how one might divide up a large square quantum computer into dark patches that represent protected logical qubits, a large open rectangle representing a T state factory, and white squares representing parts permitting logical qubits to be moved around and interacted. Note that the factory is a large but not dominant source of overhead. Not so, long ago, it was frequently necessary to devote 90% or more of the area of a quantum computer to T state production to achieve a reasonable quantum algorithm run times. Then new visibly lower fraction reflects significant improvements in distillation and a shift in focus to quantum chemistry algorithms where massive overhead reduction has been achieved in recent years.

26. Surface Code Introduction; The surface code is a type of quantum error correction code. Which of the following are true for the surface code

- The surface code relies solely on nearest-neighbor interactions between qubits.
- The surface code can detect and correct for both bit-flip and phase-flip errors.
- The surface code error threshold is around 1%.
- The surface code is a leading candidate for solid-state quantum error correction implementations

Solution:

Due to the nearest-neighbor interactions, a relatively lenient threshold around 1%, and the ability to correct for both bit-flip and phase-flip errors, the surface code is a leading candidate for solid-state implementations of quantum error correction.

27. BitFlip Events; Referring to the surface-code qubit array shown in the section, assume that all data qubits are initialized in-state $|0\rangle$. If each of the data qubits along a vertical line from the bottom edge to the top edge of the array are flipped to state $|1\rangle$, then which of the following are true.

- These bit-flip events are detectable using the measure qubits since the surface code can detect bit-flip errors.
- These bit-flip events are not detectable since each measure qubit touches two data qubits, and therefore there is no change in parity.
- Because the vertical line of bit flips is not detectable as an error, and it can be used to encode logical $|1\rangle$.
- Flipping the vertical line of data qubits back to $|0\rangle$ is also not detectable using the measure qubits, and this state is an encoding of logical $|0\rangle$.

Solution:

A vertical line of data qubits that connects the bottom edge to the top edge of the qubit array has the property that each measure qubit next to the line will touch two data qubits. Therefore, if all data qubits in the line switch state, there is no detectable change in parity by the measure qubits. The same concept is true for a horizontal line connecting the left and right edges of the array. Note that if the line of data qubits stops short of an edge, then the measure qubit at the end of the line will touch only one data qubit and detect the bit flip as a change in parity. In this way, lines of data qubits connecting edges of the array are unique.

28. Quantum Response Function; Consider an ideal qubit rotation about the x-axis at an angle θ , $R_x(\theta)$. If the angle of the rotation θ is affected by a systematic error ϵ , then

- The implemented gate can be written as $M_x(\theta) = R_x(\theta(1 + \epsilon))$.
- The quantum response function for a π_x pulse is given by the probability of transition between the ground and excited states when a π pulse about the x-axis is applied to the system.
- The quantum response function quantifies the effect of the systematic errors ϵ .
- When there is no systematic error, $\epsilon = 0$, the quantum response is equal to zero.

Solution:

The quantum response function quantifies the effect of systematic errors, and, for a π_x pulse, it is given by the probability of transition between the ground $|0\rangle$ and excited $|1\rangle$ states when a π pulse on the x-axis is implemented, $|\langle 1|M_x(\pi)|0\rangle|^2$, where the implemented gate can be written as,

$$\begin{aligned} M_x(\pi) &= R_x(\pi(1 + \epsilon)) \\ &= \cos(\pi(1 + \epsilon))I - i \sin(\pi(1 + \epsilon))X. \end{aligned}$$

When the systematic error is zero, $\epsilon = 0$, the quantum response is maximal and equal to one.

29. Magnetic Flux Noise; In a superconducting flux qubit, the energy level separation between the ground and excited state, $|0\rangle$, and $|1\rangle$, can fluctuate due to local magnetic field fluctuations in the qubit environment., the energy difference determines the rate at which relative phase accrues between the components $|0\rangle$ and $|1\rangle$.

Which of the statements regarding the impact of magnetic flux noise in a flux qubit is correct?

- Fluctuations in the magnetic field translate to qubit energy fluctuations.
- Fluctuations in the magnetic field translate to fluctuations of the relative phase accrual rate during free evolution.
- Fluctuations of the relative phase during free evolution lead to dephasing.

- All of the above.

Solution:

An external magnetic field sets the energy difference between the states of a flux qubit. Thus, fluctuations in the magnetic field translate to qubit energy fluctuations. The oscillation frequency during the free evolution of a qubit in the equator of the Bloch sphere is set by the energy difference between the states of a flux qubit. This is why fluctuations in the magnetic flux translate to fluctuations of oscillation frequency during free evolution. Fluctuations of oscillation frequency during free evolution creates dephasing when averaging over an ensemble of qubits, or over several implementations of the experiment on one qubit.

30. Ramsey Experiment; A Ramsey experiment is sensitive to the energy difference between the two levels of a qubit or an atom., recall that energy is proportional to frequency through Planck's constant, $E=hf$. Thus, a Ramsey experiment can form the basis for ultra-precise atomic clocks [84,85] by monitoring the frequency of an atomic transition with stable energy levels. The current metrological definition of a second is 9.192.631.770 cycles of two particular states of a Caesium atom in a Ramsey experiment.

Consider a Ramsey experiment, in which the qubit (atom) is prepared in-state $|0\rangle$. A $\pi/2$ pulse along the σ_x axis brings the Bloch vector to the equator. In the qubit frame of reference (that is, not using a rotating reference frame, the Bloch vector will rotate around the equator at a frequency f . After free evolution for a time τ , a second $\pi/2$ pulse is applied along the σ_x axis. A measurement is then made that records the projection of the Bloch vector onto the σ_z axis.

Assume ideal pulses, no noise, and operation in the qubit frame. Which of the following statements is true?

- If $\tau = 0$, the qubit will be measured in-state $|1\rangle$.
- If τ is such that the qubit rotates halfway around the equator, the qubit will be measured in-state $|0\rangle$.
- If τ is such that the qubit rotates one time around the equator, the qubit will be measured in-state $|1\rangle$.
- The inverse of the time τ that takes to qubit to make one rotation around the equator is the qubit frequency.

Solution:

The qubit is left to evolve around the equator for a given period of τ . The energy difference between the two levels of a qubit causes the qubit to rotate around the z-axis of the Bloch sphere. This energy is proportional to frequency, $E = hf$, where h is Planck's constant. Thus, measuring the time τ for a single rotation around the equator is a measure of the frequency of $f = 1/\tau$.

31. Spin Echo; A "spin-echo" is a procedure implemented by adding a π pulse during a free-evolution period. It is used to reduce the effect of certain types of stochastic noise. Which of the following descriptions is correct about spin echo?

- It refocuses incoherent evolution introduced by a noisy environment.
- It mitigates coherent, low-frequency noise.
- It generally works for noise spectra that increase with frequency.

Solution:

A spin-echo procedure can only correct for stochastic noise from the environment that produces

a coherent (reversible) evolution of the qubit. It generally works for noise spectra that decrease with frequency, because adding a π pulse will push the filter function centroid out to higher frequencies.

32. Rotary Echo; A rotary echo is a procedure used to reduce the effect of certain types of stochastic noise during driven evolution. Which of the following descriptions is true about a rotary echo?

- It reduces the effect of coherent, but stochastic, evolution introduced by the noise in the driving field.
- By reversing the driving field at the mid-point of the driven evolution, this procedure refocuses the Bloch vector.
- The procedure works for environmental noise spectral densities that increase with frequency.

Solution:

Rotary echo, like spin echo, is applicable to environmental noise spectral densities that decrease with frequency.

Figure 12: Dynamical Decoupling During Free Evolution

$$= \exp \left[-\frac{t^2}{2\hbar^2} \left(\frac{\partial E_{01}}{\partial \Phi} \right)^2 \int d\omega S_{\Phi}(\omega) \overbrace{g_N(\omega t)}^{\text{Filter function shapes noise}} \right]$$

for Gaussian-distributed fluctuations

sensitivity of qubit energy to fluctuations Φ

strength (variance) of fluctuations

Figure 13: Dynamical Decoupling During Free Evolution

Figure 14: Dynamical Decoupling During Driven Evolution

Carr – Purcell (– Meiboom – Gill) Sequence

Figure 15: Dynamical Decoupling During Driven Evolution

31 Computational Complexity and Quantum Supremacy: Introduction to Complexity Theory

Let us begin by describing the sort of problems that we might want to solve. In general, when we say that we want to compute something, what we mean usually is that we are computing a function. So, there is some function f that its input is a binary string, and whose output is a binary string. When we write $0, 1^*$, what we mean is the set of strings of any length? So, $0, 1^*$ means the union over n from 0 to ∞ . So, this is a compact way of saying we have just taken a string of any length and output another binary string of any length. Because we can encode anything into bits, we can put any kind of standard function that we are interested in in this paradigm. So, this includes matrix multiplication, shortest path in a graph, integer factorization, the halting problem. This last one asks if we have some code and a given input, will that code ever terminate. All of these are functions that we can define on bit strings. Even though a matrix is described in terms of letting us say it is a matrix full of integers, we can write those integers. Alternatively, if they are rational, we can write those in terms of bits. They are real numbers. We can approximate them in terms of bits. All of these problems, even though their inputs may not look a priori like they are in terms of bits, we can always encode them in some way. Some of these are, much, much harder than others. So, when we are talking about complexity theory [86], the first task that we usually consider is computing functions. It is often helpful to simplify to the case where the answer is one bit. Partly to simplify some of the proofs, partly, it is just convenient. Thus, a lot of what we will be discussing are describing to our conventions in the field of complexity theory where they could have defined it a different way. However, since the literature is mostly in terms of a particular convention, we want us to be familiar with it. So, the usual convention is to discuss a special case of functions called languages. What that means is just that the function has a 1-bit output? So, instead of outputting a string of any length, it just outputs a single bit. This has the same computational power as functions. We should not say the same. Nearly the same computational power as a general function, because we could always give this one more input that tells us which bit of the string we are interested in. Then, by calling this 1-bit function repeatedly, we can extract all the information from a general function—for example, integer factorization. We take in a number. We output its prime factorization. That really seems like a function with many bits of output. However, we could ask we could say input a number, as well as another index i , and then tell the i -th bit of the prime factorization. So, now that is just one bit. If we can have access to that function, we can call it repeatedly. We

can read out all the bits of the prime factorization. There is a little bit of overhead in that we have to call this function many times. It is not the most efficient way to do it on a computer. However, there is not a big overhead in moving from the language picture to the function picture. Now, we might ask, why do we call it a language just because it a 1-bit output? Furthermore, the reason is, and this is also part of what makes it mathematically and a little bit nicer. If we have a 1-bit output, then we can describe the whole function by just specifying the set that gets mapped to 0, or the set that gets mapped to 1. So, let us define l to be f inverse of 1. In other words, the set of strings that gets mapped to 1. Thus, we say l is the language that describes this function. This is a subset of $0, 1$ star. So, instead of discussing a function, we could just discuss a subset of strings corresponding to the inputs that give rise to one. We say that to decide on the language, and we should accept x in the language, or reject x , not in the language. So, we could think of this problem as instead of computing it bit, just equivalently, we can say it is determining membership in a set. If we are in the set l , we want to accept the input. If we are not on the set l , we want to reject the input—just different terminology for the same basic math. We want to output 1, which we call to accept, or 0, which we call reject. Thus, any general problem we can phrase is the yes/no problem. That is all that is going on. The language picture is, however, conventional. When we discuss complexity classes, we will mostly discuss it in terms of languages, although we can imagine the other versions.

32 Classical Complexity Theory: Promise Problems

So, these are the basic problems that we would like to solve. There are also some more complicated ones, which are often useful to discuss. So, one that comes up is promise problems. What this means is that there is instead of the input being all strings, we only need the input to be a subset of strings. So, we only need the correct answer when x belongs to some set p , which is some subset of strings. So, we could say that our input is promised to be in that set. Our algorithm only needs to run on strings satisfying the promise. When it is outside of that set, we do not need any guarantee on what our program does. The last type of problem we might consider is sampling problems. These are a generalization of functions. So, the function we can take in an input, and we are supposed to output a bit string. However, more generally, we might say, associated with every input x is some distribution that we would like to sample from. So, given input x , sample perhaps approximately from a probability distribution, d sub x . So, instead of having some output that is a deterministic string, now the goal is to output a sample from some distribution parameterized by x . So, we can see this is a significant generalization of functions, and also, in some cases, useful to consider. There are other types of problems we can consider as well, and our goal is to output a quantum state. However, we think this is probably a good first pass at the range of computational tasks that we might ask something to do. We guess we should say that promise problems modify all of the others, right? So, a promise problem could be a language, a function, or a sampling problem. Actually, we will mention one more, which is a relation. In this, there are multiple correct answers. So, we have $\sum r$, which is a subset of zero one star given zero one star. Given x , the goal is to output y such that xy is in the relation. So, we can see this one example is we could view integer factorization also in this way. The goal is given a number, output any prime factor. Right? Thus, it could be multiple correct answers. So, these are the more advanced types of problems. Most things we can express just in terms of languages, but it can sometimes be convenient to look at these other types of problems.

33 Models of Computing: Circuits

So, let us discuss models of computing. This will be kind of like the problems that there are we going to give we a list of models of computing, but they are partially overlapping. These are attributes that can be combined with each other. So, the first one is one that we have seen already, which is the circuit model. So, in this, we have some bits, x_1 through x_n . if we have classical circuits, we combine them via gates like AND, and NOT, and OR. if it is a classical circuit so, classical circuits could have unbounded fan-in AND/OR fan-out. what this means is we could take the AND of many different bits. That could be a valid thing to do. then the output of that AND, we could feed into many, many other gates. There is, in principle, no restriction on this. Now we may prefer to consider special classes of classical circuits. we might prefer to consider ones only with bounded fan-in and fan-out. Fan-in means how many wires go in. Fan-out means how many wires go out. we might also prefer to consider reversible circuits. So, reversible is a special case. However, for classical circuits, we are not restricted to consider bounded fan-in, and out the same way, we are for quantum unitary circuits [87]. So, compare, whereas for quantum circuits, the gates are unitary, and we start with some ancilla qubits in the zero state, we do not need ancillas in the classical case because we can kind of create more bits as we go along. The internal wires of the circuit are kind of like bits. So, if we have an AND and it has 100 outputs, those can be like the inputs to the next layer of the circuit. Whereas quantumly, if every gate is unitary, that means it has the same number of inputs and outputs. If we have control of NOT gate, two qubits go in, two qubits to go out, Toffoli gate, three qubits go in, three qubits go out. So, the gates are not going to create any extra data. we have to put them all in at the start with a bunch of ancillas initialized to the zero states. It is kind of the usual model of computing we have seen so far. So, as we are discussing these models of computing, we also want to kind of measure how complex they are. So, complexity theory is distinguished from computability theory. Computability theory says can we, yes or no, compute this function, or this relation, or this promise problem, whatever. Complexity theory says, given that we know we can compute it, how hard is it to compute it? How much time does it take? How much effort? To measure this for circuits, let us draw a model of a circuit again. Let us say we have a bunch of gates, some more gates. Then we measure. If it is a language, then we get the answer, which is, let us say, accept or reject, one or zero. So, how do we measure the complexity of such a circuit? So, the number of bits is called the width of the circuit. That is kind of how much memory it takes to run it. The amount of time it takes is called the depth. here, we imagine that the gates are in layers. If two gates happen on disjoint pairs of qubits, we can do them in parallel. Thus, in a one-time step, we could hit many different pairs of qubits with gates at the same time. the depth measures the number of layers in this kind of decomposition. then finally another measure is to say what is the number of gates. So, the size just counts the number of gates, which, in some cases, is also a measure of the amount of effort we have to put into the circuit. so, circuits can be measured in terms of their width, depth, and/or size as a way to measure their complexity. so, the question is what depth means in terms of the unitaries. Each one of these gates is a unitary operator. Size is the number of gates we apply. However, in this circuit, we see we did three gates all at the same time. So, in the circuit we have drawn, the depth would just be three. Here is one layer of gates. Here is another layer of gates. Here is one more layer of gates. The measurement we do not count. Some people would count it. However, we will choose not to count it. So, the circuit model is a very appealing one in many ways. we guess the good feature of the circuit model is that it is a very concrete model of computation. However, they have one big flaw, which is when we defined a function, we said the input could be any length, like matrix multiplication. That is just one function. It includes multiplying two by two matrices, or seven by seven matrices, or rectangular matrices. we do not want to

define a new function for every size of the matrix. we just want to say matrix multiplication, and it encompasses all of those. Nevertheless, circuits are kind of funny. we can think of them on a classical circuit we could imagine actually soldering these things together. On a quantum circuit, this is just really a sequence of laser pulses, or magnetic fields, or whatever. However, they always have a fixed number of inputs. Any circuit does not have a variable-sized input. It has a definite number of bits that go in, a definite sequence of operations. Thus, the one big flaw of circuits is that they depend on the input size n . let us write n when we write the absolute value of x , and we mean the length of the string x . So, n is the number of bits of input. It is the length of the input x . So, for every value of n , we have to specify a circuit. Thus, when we tell we have a recipe for solving the problem, if we are going to tell we a circuit, that is only a recipe for one value of n . So, to fully specify how to solve a problem, we have to give we a circuit for every possible input length n . that is kind of an unsatisfactory feature of the model. In part, one reason why it is unsatisfactory is if we just say for each value n we want a circuit, the width, and depth, and size should be some bounded functions of n . Nevertheless, that is it. we are allowing the circle to depend on n arbitrarily up to those limits. we could smuggle in information in that way. we could have it so that it could depend on n in a very hard to compute sort of way, in a way that would make this a somewhat unrealistic model of computing. So, that is kind of the one drawback of circuits. Let us just expand on this a little bit. Suppose we want to know does the n th Turing machine halt? So, we will come back to say in a minute what a Turing machine is. by halt, we mean if we just start it on a blank input, does it go into an infinite loop, or does it stop? Moreover, it turns out that there is no algorithm that will compute this for all inputs. However, we could smuggle it into something that could be solved on a circuit. we could just say, look at the length of the input. That tells n . we want to know does the n th Turing machine halt. because this model lets the circuit depend arbitrarily on n , the circuit could just do nothing, just ignore the input and just output zero or one immediately, and thereby would solve this problem. So, that sort of recognizes a flaw of the circuit model in that it gives us this uncontrolled dependence on n , which could give us in a sense too much computing power. There are ways around that which we will come back to in a minute. we end up still using circuits. we just have to kind of deal with this flaw. Another flaw, which is related, is that it has no loops. If we ever write code, and we write a program with no loops in it, our program is we would not want to write a long program that way. we are kind of only do that for a very simple program. Loops are a kind of an important feature of programming. No loops are also a pro. It means that there are no infinite loops. we know the circuit will always end after a certain amount of time. However, we give up some of the powerful features of programming that make this possible. so, that is one model of computing, which sort of gets at a lot of what computers do but misses out some of the important things, like being independent of the size of the input and having recursion and loops.

34 Models of Computing: Random, Quantum, and Non-Determinism

The basic models, we said, are circuits and Turing machines. These are good ways of describing deterministic computations. This is a section on quantum, so, let us discuss quantum, and even build up to that randomized computations. So, randomness is something that can go into the computing model. There are kind of two ways of doing it. We can either have some extra inputs, let us say r_1 through r_m are random bits. Alternatively, our gates or Turing machine rules can be random. For example, in that Turing machine table, we could say with $1/2$ probability, if

the current position is 0, then with $1/2$ probability do this, and with $1/2$ probability do that. Alternatively, we could add not just AND, OR, and NOT gates, but one extra gate called the “random gate,” that just outputs 0 or 1 randomly each time we use it. So, that is one way we could do it. Alternatively, we could have all our operations to be deterministic, but we push our randomness to the beginning. We say we are going to take in an extra input, which is a long string of random bits that could either be more inputs to the gates or more inputs to the Turing machine. We are going to use that as a source of randomness. These are basically equivalent. Thus, either one of these is a way of modeling randomness. Finally, let us discuss quantum. So, we kind of already described quantum circuits. We do not want to say too much more about it, because it is also the model we are used to seeing. So, quantum circuits have unitaries. They have ancillas in the zero state. They have some depth, some width, some size. The only drawback of them is this uncontrolled dependence on the input size. Just like classical circuits, they have the same problem. Thus, there are two ways around this. So, there are quantum Turing machines. They were defined in a paper about 20 years ago. However, almost nobody uses these. These are rarely used. Instead, one of the main preferred models is a classical Turing machine that outputs a quantum circuit. So, that is the compromise model we were discussing. For classical circuits, it does not make a whole lot of sense. We mean, there are cases in which it does, but often, if the Turing machine could output a circuit, it could just go on and compute the output of that circuit. Why bother outputting a circuit just to run it a minute later? However, here, we can have the advantage of a classical Turing machine. We can have a program with loops, recursion, a finite program for all input sizes. Then that could output a quantum circuit for each input length. Thus, then, this sort of keeps the benefits of the quantum circuit model, while using a classical Turing machine. So, when we discuss quantum circuits, formally, this is the computing model that we usually mean, that almost everybody means when they discuss quantum circuits being able to compute something. There is one last model, which is called the non-determinism. If we have discussed of NP, that is where this model is used. What it means is we can think of it as the classical computer takes the OR of two branches of a computation. So, if we go back to randomized and quantum, we can think of when we make a random choice, we are sort of averaging over two branches. If we keep making random choices, we are going to average over many, many branches. Then we are going to end up these branches will add up to some accept probability or add up to some reject probability. However, we are spreading probability among many branches. Quantumly, we can do something like a Hadamard that will put amplitude on what we could consider two different branches. Non-determinism is a physically unreasonable form of computation that can be useful for thinking about proof systems. There are some nice features of it that way, but it does not correspond to something we can compute in the real world. The idea is that our computer can go into two branches. Those branches can further branch. So, after n steps, we could have 2^n possible branches. Then, in the end, if any of those branches accept, the overall computer will accept. If all of them reject, then the overall computer will reject. That is what we mean by taking the OR of those branches. Accept corresponds to 1. So, if there are any 1's in the output, the OR is going to be 1. So, this is called non-determinism. We will discuss more this a little bit later. However, we could, for now, just think of it as another kind of wacky model of computation.

33. Definition of a Language; Computation generates an output for a given input, directly analogous to a mathematical function. In a computer, the input and output are represented by strings of zeros and ones, denoted as $\{0,1\}^*$. An algorithm calculates the action of a function f given an input string. To study the complexity of a function, that is, how hard it is to compute it is convenient to restrict the problem to functions with a single-bit output, zero or one, without loss of generality. Using this particular type of function, we can then introduce the definition of

a Language. What is Language?

- It is the set of strings of zeros and ones ($\{0, 1\}^*$) that when the input to a function f results in an output equal to 1.
- It is the inverse of the function f applied to output equal to 1.
- It is a subset of all possible strings of zeros and ones ($\{0, 1\}^*$). Solution:
 - a) and b) are the same definition but said in different ways. Although c) is not a formal definition, it is true, and it can be inferred from a).

34. The Circuit Model; There are different models of computing that depict how a given calculation is performed with a computer. Throughout, we have often represented our computation with circuits composed of wires and gates. Although this circuit model is concrete and intuitive, it has certain disadvantages. Which of the following are disadvantages of using the circuit model of computing

- Circuits depend on the size of the input, i.e., the length of the input string of zeros and ones
- Circuits might not halt, meaning that for certain problems, the program might continue running indefinitely.
- Circuits have no analog of a “software loop”, an important feature of programming.
- All of the above.

Solution:

Since circuits have no loops, or recursive structures, that prevent completion of a task, they will generally run until they produce output and then stop. thus, circuits will not fall into infinite loops, which is one advantage of this model.

35 Standard Classical Computational Complexity Classes: Deterministic Time

We have problems that we want to solve, we have models of computing, and the way that people put these together is they discuss complexity classes. These are, basically, classes of problems that all have similar complexity. So, one example, $DTIME f$ of n stands for deterministic time. What this means, we say that a language belongs to $DTIME$ of f of n , if there exists a Turing machine, m , such that m of x always halts with the correct answer. So, in other words, accept if x is in L , reject if x is not in L . So, so, far, that just means we have computed it correctly, but what about the time? Then we want to say in less than f of the size of x steps. So, for example, we might have $DTIME$ of $100 n$ cubed, which means these are the languages that if the input is n bits, we can solve in at most 100 times n cubed steps.

36 Complexity Classes: Polynomial Exponential and PSPACE

This is a little bit precise. Usually, we do not care if the Turing machine takes $100 n$ cubed or $300 n$ cubed. We just want to know the scaling because, as we change from different memory access models, it might change the runtime a little bit. We do not care about that too much. We kind of want to know very crudely, is this poly time or exponential time. So, instead of just

looking at D time for very specific functions, usually, we just discuss at these very crude ones so, P, probably the most famous complexity class, is the union of D time and the k for all values of k. So, k just ranges over all integers. Thus, this just means there is some polynomial of n, and we can solve the function in time that grows at most like a polynomial event. We could also discuss exponential time, which is the union over 2 to the n to the k. So, it means all the problems for which there is some finite k such that we can solve it in time 2 to the n to the k. So, in general, P, polynomial time, corresponds to the things that we think are relatively easy to compute, and we might object we might say, well, n or n squared seems like reasonable scaling. It was n to the 17 that does not sound very reasonable. That does not sound so easy to compute. N to the 100 already when n is 2, that is going to be out of reach. The reason why people study P is that, empirically, for problems that we are interested in, if we start with an algorithm, it takes time n to the 84, we tend to find further improvements. Usually, if people care about the problem, they find ways of doing it faster and bringing that number down. There is no law of nature that says it has to be that way. However, because it has often been true, people find P to be a useful organizing principle. Often m squared is not enough. We really want to be linear in n. It is not like P is the end of the story. However, it is a first pass at what is efficient or what is not. So, that is time. We might also consider space. So, we say the class space f of n is the set of languages that can be solved using at most f of n cells of tape. So, we can think of it as we have an infinite tape. However, if the Turing machine solves it without ever going beyond a certain region of tape, then we have not used that much. Thus, we say space of f of n means the space we need to solve the problem is bounded by f of n, the number of cells of tape. Again, we prefer to be vague about how much and just say P space means polynomial space. There is also log space, which is a little trickier to define because then we have to argue why we are not already using n just for the input.

37 Complexity Classes: NP (Nondeterministic Polynomial Time)

There are a few other classes that are important. One of them is NP. So, NP is the set of problems that we can verify in polynomial time [88], and here, when we say verify, we mean only if the answer is yes. So, if the answer is yes, there should be a short we are of it, whereas if the answer is no, there does not have to be. Thus, an example of this would be the traveling salesman problem. Can we visit all of these cities without revisiting any city, just visiting each city once? Furthermore, do this where the total length of the route is less than 1,000 miles. If the answer is yes, we can prove that to us easily. We mean, there exists a short proof. It might be hard to come up with. However, there exists a proof, which we can verify easily. The proof is just, here is a list of cities. Then we have to count. Yes, do the miles add up to less than 1,000. If so, we verify that the answer to the original question about does there exist such a route is yes. If the answer is no, like there is no route under 1,000 miles, there might not be a succinct way to communicate that fact, to prove that fact. So, NP, we can think of it as a statement about non-determinism. Like, if a problem has a short proof, then one thing we could do is we could non-deterministically check all the proofs. Essentially, what we want to do is take the OR of all the possible proofs. However, it is also just a statement about what is provable. So, when we said at the beginning, we think we have erased it now complexity theory studies what we can compute quickly, but also what is the power of proof. We can think of NP as being a statement about proof complexity. The way we like to think of this that makes it simple to say that f is in NP if f of x can be expressed as a giant OR of g of XY where y should be a bit string whose

length is polynomial in x . Sorry, the length of x . This is the length of x to the c . So, c if some constant. Y is, therefore, a polynomial length of x . g should be polynomial-time computable. So, the wasting of NP is we have something polytime commutable, but we take the OR of it over an exponentially large number of things. Thus, if f of x is equal to 1, the way we can demonstrate that to us is by exhibiting a y for which g of XY is 1. So, if f of x equals 1, then the proof of this is the y such that g of XY is equal to 1. If we give us such a y , then g is polytime commutable. We can quickly compute g of XY , verify that equals 1, and thereby be convinced that f of x is equal to 1. If f of x is 0, all that we need is that there is no such proof. If f of x is 0 and we try to convince us that it is 1 by giving some y , we check it. We say, hey, no, g of XY is 0. No matter which y we give we, g of XY will be 0. So, if f of x equals 0, then there is no such proof.

In this section, we are evaluating the computational scaling of a classical or quantum processor from the perspective of a computer scientist. As we know, a quantum computer can outperform a classical computer for a limited set of computational problems. For many problems, a quantum computer performs no better than a classical computer. How can we differentiate these classes of problems? Computational problems are assigned to computational complexity classes [89,90] depending on how efficiently a classical or quantum computer can solve them. For example, a quantum computer can factor integers more efficiently than classical computers can use the best known classical algorithm [91], but it may perform given tasks such as playing chess, proving mathematical theorems, solving the traveling salesman problem, or even multiplying two numbers no better than a classical computer.

Computational problems are classified based on the best algorithms known today. The different complexity classes arise due to the different scaling laws as a function of problem size for the physical resources and the time requirements for these best-known algorithms. For example, computing devices comprise a fixed number of physical memory units and a processor that can perform a certain number of computational steps per time unit. The physical memory of a computing device places an upper bound on the maximum, manageable problem complexity. The number of elementary computational steps required to solve a task can be used as a quantitative measure of time.

Suppose we have a computer that can compute the solutions to a fictitious problem with 2 variables of interest using 100 memory units and 4 computational steps. For 3 variables of interest, the computing device needs 1000 memory units and 8 computational steps. 4 variables require 10000 memory units and 16 computational steps. Obviously, the physical requirements for this fictitious problem scale unfavorably. The required memory is said to scale exponentially, 10^n , with the number of variables n . In contrast, the number of computational steps scales as n^2 . Computational problems for which a parameter scales as n^x , for a constant x , as n increases, are referred to as polynomial in n .

Here, we will focus on problems and complexity classes that show a polynomial physical memory scaling. The complexity class describing problems with polynomial memory requirements independent of the respective time complexity is referred to as PSPACE.

An example of a problem that scales polynomially in both time and memory is multiplication. The multiplication of two n -bit numbers requires n^2 computational steps to generate the solution.

Table 3: The multiplication of two n-bit numbers requires n^2 computational steps

binary factors	N_1	\times	N_2	steps
$N_1 = N_2 = 001 \rightarrow n = 1$	$1 \cdot 2^0$	\times	$1 \cdot 2^0 = 00001$	$1^2 = 1$
$N_1 = N_2 = 011 \rightarrow n = 2$	$1 \cdot 2^0 \times 1 \cdot 2^0 + 1 \cdot 2^0$ $+ 1 \cdot 2^1 \times 1 \cdot 2^0 + 1 \cdot 2^1$	\times \times	$1 \cdot 2^1$ $1 \cdot 2^1 = 01001$	$2^2 = 4$
$N_1 = N_2 = 100 \rightarrow n = 3$	$0 \cdot 2^0 \times 0 \cdot 2^0 + 0 \cdot 2^0 \times 0 \cdot 2^1 + 0 \cdot 2^0$ $+ 0 \cdot 2^1 \times 0 \cdot 2^0 + 0 \cdot 2^1 \times 0 \cdot 2^1 + 0 \cdot 2^1$ $+ 1 \cdot 2^2 \times 0 \cdot 2^0 + 1 \cdot 2^2 \times 0 \cdot 2^1 + 1 \cdot 2^2$	\times \times \times	$1 \cdot 2^2$ $1 \cdot 2^2$ $1 \cdot 2^2 = 10000$	$4^2 = 16$

Computational problems with algorithms able to compute solutions in polynomial time form the computational complexity class P. Problems in class P can be efficiently computed on a classical computer. Note that here, “efficient” does not necessarily mean “on a human time scale;” it only refers to the scaling law. For example, if a computer has to solve a large, polynomial problem, such as the multiplication of two numbers, each with $n = 10^{100}$ bits, it may still take an unrealistic number of computational steps, 10^{100^2} , to finish in practice, despite being classified as efficient. Rather, the computation is efficient relative to another problem of a similar size but with an exponential time scaling, such as, for example, $2^{10^{100}}$.

Not every problem scales polynomially in time. For example, the traveling salesman problem scales exponentially with the number of cities. The problem is to evaluate the shortest route to visit multiple cities. Additional conditions are that each city is only visited once and that the traveling salesman returns to his original city at the end of his tour. For n cities, there are $n! \propto n^{(n+0.5)}$ different options to check, and evaluating every possibility scales exponentially with n .

In general, a classical computer is unable to solve problems with exponential time requirements efficiently. However, once a solution is presented, it may only take polynomial computational time to confirm the solution. Factoring an integer into two prime numbers is an exponentially hard problem, in general. However, verifying the proposed solution involves a single multiplication, which is polynomial in time, as demonstrated above—problems with solutions that can be verified in polynomial computational time form the NP complexity class. NP stands for Non-deterministic Polynomial-time. Among the problems that can be efficiently evaluated are the problems in class P. If there exists an efficient algorithm to propose a solution to a problem, then they also exist an efficient algorithm to verify the solution.

The hardest computational problems in NP those for which the computation is exponential in time and, hence not in P are assigned to the NP-Complete complexity class [92]. The traveling salesman is an NP-Complete problem [93]. It is exponentially hard to find a solution, but it only takes polynomial time to evaluate the proposed solution. A proposed solution can be easily verified by depicting the proposed solution on a map and verifying that the conditions are not violated.

It is an open question if algorithms exist that are able to solve NP-Complete problems in polynomial time. If such algorithms exist, then NP would consequently collapse into P, meaning they are the same complexity classes, $P = NP$. The search for such algorithms has continued for more than half a century. The inability to find such an algorithm leads most computer scientists to believe that, indeed, $P \neq NP$.

Figure 16: Classical Computational Complexity Classes: PSPACE contains all classes and problems which require a polynomial amount of memory on a conventional computer independent of the number of necessary computational steps to find or verify a solution. P describes the class of classically efficient computable problems. Class NP contains problems that are efficiently verifiable. The hardest problems which are still efficiently verifiable form complexity class NP-Complete.

Figure 1 summarizes the hierarchy of the four introduced complexity classes. Classical computers can efficiently solve computational tasks part of P. In the next section, and we will see how quantum computers perform and which problems it can solve efficiently and which ones it performs similarly to classical computers.

35. DTIME; A complexity class is a set of problems with the same degree of computational complexity. To define certain complexity classes, it is helpful to think in terms of the time it would take to solve a given problem. This concept of “how much time” can be described mathematically using something called $DTIME(f(n))$, where f is a given function (not to be confused with the computed function f in section) and n is the size of the input (previously denoted $|x|$). Which of the following sentences is/are true about DTIME?

- $DTIME(f(n))$ is a set of input strings of zeros and ones.
- $DTIME(f(n))$ is the set of functions that can be computed in a deterministic time shorter than n , where n is the size of the input.
- $DTIME(f(n))$ is the set of languages L that can be solved in deterministic time, equal to or smaller than $f(n)$ steps.

Solution:

c) is the correct definition of DTIME, and a) is a true statement that can be inferred from c).

36. Complexity Classes; Some complexity classes are defined by the scaling law for the amount of time it takes to compute a given set of problems. This time is characterized using the concept of $\text{DTIME}(f(n))$, where $\text{DTIME}(f(n))$ is the set of languages L that can be solved in a deterministic time, equal to or smaller than $f(n)$ steps, where n is the length of the input string of bits. Which of the following are proper definitions of valid complexity classes?

- EXPTIME complexity class: Exponential time is the union of all $\text{DTIME}(f(n))$, where $f(n) = 2^{n^k}$ and k runs over all positive integers.
- P complexity class: Polynomial-time is the union of all $\text{DTIME}(f(n))$, where $f(n) = n^k$ and k runs over all positive integers.
- NP complexity class: Non-Polynomial time is the union of all $\text{DTIME}(f(n))$, where $f(n) \neq n^k$ and k runs over all positive integers.

Solution:

In complexity theory, NP stands for non-deterministic polynomial time, and it is defined by the set of problems that can be solved in polynomial time by a non-deterministic Turing machine.

38 BPP and BQP

The two more important classes, BPP and BQP [94–96], these correspond to random and quantum polynomial time. So, the P or Q here means probabilistic or quantum, and the final P means polynomial time. Thus, that leaves only the B. So, the B stands for bounded error, right? Because if we are doing a deterministic computation, we are always thinking of the same answer. Thus, the correct behavior of the algorithm means it should be the right answer. Pretty clear. If our calculation is random, or quantum, then normally, the answer we get will not always be the same. However, we would like that it is the correct answer most of the time. Thus, here, let us say we are working with languages, so, the answer is a bit. So, we demand that so, here, correctness means that for all x , the probability that the algorithm on input x is equal to f of x is greater than or equal to $2/3$. This is, we guess we should say, for f mapping to 0, 1, i.e., languages, although we guess it would work for functions also. However, it is sort of convenient to use it for languages. So, here, we are allowed to use random gates or quantum gates, and we should get the answer right most of the time. Alg means the algorithm. So, and let us say one more thing, which is, just like the others, these are classes of languages. So, just sort of as objects, we say that L belongs to BQP if there exists a quantum algorithm [97], we know, such that this is true. L here, we should think of as a subset of all the binary strings.

39 BQP-Complete Problem: Quantum Circuit Evaluation

We discuss NP a lot because there are so many kinds of optimization and planning problems that are naturally NP-complete. Thus, it is historically something people have cared about a lot. A lot of the effort has been devoted to NP. But what about quantum computing? Can we do the same thing for BQP? Can we find a complete problem for a BQP? Can we say that this is BQP complete [96], and so, it is unlikely to have a poly-time solution? So, the complete natural problem for BQP, kind of analogous to circuit sat, is called “Quantum Circuit Evaluation.” Furthermore, the problem is the following so, the input is a circuit U . Let us say it is on n qubits. Let us say it starts in the 0 states, applies n squared gates, and at the end of those n squared gates, and it measures the first qubit. So, that is the format of the problem. The particular

input will specify what those n squared gates are. We are promised that the probability of getting output 1 is either greater than $2/3$ or less than $1/3$. We want to determine which is the case. Because remember, for BQP, these are only problems where we get the answer right with probability at least $2/3$. Thus, what that means is if the answer is yes, we get if the answer is 1, we get 1 with probability at least $2/3$. If the true answer was 0, we should get output 1 with a probability of less than $1/3$. So, we should always see outputs. We should never see things that are kind of in the middle. We should only see things that are more than $2/3$ or less than $1/3$. This condition here is called a promise. Remember, we discussed promise problems last time. We said they are not defined in all inputs. So, in this case, we only wanted to define this problem on the inputs that have this property. It is a very non-trivial restriction, and it might be hard to evaluate. However, promises do not have to be easy to evaluate. We just want to restrict attention to this and say, what that means is to solve quantum circuit evaluation, we only need to solve it on the inputs that have this property. Then we would be happy just to solve it in those cases. We claim that this is BQP-complete. So, first of all, we claim it is in BQP. Why is that? Well, if we are giving this input, we just run the circuit, and we measure. We use the output directly. We promised that the output has probably at least $2/3$ of being one thing or the other. Thus, that output, with error probability less than $1/3$, we can distinguish which is the case. If the way we have run it has introduced more errors, let us say from the theorem, we could just amplify. We could just repeat it a few times and drive our error probability below $1/3$. So, it is in BQP. On the other hand, any problem in BQP can be expressed in this way. If we have something in BQP, practically the definition of BQP is to say there exists a circuit that does something like this. We might get nervous. We might say, well, BQP allowed to run polynomial like n to the 17. this only allows n squared gates. We had to pick something concrete, so we picked n squared. Does anyone see how to get around that problem? It shows us; we think some of the subtleties, we think, of poly-time reduction. Remember that is what we need for hardness. We need there to be a polynomial-time reduction from any problem in BQP to this one. The number of gates here is defined in terms of the input to this problem. So, we say, here, we have this many qubits and this many gates. Thus, we start with our original n , and then we might need to do n to the 10 gates. Then we have some new n prime, which is the length of this output, which could be like n to the 20. then we have got n prime qubits and n prime squared gates. That budget is more than enough to accomplish what we want. So, the answer, basically, is this poly-time reduction. Seems very innocent, but it can smuggle in polynomial overheads. The length can get polynomials larger. Thus, it is a very one way to think about this, and it is a very crude notion of complexity. As a practical matter, we care about the difference being n squared and n cubed. However, this crude notion of complexity will really just tell if it is polynomial versus exponential a little bit more than that. However, it is not going to distinguish between different kinds of polynomials. So, that is why we can say very crude things like this. It is enough to give we kind of a first-order answer. If we refine the same techniques, we can get a more refined answer, as well.

40 BQP and BPP: Quantum vs. Classical Complexity

Quantum circuit evaluation, the same thing we were over there. This is not in BPP unless BPP equals BQP. We could have put here P instead of BPP, remember BPP is randomized computation. Randomized seems like a slightly more, we know, closer to quantum. We should say that P is contained in BPP, is contained in BQP. So, just to give we sort of the cast of characters, P is the weakest. Everything else contains P., But these sorts of branches look like they may be incomparable. In other words, it looks like there may be problems in NP that are not

in BQP and vice versa. BBP is a funny beast, so, it is conjectured. We mentioned that we believe that P is not equal to NP, but people also believe, we mean, the conventional wisdom sort of leans towards P being equal to BPP. There is no proof of this either. However, the intuition is, if we want to do random numbers on our computer, we have a pseudo-random number generator. Our computer just calls in a random number generator, but it is a pseudo-random number generator. It makes numbers, a sequence of numbers that are deterministic. However, the structure in them seems to be hard to extract by any program, kind of related to the intuition that we believe P is not equal to NP, we know, that there can be patterns that are present, which we cannot efficiently extract. So, we believe that the random number generator, even though there is information, theoretically, a pattern, it is too hard computationally to extract it. Thus, we can treat the output of the random number of our, sorry, our pseudo-random number generator as though it were true randomness, and our program will do just as well as if it had true randomness. So, that is the argument for why P is equal to BPP. There are some theorems that sort of move in that direction, but it is really conjecture. It is really not proven, but it is believed to be true., we believe that this is not equal to BQP, right? That is why we are interested in quantum computers because we think they can do things we cannot do with a randomized classical computer.

Classical computers can efficiently solve problems in the computational complexity class P. There is a desire (and a question if it is possible) to develop a computational device able to solve exponentially hard problems in NP-Complete and even harder problems. With the complexity classes P, NP, NP-Complete [98], and PSPACE defined, we will now discuss the performance of quantum computers, and where the class of problems a quantum computer can solve efficiently falls within the computational complexity class hierarchy.

Quantum computers outperform classical computers for specific problems, such as factoring large integer numbers, a problem that is believed to be part of NP. The advantage of a quantum computer arises due to its ability to exploit the problem's underlying mathematical structure differently than classical computers can. The quantum computer can determine the prime factors of a large integer number in polynomial time, which is exponentially faster than it takes classical computers to perform the same task.

Can a quantum computer solve NP-Complete problems? As the example of Shor's factoring algorithm suggests, quantum computers are able to outperform classical computers on problems that feature a mathematical structure that can be exploited by the working principles of quantum computers. NP-Complete problems do not seem to exhibit these sorts of favorable mathematical structures. There is no evidence to date that suggests quantum algorithms exist that could outperform classical algorithms for NP-Complete problems.

The classical search problem searching for a particular element in a list composed of n elements can take up to n trials to perform deterministically, and it takes on average $n/2$. Grover's quantum search algorithm finds the particular element in only \sqrt{n} steps [99]. While quantum processors outperform classical computers for some problems, the degree of quantum speedup may only be polynomial in certain cases [100].

There exist other quantum algorithms able to generate minor speedups over the best known classical algorithms for problems in N and NP [15]. Still, there is no evidence that quantum computers can efficiently solve NP-Complete problems [101]. There are proposals for quantum algorithms that may be able to verify a proposed solution in polynomial time for problems outside of NP. However, there is no evidence that quantum computers can outperform classical computers on problems outside of PSPACE. The problems quantum computers can solve efficiently form the computational complexity class BQP, with BQP being an abbreviation for Bounded-error Quantum Polynomial-time.

Complexity Classes

Figure 17: Computational Complexity Classes: PSPACE contains all classes and problems which require a polynomial amount of memory on a conventional computer independent of the number of necessary computational steps to find or verify a solution. P describes the class of classically efficient computable problems. Problems are efficiently computable by a quantum computer form the complexity class BQP. Class NP contains problems that are efficiently verifiable. The hardest problems which are still efficiently verifiable form complexity class NP-Complete.

Quantum computers are apparently more powerful than classical computers for certain problems. However, there is no formal proof that the hierarchy shown in Figure 1 is manifestly true. That is, there is no proof that an “as-yet-undiscovered” classical algorithm could not perform as well as a quantum algorithm for problems in NP where today there is a quantum advantage [102]. The probability that a better classical algorithm exists is likely small, but it is not zero. Thus, quantum computers are able to outperform classical computers for certain tasks, but there is no formal proof that says it must be so.

37. BPP and BQP; Two important complexity classes regarding random and quantum models of computation are BPP and BQP. Which of the following sentences are true about BPP and BQP:

- BPP and BQP are defined by the set of languages that, after computation, lead to the wrong result more than $2/3$ of the time in polynomial computational time.
- BPP and BQP are defined by the set of languages that, after computation, lead to the wrong result of less than $1/3$ of the time in polynomial computational time.
- PP and BQP are defined by the set of languages that, after computation, lead to the correct result more than $2/3$ of the time in exponential computational time.

Solution:

BPP and BQP stand for “Bounded-error Probabilistic Polynomial” time and “Bounded-error Quantum Polynomial” time, respectively. They represent the set of problems that can be computed in polynomial time with a bounded error of less than $1/3$.

38. Relation Between Complexity Classes; Complexity classes can overlap; they need not exclude one another. In fact, some complexity classes are entirely contained within larger complexity classes. Considering the complexity classes, we have studied so far P , NP , BPP , and BQP , which of the following describe valid relationships between these complexity classes? (the notation " $x \subseteq y$ " means "all elements in x are also in y ").

- $P \subseteq BQP \subseteq BPP \subseteq NP$
- $NP \subseteq BPP \subseteq BQP \subseteq P$
- $BPP \subseteq BQP \subseteq P \subseteq NP$
- $P \subseteq BPP \subseteq BQP$

Solution:

It is still an open question whether some of these complexity classes are in fact equal. One conjecture says that $P = BPP$, and we might be familiar with the conjecture that $P \neq NP$, the formal proof of which statement is one of the Millennium Prize Problems.

41 How to Think About Quantum Supremacy: BQP and BPP - A Taste of Quantum Supremacy

This now gives us a way of arguing that a certain quantum thing that a quantum computer can do cannot be done classically. So, this gives rise to what we could call quantum supremacy [103,104]. If L is BQP-complete, then a quantum computer can solve it, and a classical computer cannot. So, then, a quantum computer can solve L . Classical computer-

42 How to Think About Quantum Supremacy: Beyond NP - Counting Solutions

What we want to discuss about next is a way of going, in a sense, beyond NP. It may seem strange. We might think, well, look NP already takes exponential time. However, we want to discuss things were even to verify it takes exponential time. Thus, this is a way of separating NP from things even above it. We will see that it can be useful for reasoning about real-world devices, even devices that are weaker than a universal quantum computer. So, it shows we kind of the remarkable subtlety and flexibility of complexity theory [86]. So, to do this, let us go back to three-set. So, the three-set is a Boolean formula. We put in input. We do these or's and these ands, and the answer is going to be either true or false. Let us say one or 0. So, let us say ϕ of X is equal to 0 if unsatisfied. False one is satisfied, i.e., true. In other words, if all the clauses are true, we say the formula satisfied, ϕ of X is 1. If not, the ϕ of X is 0. This is ϕ at a particular input. now, let us define the count of ϕ to be the total number of satisfying assignments. So, in other words, we sum overall and bitstrings X , ϕ of X . now, we can rephrase the basic problem of NP, in terms of this count function. We can say that an NP-complete task is to determine whether the count of ϕ is either equal to 0 or greater than 0. So, remember, the three set problems ask, given this formula, does there exist an X that satisfies it? Furthermore, that is equivalent to saying, is the total number of solutions positive? Is it one or more versus it equal to 0? So, distinguishing these two cases is an empty NP-complete. ϕ is given. ϕ likes the input. So, we have a problem specified by our input, which is ϕ , and now we want to know

the answer to this question. Is the count of the solution 0 or positive? The question is, is it NP-complete for arbitrary ϕ . the point is NP-completeness referred to as a language, or we could say a problem. So, the language is basically the set of all ϕ that has one or more solutions. We could also think of this as a problem. The problem is given an arbitrary ϕ , determined if it has a satisfying ascent. Thus, problems are never defined for a fixed input. Because if so, there would not be hard. The answer would just be 0 or 1, and that would be the end of that. The key thing is we have to say this is the worst-case complexity, meaning that we have to be able to solve the problem, we demand to be able to solve it for any input ϕ . Just like for factoring. It is not hard to factor the number 1,372,000. Right? Any particular number is not hard because there is an answer. What is hard is factoring an arbitrary number. Just like what is hard is to compute the count of this for an arbitrary ϕ .

43 How to Think About Quantum Supremacy: Beyond NP - Approximate and Exact Counting

So, this is what NP is. Let us now define some things that are kind of harder than this. So, one of them is there is a complexity class for it, but it is not the most natural one. So, we just in to call it the approximate counting problem which says given ϕ at the threshold T, determine whether the count of ϕ is either greater than $2T$ or less than T . So, now, we promise that one of these is the case, and now we are going to determine which one it is. So, T here, we would call it a threshold. So, we are promised there is some threshold. We either have more than let us say 2,000 solutions or less than 1,000. We want to determine which is the case. Alternatively, we have more than 2 to the 100 solutions or less than 2 to the 99 solutions, determine which is the case. It is clearly at least as hard as NP because we could take T to be like $1/2$ or something, and that would include NP. However, we can choose T to be with it whatever we like, so it includes things that look quite different than NP. If we want to distinguish, there are more than 2 to the 1,000 or fewer than 2 to the 99 solutions, that do not look like something we can phrase as an NP problem. So, it looks a priori harder than NP. Then, we can do something else, which is yet harder than this, which is called exact counting. This actually corresponds to the complexity class known as sharp P. This is like sharp. It is kind of dumb. We say sharp like the musical note, but we really mean like the number sign, so it is also called number P. what this is is given ϕ and T, is the count of ϕ either greater than T or less than or equal to T minus 1? So, we are going to think of that as exact counting, except we try to phrase it actually, we sorry. We wrote sharp P. It should really be PP. The reason for that name, it is kind of a tangent, which we will not go on. The point is that it is the third one of these problems. The first one is, is the number 0 or positive? The second one is approximate to within a factor of 2. The third one nails it down exactly, figure out exactly is it above this threshold or below it? Are there more than 1,000,300,042 solutions, or are there fewer than that? Again, this does not look like it reduces to NP. It also does not look like it reduces to exact counting. If we can estimate it to within a factor of 2, that does not give the ability to nail it down on the nose, especially if the numbers we are discussing are exponentially large. Let us try to give us an example of this. So, let us take the Goldbach Conjecture. Here is a program and consider the following program. Does it take a purported proof of the Goldbach Conjecture that fits in a million lines? So, we have a proof written in some kind of formal reasoning system, that is no more than a million lines. It takes that proof, and it checks, does this purported proof actually prove the Goldbach Conjecture? Right? If it does, then it outputs 1. If it does not, it outputs 0. Now, most proofs do not even parse correctly, so they will just output 0. maybe the Goldbach Conjecture is false,

or it has no proof in less than a million lines. In that case, it will always output 0. It will be, as we say, the trivial map. Nevertheless, maybe the Goldbach Conjecture is true and has a proof under a million lines, in which case this thing will not be trivial. It will sometimes output 1. So, distinguishing those cases sounds like a pretty hard problem. Right? It sounds like it would be surprising if a computer could do this, or if there was some like simple automated way of doing it in a very short amount of time. Because when we try to solve proofs, we have not really figured out a systematic way of doing it. We just use creativity. We bring in new ideas. We have never found like a foolproof way that will always tell us, is there a short proof or not? Thus, that is why the consensus is that such an algorithm does not exist, to tell, if we have a short little program, we want to tell if it is trivial or not, the consensus is that we cannot do it.

44 How to Think About Quantum Supremacy: Modern Argument of Quantum Supremacy

Let us just tell us the high-level argument. The goal of quantum supremacy is to say, here is something that a quantum computer could do that a classical computer cannot do. By cannot, we have to mean relative to some assumption. So, the kind of the more modern approach is to say, assume that approximate counting is not equivalent to exact counting. In other words, if we can do approximate counting, there is no polynomial-time reduction from exact counting to approximate counting. So, we reason about things far above MP ., But that is fine. We can still discuss them. Moreover, they sure look different. It looks like if we can do approximate counting, there is no way with polynomial overhead to make it to exact counting. If we believe that, then that implies that there is no classical simulation of quantum computing [105]. So, that is kind of the more modern approach to showing quantum supremacy. There are kind of two advantages to it. One of them is that it applies even to non-universal quantum computing [106]. So, if we have a system of non-interacting photons, they have to be single photons going through a bunch of beam splitters [107], and then we measure them that has been called, sometimes, boson sampling [108] that is not a universal architecture of quantum computing [55, 109]. However, even simulating this, it turns out, can be ruled out if we assume that approximate counting is not equal to exact counting. And then the second advantage is kind of more sociological, is that the assumption looks non-quantum. So, a lot of this started with Scott Aaronson, who had spent his time discussing to non-quantum computer scientists, who do not know what \hbar is. They are kind of fuzzy on complex numbers. They do not really believe in this whole quantum thing. Thus, when we say a quantum computer can do things that a classical computer cannot if we assume that BPP is not equal to BQP , they are not very impressed because we have just assumed that a quantum computer can do things that a classical computer cannot. So, what are we even saying here? However, if we say, assume that approximate counting is not equal to exact counting, we could say, well, we do not know about quantum mechanics. However, sure, that seems believable. And then we say, well, if we accept that, then a quantum computer can do things that the classic computer cannot, that is a more interesting statement. So, again, it comes down to the fact that complexity statements are somewhat sociological, and our belief in them depends on how plausible the assumption is and how widely it has been studied. Thus, that is why these quantum supremacy arguments are considered more plausible, and kind of the assumption is more desirable than the BPP versus BQP .

The performance of a computational task by a quantum computer that is beyond the capability of any classical computer is known as quantum supremacy. Such a demonstration would further confirm our understanding of quantum mechanics and contradict the extended Church-

Turing thesis. The Church-Turing thesis states that quantum computers can be simulated by classical computers with polynomial overhead. More practically, a demonstration of quantum supremacy would increase our confidence in the eventual success of universal quantum computers.

While it is thought that existing quantum algorithms, such as Shor's factoring algorithm and Grover's search algorithm, could eventually be used to demonstrate quantum supremacy, the number of gates required for these demonstrations is far beyond the reach of current technology. Therefore, the focus of modern quantum supremacy research is on finding restricted models of quantum computation, which are not only realizable in the near term but ones for which we also have significant complexity-theoretic evidence that the classical simulation of these models is hard. It should be emphasized that the problems solved by these restricted models are, unlike Shor's factoring algorithm or Grover's search algorithm, generally not one of practical value beyond the demonstration of quantum supremacy [110]. Currently, the leading proposals for such a demonstration are boson sampling and random quantum circuits, each of which will be described below.

Boson sampling, originally proposed by Scott Aaronson and Alex Arkhipov, is a problem related to the simulation of photons traversing a linear-optical network. The network, usually generated at random, consists of m input and output ports and $n \ll m$ photons injected into different input ports. The output ports are monitored by photon detectors, and the computational challenge is to sample the output photon distribution. This problem is of interest because the transition amplitudes of the photons in these experiments have been shown to be related to the permanent of a complex matrix, primarily used in combinatorics.

The permanent of a matrix M , with elements $m_{i,j}$, is given by

$$\text{per}(M) = \sum_{\sigma \in S_n} \prod_{i=1}^n m_{i,\sigma(i)} \quad (53)$$

Where the $\sigma \in S_n$ means that the sum is over the symmetric group of size n , in practice, this means the sum is over all permutations of a list going from 1 to n .

As an example, consider a general 3×3 matrix; the sum would then be over lists with elements given by both the even permutations (1,2,3), (2,3,1), (3,1,2), and the odd permutations (2,1,3), (1,3,2) and (3,2,1). The first sum is then given by $m_{1,1}m_{2,2}m_{3,3}$, the second sum by $m_{1,2}m_{2,3}m_{3,1}$, the third by $m_{1,3}m_{2,1}, m_{3,2}$, and so on. Finding all of these terms results in the formula, for a general 3×3 matrix given by

$$\text{per} \begin{pmatrix} a & b & c \\ d & e & f \\ g & h & i \end{pmatrix} = aei + bfg + cdh + ceg + bdi + afh.$$

This is closely related to the better-known matrix determinant which is given by

$$\det(M) = \sum_{\sigma \in S_n} \left(\text{sgn}(\sigma) \prod_{i=1}^n m_{i,\sigma(i)} \right) \quad (54)$$

Where sgn denotes the sign of the permutation. Using the same example as above, the determinant of a general 3×3 matrix becomes

$$\det \begin{pmatrix} a & b & c \\ d & e & f \\ g & h & i \end{pmatrix} = aei + bfg + cdh - ceg - bdi - afh.$$

Despite the similarities of these two definitions, the matrix permanent is thought to be significantly more difficult to compute as n increases. Understanding exactly why this is so is beyond the scope of this text unit. However, we can make the following simple argument for why we would expect this to be the case. While the above calculations follow directly from the definitions of the matrix permanent and determinant, we can also use an alternative formulation, more familiar to students of linear algebra, called Laplace’s formula. Laplace’s formula expands the calculation of the determinant along a single row or column and relies on the computation of the determinants of smaller sub-matrices.

For our matrix above, this would look like

$$\begin{pmatrix} a & b & c \\ d & e & f \\ g & h & i \end{pmatrix} = a \times \det \begin{pmatrix} e & f \\ h & i \end{pmatrix} - b \times \det \begin{pmatrix} d & f \\ g & i \end{pmatrix} + c \times \det \begin{pmatrix} d & e \\ g & h \end{pmatrix}. \quad (55)$$

An analogous formula exists for calculating the matrix permanent, but with the sign of all of the terms being positive.

The benefit of this formulation is that, since the matrix determinant is invariant to elementary row and column operations, a matrix can be reformulated such that a single row or column is mostly zeroed, significantly reducing the overall number of terms that need to be calculated. Surprisingly, the matrix permanent is not invariant to elementary row and column operations, and therefore this shortcut does not exist.

It is precisely the appearance of the matrix permanent in the calculation of detection statistics in boson sampling, which is used to estimate the computational complexity of the classical problem. Several experimental realizations of boson sampling have been achieved with nine modes and five photons. However, it is currently thought that at least 50 or more single photons would be required to reach quantum supremacy.

Random quantum circuits provide a model for quantum supremacy [111], which resides within the quantum circuit model. The most basic model referred to as Instantaneous Quantum Polynomial (IQP) circuits [112], is based on the application of gates, which all commute with one another. One way this can be realized is, to begin with, a state where every qubit is zero, such as $|00\dots0\rangle$, and applying a Hadamard gate to each qubit. This is then followed by gates, which are only diagonal, and finally, Hadamard’s are applied to each qubit one more time. Diagonal gates are required here because matrix multiplication is commutative for diagonal matrices, a fact that is easily proven.

The computational task is then to sample from the distribution of measurement outcomes for a random implementation of this circuit. Since these circuits are made up of a restricted class of gates, they are easier to implement physically and simpler to analyze theoretically than full-scale models of quantum computation [1]. Unfortunately, it is thought that this simplicity causes IQP to become classically simulable when noise is present [88, 113, 114]. A related proposal for achieving quantum supremacy is to sample the output distribution of random circuits comprised of single and two-qubit gates, which in general do not commute.

39. Relation Between Complexity Classes; According to the section, “How to think about quantum supremacy: modern argument of quantum supremacy,” which of the following are true statements about the modern concept of quantum supremacy?

- Quantum supremacy implies a classical computer cannot simulate a quantum computer under certain assumptions.

- The assumption “approximate counting does not equal exact counting” implies quantum supremacy.
- The assumption “approximate counting does not equal exact counting” is viewed as more desirable than quantum supremacy arguments surrounding BQP and BPP, because it need not invoke quantum mechanics directly.
- Quantum supremacy applies even to non-universal quantum computers.

Solution:

All of the above statements are true.

45 Mitigating Errors in a Superconducting Qubit System with Composite Pulses

In this IBM Q experience, we will apply the composite pulsing technique that we discussed during section 3. We strongly advise we to revisit the content on “Correcting Systematic Control Errors.”

In the first section, we will discuss how to implement advanced single-qubit gates, and in the second section, we will discuss how to define new gates from the built-in ones, and in particular, how to define basic rotations. In the third section, we will review the basic theory about the composite pulse $BB1(\pi)$ and will discuss how to define it in QASM [115]. Last, in the fourth section, we will compare our IBM Q measurement results from the implementation of $R_x(\pi)^{2N}$ and $BB1(\pi)^{2N}$ to decide which one is the better implementation of a rotation about the x-axis at an angle $\theta = \pi$.

Advanced Gates

QASM codes [116] that used the basic pre-defined single-qubit gates provided by the IBM Quantum Experience. We will need to go beyond these basic single-qubit gates in order to implement the composite pulse experiments.

In this first exercise, we will discuss how to use the advanced single-qubit gates that we will need for the subsequent experiments. We can gain access to these gates on the IBM Q website by clicking the “Advanced” checkbox, as shown below.

Figure 18: Advance gates

The table below shows the three pre-defined advanced single-qubit gates $U_1(\lambda)$, $U_2(\phi, \lambda)$, and $U_3(\theta, \phi, \lambda)$. Using combinations of these three gates, it is possible to implement any single-qubit rotation.

Table 4: Single-qubit gates $U_1(\lambda)$, $U_2(\phi, \lambda)$, and $U_3(\theta, \phi, \lambda)$

QASM Code	Matrix	Definition
$U_1(\lambda)$	$U_1(\lambda) = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & e^{i\lambda} \end{pmatrix}$	One-parameter single-qubit phase gate with zero duration (0-pulses).
$U_2(\phi, \lambda)$	$U_2(\phi, \lambda) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{pmatrix} 1 & -e^{i\lambda} \\ e^{i\phi} & e^{i(\phi+\lambda)} \end{pmatrix}$	Two-parameter single-qubit gate with duration one unit of time (1-pulse).
$U_3(\theta, \phi, \lambda)$	$U_3(\theta, \phi, \lambda) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{pmatrix} \cos(\theta/2) & -e^{i\lambda} \sin(\theta/2) \\ e^{i\phi} \sin(\theta/2) & e^{i(\phi+\lambda)} \cos(\theta/2) \end{pmatrix}$	Three-parameter single-qubit gate with duration 2 units of gate time (2-pulses).

Example 1:

The following QASM code applies a $U_3(\theta, \phi, \lambda)$ gate to the first qubit with $\theta = \pi$, $\phi = \arccos(1/4)$, and $\lambda = \pi/4$,

```

1 include "qelib1.inc";
2 qreg q[1];
3 creg c[1];
4 u3(pi, acos(1/4), pi/4) q[0];
5 measure q[0] -> c[0];

```

Example 2:

The following QASM code applies a $U_2(\phi, \lambda)$ gate to the first qubit with $\phi = 3 * \pi/4$, and

$$\lambda = 5 * \pi / 4,$$

```

1 qreg q[1];
2 creg c[1];
3 u2(3*pi/4, 5*pi/4) q[0];
4 measure q[0] -> c[0];

```

40. Advanced Gates; Run a QASM code that implements the following three gates in order: $U_3(\theta, \phi, \lambda)$, $U_2(\phi, \lambda)$, and $U_1(\lambda)$. Use qubit $q[0]$ and angles $\theta = \pi$, $\phi = \pi/4$, and $\lambda = \pi/4$.

```

1 include "qelib1.inc";
2
3 qreg q[1];
4 creg c[1];
5 u3(pi, pi/4, pi/4) q[0];
6 measure q[0] -> c[0];

```

Gate Definition and Rotations

To implement the following exercises, we will need to define new gates using the built-in standard and advanced gates. A gate named `name1` with parameters α , β , and γ is defined as follows:

```
gate name1( $\alpha, \beta, \gamma$ ) a
```

where `a` indicates the qubit (within the definition of the new gate) on which the gate is acting, and the body is a single gate such as $u3(\pi, \beta, \gamma)$ or a combination of gates.

Example 1: A rotation of an angle θ about the x-axis, $R_x(\theta)$, and applied to qubit `a` is defined using the advanced gate $u3(\theta, \beta, \gamma)$ by assigning the value of β to $-\pi/2$ and the value of γ to $\pi/2$.

```
gate rx( $\theta$ ) a
u3(theta, -pi/2, pi/2) a;
```

```

1 gate rx(theta) a
2 {
3     u3(theta, -pi/2, pi/2) a;
4 }

```

Example 2: The sequence of single-qubit gates XYZ is defined using the basic built-in gates X, Y and Z in the following manner:

```
gate name a
```

```

z a; // In the sequence XYZ, Z is applied
first
y a;
x a; // In the sequence XYZ, X is applied
last

```

Note that the basic built-in gates do not necessarily require arguments.

Example 3: In the code below, the gate `id5` is defined as the multiplication of five identity gates `IIIII`, and it is implemented in the first qubit, in the following manner:

```

1 include ‘‘qelib1.inc’’;
2 qreg q[1];
3 creg c[1];
4
5 gate id5 a
6 { id a; id a; id a; id a; id a;
7 }
8
9 id5 q[0];
10 measure q[0] -> c[0];

```

On the IBM Q website, the code appears as follows:

```

1 include "qelib1.inc";
2 qreg q[1];
3 creg c[1];
4
5 gate id5 a
6 { id a; id a; id a; id a; id a;
7 }
8
9 id5 q[0];
10 measure q[0] -> c[0];
11

```


Figure 19: gate `id5`

41. Gate Definition 1; Write the QASM code, which defines a gate called `mygate`. This gate implements a `Z` gate followed by an `X` gate, and it does this twice. Recall the order of these gates is read from right to left. We can represent the repeated concatenation of these gates as $(XZ)^2 = XZ XZ$. The state of a single qubit is transformed in the following manner: $|0\rangle \rightarrow (XZ)^2 |0\rangle$. Write the QASM codes that applies `mygate` to the first qubit.

```

1 include ‘‘qelib1.inc’’;
2 qreg q[1];
3 creg c[1];
4
5 gate mygate a
6 { z a; x a; z a; x a;
7 }
8

```

```

9 mygate q[0];
10 measure q[0] -> c[0];

```

42. Gate Definition 2; Write a QASM code that defines a gate `mygate2(α)` and then applies it to the first qubit with a parameter of $\alpha = \pi$. This gate comprises the product of three $U_3(\theta, \phi, \lambda)$ gates, and it transforms the state of the qubit as follows:

$$|0\rangle \rightarrow U_3\left(\pi, \alpha - \frac{\pi}{2}, \alpha + \frac{\pi}{2}\right) U_3\left(\pi, 3\alpha - \frac{\pi}{2}, -3\alpha + \frac{\pi}{2}\right) U_3\left(\pi, \alpha + \frac{\pi}{2}, \alpha - \frac{\pi}{2}\right) |0\rangle \quad (56)$$

```

1 include ‘‘qelib1.inc’’;
2 qreg q[1];
3 creg c[1];
4
5 gate mygate2(alpha) a
6 {   u3(pi, alpha + pi/2, alpha - pi/2) a;
7     u3(pi, 3*alpha - pi/2, -3*alpha + pi/2) a;
8     u3(pi, alpha - pi/2, alpha + pi/2) a;
9 }
10 mygate2(pi) q[0];
11 measure q[0] -> c[0];

```

Basic Gates

Single-qubit rotations around the x, y, and z axes are predefined as $rx(\theta)$, $ry(\theta)$, and $rz(\theta)$ in the “qelib1.inc” file included in our QASM codes; as a result, they should work in any of the exercises on this site without needing to be defined again. While these gates are not yet supported on the IBM Q website, it is possible to implement them using the formalisms described above. The table below shows the matrix form of rotations around each axis, their corresponding advance gate matrix, and the QASM code we can use if $rx(\theta)$, $ry(\theta)$, and $rz(\theta)$ are not available:

Table 5: The matrix form of rotations around each axis, their corresponding advance gate matrix, and the QASM code we can use if $rx(\theta)$, $ry(\theta)$, and $rz(\theta)$

Basic Rotation	Advance Gate Matrix	QASM Equivalent Gate
$R_x(\theta) = \begin{pmatrix} \cos \frac{\theta}{2} & -i \sin \frac{\theta}{2} \\ -i \sin \frac{\theta}{2} & \cos \frac{\theta}{2} \end{pmatrix}$	$U_3(\theta, -\frac{\pi}{2}, \frac{\pi}{2}) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{pmatrix} \cos \frac{\theta}{2} & -i \sin \frac{\theta}{2} \\ -i \sin \frac{\theta}{2} & \cos \frac{\theta}{2} \end{pmatrix}$	<code>u3(theta, -pi/2, pi/2)</code>
$R_y(\theta) = \begin{pmatrix} \cos \frac{\theta}{2} & -\sin \frac{\theta}{2} \\ \sin \frac{\theta}{2} & \cos \frac{\theta}{2} \end{pmatrix}$	$U_3(\theta, 0, 0) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{pmatrix} \cos \frac{\theta}{2} & -\sin \frac{\theta}{2} \\ \sin \frac{\theta}{2} & \cos \frac{\theta}{2} \end{pmatrix}$	<code>u3(theta, 0, 0)</code>
$R_z(\theta) = \begin{pmatrix} \exp\{-i\frac{\theta}{2}\} & 0 \\ 0 & \exp\{i\frac{\theta}{2}\} \end{pmatrix}$	$U_1(\phi) = \exp\{i\frac{\theta}{2}\} \begin{pmatrix} \exp\{-i\frac{\theta}{2}\} & 0 \\ 0 & \exp\{i\frac{\theta}{2}\} \end{pmatrix}$	<code>u1(phi)</code>

Note that there are differences between the basic rotation matrices and their corresponding advanced gate matrices, but these differences correspond to a global phase, and therefore it is valid to consider the matrices as equivalent.

43. Rotation About Y; Write a QASM code that applies a rotation of $\theta = \frac{\pi}{2}$ about the y-axis to the first qubit. we can use either the predefined $ry(\theta)$ gate or the equivalent advanced gate from the table above.

```

1 include ‘‘qelib1.inc’’;
2 qreg q[1];
3 creg c[1];
4
5 ry(pi/2) q[0]; // Alternatively: u3(pi/2,0,0) q[0];
6
7 measure q[0] -> c[0];

```

Composite Pulse $BB1(\theta)$

Introduction

As we discussed there are different types of errors that may impact a desired operation. For example, the rotation of a single-qubit state about the \hat{n} -axis at an angle θ ,

$$R_{\hat{n}}(\theta) = \exp\left(-i\frac{\theta}{2}\hat{n}\cdot\vec{\sigma}\right) \quad (57)$$

may be affected by under and over-rotation errors, such that the rotation angle is no longer θ , but is instead given by $\theta(1 + \epsilon)$, where ϵ is an unknown, but fixed, parameter,

$$R_{\hat{n}}(\theta) \rightarrow \tilde{R}_{\hat{n}}(\theta(1 + \epsilon)) = \exp\left(-i\frac{\theta(1 + \epsilon)}{2}\hat{n}\cdot\vec{\sigma}\right) \quad (58)$$

Implementing the rotation using the $BB1(\theta)$ composite pulse realizes the operation with ϵ to higher order (see reference at the end). For example, whereas the average gate fidelity of the conventional $R_x(\frac{\pi}{2})$ rotation is quadratic in ϵ for small ϵ , the net error for $BB1(\pi/2)$ goes as ϵ^6 . The $BB1(\theta)$ sequence is implemented using the product of four rotations about different axes and at different angles,

$$BB1(\theta) = \tilde{R}_{\phi}(\pi) \tilde{R}_{3\phi}(2\pi) \tilde{R}_{\phi}(\pi) \tilde{R}_x(\theta) \quad (59)$$

where

$$\tilde{R}_{\phi}(\theta) = \begin{pmatrix} \cos\frac{\theta}{2} & -ie^{-i\phi}\sin\frac{\theta}{2} \\ -ie^{i\phi}\sin\frac{\theta}{2} & \cos\frac{\theta}{2} \end{pmatrix}$$

is a rotation about the $(\cos\phi, \sin\phi, 0)$ -axis at an angle θ with $\phi = \arccos(-\theta/4\pi)$.

QASM Implementation

To write the $BB1_{\theta}$ sequence in QASM, we will need the rotations $\tilde{R}_{\phi}(\pi)$, $\tilde{R}_{3\phi}(2\pi)$ and $\tilde{R}_x(\theta)$. These three operations can be implemented using the advanced gate,

$$U_3(\theta, \phi, \lambda) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{pmatrix} \cos\frac{\theta}{2} & -e^{i\lambda}\sin\frac{\theta}{2} \\ e^{i\phi}\sin\frac{\theta}{2} & e^{i(\phi+\lambda)}\cos\frac{\theta}{2} \end{pmatrix} \quad (60)$$

A rotation of angle $\theta = \pi$ about the $(\cos\phi, \sin\phi, 0)$ -axis,

$$\tilde{R}_{\phi}(\pi) = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & -ie^{-i\arccos(-\theta/4\pi)} \\ -ie^{i\arccos(-\theta/4\pi)} & 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

can be implemented as,

$$U_3\left(\pi, \arccos(-\theta/4\pi) - \frac{\pi}{2}, -\arccos(-\theta/4\pi) + \frac{\pi}{2}\right) \quad (61)$$

A rotation of angle $\theta = 2\pi$ about the $(\cos 3\phi, \sin 3\phi, 0)$ -axis,
 $\tilde{R}_{3\phi}(2\pi) = \begin{pmatrix} \cos \pi & -ie^{-3i\phi} \sin \pi \\ -ie^{3i\phi} \sin \pi & \cos \pi \end{pmatrix}$,
can be implemented as,

$$U_3 \left(2\pi, 3 \arccos(-\theta/4\pi) - \frac{\pi}{2}, -3 \arccos(-\theta/4\pi) + \frac{\pi}{2} \right) \quad (62)$$

And, a rotation of angle θ about the x-axis
 $\tilde{R}_x(\theta) = \begin{pmatrix} \cos \frac{\theta}{2} & -i \sin \frac{\theta}{2} \\ -i \sin \frac{\theta}{2} & \cos \frac{\theta}{2} \end{pmatrix}$
can be implemented as,

$$U_3 \left(\theta, -\frac{\pi}{2}, \frac{\pi}{2} \right) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{pmatrix} \cos \frac{\theta}{2} & -i \sin \frac{\theta}{2} \\ -i \sin \frac{\theta}{2} & \cos \frac{\theta}{2} \end{pmatrix} \quad (63)$$

QASM Code For BB1

Given the gate definitions above, we might naïvely expect to define a $BB1(\theta)$ composite pulse in QASM as follows:

```

1 gate bb1($ \theta $) a {
2 // Rotation about the x-axis at an angle $ \theta $:
3 u3($ \theta $, $ -\pi/2 $, $ \pi/2 $) a;
4
5 // Rotation about the (cos(phi), (sin(phi),0)-axis at an angle $ \pi $:
6 u3($ \pi $, acos(-$ \theta $/(4*$ \pi $)) - $ \pi/2 $, -acos(-$ \theta $/(4*$ \pi $)) + $ \pi/2 $) a;
7
8 // Rotation about the (cos(3phi), (sin(3phi),0)-axis at an angle 2pi:
9 u3(2*$ \pi $, 3*acos(-theta/(4*$ \pi $)) - $ \pi/2 $, -3*acos(-$ \theta $/(4*$ \pi $)) + $ \pi/2 $) a;
10
11 //Rotation about the (cos(phi), (sin(phi),0)-axis at an angle $ \pi $:
12 u3($ \pi $, acos(-$ \theta $/(4*$ \pi $)) - $ \pi/2 $, -acos(-$ \theta $/(4*$ \pi $)) + $ \pi/2 $) a;
13 }
```

If we were to try this on the IBMQ hardware, however, we might find that it does not perform as well as expected. The reason is subtle: while U_3 can describe a rotation of an arbitrary angle θ , the actual quantum computer does not have a physical gate capable of carrying out such a rotation in one step. In fact, all gates on the IBMQ hardware are constructed from a combination of:

(a) 90-degree rotations about the x-axis of the Bloch sphere (implemented using fixed-duration microwave pulses), [117, 118] and

(b) “virtual” rotations about the z-axis (implemented in the software by changing the reference phase of subsequent pulses, effectively changing the rotation axis in the X-Y plane).

In particular, U_3 is implemented using two 90-degree x pulses and three virtual z rotations [83]:

$$U_3(\theta, \phi, \lambda) = R_z(\phi + 3\pi)R_x\left(\frac{\pi}{2}\right)R_z(\theta + \pi)R_x\left(\frac{\pi}{2}\right)R_z(\lambda)$$

While the abstraction above is fine for quantum computing (which is what QASM was designed for!), it does mean that we must be careful when our aim is to execute specific pulse

sequences like BB1. In this case, since all operations must eventually be translated to 90-degree hardware pulses, there are only two special cases of $BB1(\theta)$ which can be implemented exactly on the IBMQ hardware: $BB1(\pi)$ and $BB1_{\pi/2}$. In QASM, these are:

```

1 gate bb1pi a {
2     u3(pi, -pi/2, pi/2) a;
3     u3(pi, acos(-1/4) - pi/2, -acos(-1/4) + pi/2) a;
4     u3(pi, 3*acos(-1/4) - pi/2, -3*acos(-1/4) + pi/2) a;
5     u3(pi, 3*acos(-1/4) - pi/2, -3*acos(-1/4) + pi/2) a;
6     u3(pi, acos(-1/4) - pi/2, -acos(-1/4) + pi/2) a;
7 }\\
8 gate bb1piover2 a {
9     u2(-pi/2, pi/2) a; // Implements a single-pulse 90 degree rotation about the x-axis
10    u3(pi, acos(-1/8) - pi/2, -acos(-1/8) + pi/2) a;
11    u3(pi, 3*acos(-1/8) - pi/2, -3*acos(-1/8) + pi/2) a;
12    u3(pi, 3*acos(-1/8) - pi/2, -3*acos(-1/8) + pi/2) a;
13    u3(pi, acos(-1/8) - pi/2, -acos(-1/8) + pi/2) a;
14 }

```

Note that:

- (a) the single $U_3(2\pi, \dots)$ gate has been split into two applications of $U_3(\pi, \dots)$, each of which is implemented with two 90-degree pulses on IBMQ hardware, and
- (b) the x-rotation of $\pi/2$ is implemented using a different advanced gate U_2 , which ensures that it is implemented in hardware with a single 90-degree pulse as desired.

44. BB1 With $\theta = \pi$; Run a QASM code that implements $BB1(\theta)$ with $\theta = \pi$ using the gate definition above. Implement this sequence on the first qubit.

```

1 include "qelib1.inc";
2 gate bb1pi a {
3     u3(pi, -pi/2, pi/2) a;
4     u3(pi, acos(-1/4) - pi/2, -acos(-1/4) + pi/2) a;
5     u3(pi, 3*acos(-1/4) - pi/2, -3*acos(-1/4) + pi/2) a;
6     u3(pi, 3*acos(-1/4) - pi/2, -3*acos(-1/4) + pi/2) a;
7     u3(pi, acos(-1/4) - pi/2, -acos(-1/4) + pi/2) a;
8 }
9 qreg q[1];
10 creg c[1];
11
12 bb1pi q[0];
13 measure q[0] -> c[0];

```

45. Rotation About x-Axis With At An Angle $\theta = \pi$; Run a QASM code that implements a rotation about the x axis at an angle $\theta = \pi$ using the gate definition above. Use $U_3(\theta, \phi, \lambda)$ to implement the rotation on the first qubit.

```

1 include "qelib1.inc";
2
3 qreg q[1];

```

```

4 creg c[1];
5
6 u3(pi, -pi/2, pi/2) q[0];
7 measure q[0] -> c[0];

```

BB1(π) Versus Basic Rotation:

In this section, we will compare $BB1(\theta)$ with $R_x(\theta)$, for the case $\theta = \pi$. Ideally, $BB1(\pi)$ and $R_x(\pi)$ implement an equivalent net rotation: they both rotate the state of a qubit an angle $\theta = \pi$ about the x-axis. When they are applied to the initial state $|0\rangle$, they ideally will rotate this state to $|1\rangle$. When $BB1(\pi)$ and $R_x(\pi)$ are applied an even number of times, they ideally rotate the state $|0\rangle$ back to $|0\rangle$. In reality, when one applies $BB1(\theta)$ and $R_x(\theta)$, due to noise and systematic imperfections, the measurements results are generally not the same.

46. IBM Q Results: $2N=20, 40, 60, 80$; Below, we will find the IBM Q measurement results of $BB1(\pi)^{2N}$ and $R_x(\pi)^{2N}$ for $2N=20,40,60,80$, alongside the usual simulation results (which do not suffer from systematic rotation errors and are therefore much closer to the “ideal” outcome). Use these results to respond which one of the following statements is correct.

- The measured results from $BB1(\pi)$ are always in better agreement with the idealized simulation results than the ones from the basic rotation $R_x(\pi)$.
- The measured results from $BB1(\pi)$ are equivalent to the idealized simulation results, and in better agreement than the ones from the basic rotation $R_x(\pi)$.
- The measured results from $BB1(\pi)$ are always in worse agreement with the idealized simulation results than the ones from the basic rotation $R_x(\pi)$.

Solution:

From the two figures below, one can notice that the number of projections on the $|0\rangle$ state is always greater for $BB1(\pi)^{2N}$ than for $R_x(\pi)^{2N}$. For example, while the simulation result (blue) of $BB1(\pi)^{40}$ is 994, and 989 for $R_x(\pi)^{40}$, the actual result (orange) obtained for $BB1(\pi)^{40}$ is 786, and only 607 for $R_x(\pi)^{40}$.

The figure below shows the results from implementing $BB1(\pi)^{2N}$ for $2N=20, 40, 60, 80$. The vertical axis corresponds to the number of times the qubit was projected to state $|0\rangle$ from a total of 1024 measurements.

Figure 20: $BB1(\pi)^{2N}$ for $2N=20, 40, 60, 80$

The figure below shows the results from implementing $R_x(\pi)^{2N}$ for $2N=20, 40, 60, 80$. The vertical axis corresponds to the number of times the qubit was projected to state |0> from a total of 1024 measurements.

Figure 21: $R_x(\pi)^{2N}$ for $2N=20, 40, 60, 80$

Let us recall that the $BB1(\pi)$ sequence pulse can be defined in QASM as

```
1 gate bb1 pi a{
2
3 u3(pi, -pi/2, pi/2)a;
4 u3(pi, acos(-1/4)-pi/2, -acos(-1/4)+pi/2)a;
5 u3(pi, 3*acos(-1/4)-pi/2, -3*acos(-1/4)+pi/2)a;
6 u3(pi, 3*acos(-1/4)-pi/2, -3*acos(-1/4)+pi/2)a;
7 u3(pi, acos(-1/4)-pi/2, -acos(-1/4)+pi/2)a;
8
9 }
```

and that the rotation $R_x(\theta)$ can be defined as

```
1 gate rx(theta) a {
2
3     u3(theta,-pi/2,pi/2) a;
4 }
```

However, we do not need to define $rx(\theta)$ in the following assessments, since it was already defined in our platform.

For our convenience in the following exercises, we have defined a new command not present in standard QASM: “repeat(N)”. This command repeats the indicated gate N times and applies it to the specified qubit. For example,

```
1 repeat(5) ry(pi/2) q[0];
```

applies five (5) y-axis rotations of π to the first qubit; that is, it is equivalent to writing

```
1 ry(pi/2) q[0];
2 ry(pi/2) q[0];
3 ry(pi/2) q[0];
4 ry(pi/2) q[0];
5 ry(pi/2) q[0];
```

For some problems, we will also be able to leave the command as “repeat(N)”, with N specified elsewhere. In these cases, our entire circuit will be run numerous times with a different N value each time, and in place of a histogram, we will obtain a plot with the IBM Q measurement results for each run. For example,

```
1 repeat(N) ry(pi/16) q[0];
```

produces the following plot

Figure 22: QE Graph

47. BB1 With $\theta = \pi$ And $2N = 100$; Run a QASM code that implements $BB1(\theta)^{2N}$ with $\theta = \pi$ and $2N=100$ on the first qubit.

```

1 include "qelib1.inc";
2
3 gate bb1pi a {
4     u3(pi,-pi/2,pi/2) a;
5     u3(pi, acos(-1/4) - pi/2, -acos(-1/4) + pi/2) a;
6     u3(pi, 3*acos(-1/4) - pi/2, -3*acos(-1/4) + pi/2) a;
7     u3(pi, 3*acos(-1/4) - pi/2, -3*acos(-1/4) + pi/2) a;
8     u3(pi, acos(-1/4) - pi/2, -acos(-1/4) + pi/2) a;
9 }
10
11 qreg q[1];
12 creg c[1];
13
14 repeat(100) bb1pi q[0];
15
16 measure q -> c;

```

48. Basic x-Axis Rotation With $\theta = \pi$ And $2N = 100$; Run a QASM code that implements $R_x(\theta)^{2N}$ with $\theta = \pi$ and $2N=100$ on the first qubit. we do not need to define $rx(\theta)$ since it was already defined for this activity.

```

1 include "qelib1.inc";
2 qreg q[1];
3 creg c[1];
4
5 repeat(100) rx(pi) q[0];
6
7 measure q -> c;

```

49. BB1 With $\theta = \pi$ And $2N = 120$; Run a QASM code that implements $BB1(\theta)^{2N}$ with $\theta = \pi$ and $2N=120$ on the first qubit.

```

1 include ‘‘qelib1.inc’’;
2
3 gate bb1pi a {
4     u3(pi,-pi/2,pi/2) a;
5     u3(pi, acos(-1/4) - pi/2, -acos(-1/4) + pi/2) a;
6     u3(pi, 3*acos(-1/4) - pi/2, -3*acos(-1/4) + pi/2) a;
7     u3(pi, 3*acos(-1/4) - pi/2, -3*acos(-1/4) + pi/2) a;
8     u3(pi, acos(-1/4) - pi/2, -acos(-1/4) + pi/2) a;
9 }
10
11 qreg q[1];
12 creg c[1];
13
14 repeat(120) bb1pi q[0];
15
16 measure q -> c;

```

50. Basic x-Axis Rotation With $\theta = \pi$ And $2N = 120$; Run a QASM code that implements $R_x(\theta)^{2N}$ with $\theta = \pi$ and $2N=120$ on the first qubit. we do not need to define $rx(\theta)$ since it was already defined for this activity.

```

1 include ‘‘qelib1.inc’’;
2
3 qreg q[1];
4 creg c[1];
5
6 repeat(120) rx(pi) q[0];
7
8 measure q -> c;

```

51. IBM Q Results: $2N = 100, 120$; Consider our IBM Q results from the last four assessments above for $2N = 100, 120$. Based on the results, one of the following statements is correct.

- The measured results from $BB1(\pi)$ are always in better agreement with the idealized simulation results than the results from the basic rotation $R_x(\pi)$.
- The measured results from $BB1(\pi)$ are always in equal agreement with the idealized simulation results and are better than the results obtained from the basic rotation $R_x(\pi)$.
- The measured results from $BB1(\pi)$ are always in worse agreement with the idealized simulation results, and the results from the basic rotation $R_x(\pi)$ are in better agreement.

52. Measurement Curve For BB1; Now that we analyzed the results of $BB1(\pi)^{2N}$ and $R_x(\pi)^{2N}$ for $2N=20,40,60,80,100,120$, we should have an idea about the behavior of both operations. Use the command “repeat(N)” to write a QASM code that implements $BBB1(\pi)^{2N}$ and then outputs a plot of the number of projections on the $|0\rangle$ state versus N.

```

1 include ‘‘qelib1.inc’’;
2
3 gate bb1pi a {
4     u3(pi,-pi/2,pi/2) a;
5     u3(pi, acos(-1/4) - pi/2, -acos(-1/4) + pi/2) a;

```

```

6   u3(pi, 3*acos(-1/4) - pi/2, -3*acos(-1/4) + pi/2) a;
7   u3(pi, 3*acos(-1/4) - pi/2, -3*acos(-1/4) + pi/2) a;
8   u3(pi, acos(-1/4) - pi/2, -acos(-1/4) + pi/2) a;
9 }
10
11 qreg q[1];
12 creg c[1];
13
14 repeat(N) bb1pi q[0];
15 repeat(N) bb1pi q[0];
16
17 measure q -> c;

```

53. Measurement Curve For Basic Rotation; Use the command “repeat(N)” to write a QASM code that implements $R_x(\pi)^{2N}$ and then outputs a plot of the number of projections on the $|0\rangle$ state versus N. we do not need to define $R_X(\theta)$ since it was already defined in this activity.

```

1 include ‘‘qelib1.inc’’;
2
3 qreg q[1];
4 creg c[1];
5
6 repeat(N) rx(pi) q[0];
7 repeat(N) rx(pi) q[0];
8
9 measure q -> c;

```

The actual results we obtain above will vary depending on day-to-day changes in IBM Q calibration and performance. For reference, here are results we obtained recently using the ibmqx4 computer [119]; these were run using 8192 shots each to better illustrate the behavior. The results from $BB1(\pi)^{2N}$ and $R_x(\pi)^{2N}$ were overlaid on the same plot:

Figure 23: $BB1(\pi)^{2N}$ and $R_x(\pi)^{2N}$

Note that we expect an overall decay due to decoherence, which is not corrected by this composite pulse sequence. However, we also see that $R_x(\pi)^{2N}$ exhibits oscillations; this due to accumulated systematic rotation errors. In contrast, $BB1(\pi)^{2N}$ corrects for these systematic rotation errors and, thus, performs much better in general (no oscillations). While R_x seemingly outperforms BB1 for values between $N=65$ and $N=95$, this is only an artifact related to it having accumulated an entire revolution's worth of rotation errors and has happened to start landing closer to the correct value as a result.

54. Phase-Flip Code; The figure below shows the quantum circuit for implementation of the phase-flip quantum error correction code.

Figure 24: Phase-Flip Code

Which of the following statements is correct?

- The circuit creates identical copies of the state of the first qubit on the second qubit and the third qubits.
- The circuit can correct three simultaneous σ_Z errors.
- The circuit to the left of the error box encodes a physical qubit onto a logical qubit.
- The circuit can correct errors of the type σ_Z without measuring the ancillary qubits.

55. Shor Nine-Qubit Code; Which of the following statements about the Shor nine-qubit error correction code is correct?

- The code requires six ancilla qubits.
- The code can only correct errors of the type σ_X
- The code cannot correct for σ_Y errors.
- The code is constructed from a combination of the bit-flip and phase-flip error-correction codes.

56. Single Point of Failure; Which of the following sentences is correct about a “single point of failure”?

- It is a part of the circuit that, when a failure occurs, causes the entire process to fail.
- It is possible to create a fault-tolerant procedure with a single point of failure.
- All circuits that have no single points of failure are, by definition, fault-tolerant.
- They can only occur on quantum circuits.

57. Fault-Tolerant Procedure; A procedure is fault-tolerant if:

- When errors occur, the procedure prevents these errors from propagating through the calculation.
- A failure causes at most one error in each encoded block of bits.
- There is at most one fault path in which two gates can fail.
- When a failure occurs, it cascades into more errors as the calculation continues.

58. Dynamical Error Suppression; In order to have a reliable quantum computer, we need to minimize systematic errors from the environment or from imperfect gate operations. Which one of the following is a platform-independent experimental procedure that reduces these types of errors?

- Replacing a single-qubit gate with an iteration of the same gate always reduces the intrinsic gate error.
- Making redundant copies of a qubit always reduces the intrinsic gate error.
- A sequence of pulses applied to a system can be designed to have a net effect that reduces the effect of environmental noise.
- Adding more ancilla qubits always reduces the effect of environmental noise.

59. Surface Codes; Which one of the following sentences does not describe the error correction code called the surface code?

- Surface codes can be implemented using a two-dimensional lattice of qubits.
- In the surface code, one only needs to entangle nearest-neighbor qubits to create a logical qubit.
- In the surface code, some qubits are used as data qubits, and some are used as syndrome qubits.
- Surface codes can have an arbitrary large fault-tolerant threshold, allowing computation with arbitrarily large errors.

60. Complexity Theory and Classes; Which of the following statements about complexity theory is correct?

- The time required to solve a polynomial-time problem of input size n grows as k^n , where k is a positive constant that is problem-dependent.
- Problems that are nondeterministic polynomial time (NP) are a subset of polynomial time.
- The complexity class of a problem can generally be related to the input size of the problem, and the number of resources required to solve it.
- All exponential-time problems can be reduced to polynomial-time problems with clever engineering.

61. Complexity Classes for Quantum and Classical Computers; The quantum complexity class BQP (bounded quantum polynomial) includes the entirety of which of the following classical complexity classes?

- PSPACE
- NP-complete
- NP (nondeterministic polynomial time)
- P (polynomial time)

References

- [1] M. A. Nielsen and I. L. Chuang, *Quantum Computation and Quantum Information: 10th Anniversary Edition*, 10th ed. USA: Cambridge University Press, 2011.
- [2] I. Chuang, “Quantum Information Science II MIT EECS 6.443J / Physics 8.371J / 18.409,” 2014. [Online]. Available: <http://cua.scripts.mit.edu/8.371/S2014/index.php>
- [3] J. Preskill, “Quantum Computation Physics 219/Computer Science 219 (Formerly Physics 229),” 2019. [Online]. Available: <http://www.theory.caltech.edu/~preskill/ph219/index.html>
- [4] U. Vazirani, “Quantum Computation CS294-2,” 1997. [Online]. Available: <https://people.eecs.berkeley.edu/~vazirani/qc.html>
- [5] J. Watrous, “Theory of Quantum Information John Watrous’s Lecture Notes,” 2011. [Online]. Available: <https://cs.uwaterloo.ca/~watrous/LectureNotes.html>
- [6] U. Vazirani, “Quantum Computation CS294-2,” 2007. [Online]. Available: <https://people.eecs.berkeley.edu/~vazirani/quantum.html>
- [7] S. Aaronson, “Quantum Computing Since Democritus PHYS771,” 2006. [Online]. Available: <https://www.scottaaronson.com/democritus/>
- [8] P. W. Shor, “Quantum Computation,” 2003, library Catalog: ocw.mit.edu. [Online]. Available: <https://ocw.mit.edu/courses/mathematics/18-435j-quantum-computation-fall-2003/>
- [9] I. Chuang and P. Shor, “Quantum Information Science,” 2006, library Catalog: ocw.mit.edu. [Online]. Available: <https://ocw.mit.edu/courses/media-arts-and-sciences/mas-865j-quantum-information-science-spring-2006/>
- [10] S. Aaronson, “Quantum Complexity Theory,” 2010, library Catalog: ocw.mit.edu. [Online]. Available: <https://ocw.mit.edu/courses/electrical-engineering-and-computer-science/6-845-quantum-complexity-theory-fall-2010/>
- [11] A. W. Harrow, “Quantum Information Science 6.443/8.371/18.436,” 2018. [Online]. Available: <https://web.mit.edu/8.371/www/index.html>
- [12] A. Childs, “Quantum algorithms CO 781,” 2008. [Online]. Available: <http://www.math.uwaterloo.ca/~amchilds/teaching/w08/co781.html>
- [13] R. Cleve, “Introduction to Quantum Information Processing CS 667, C&O 681, PHYS 767,” 2007. [Online]. Available: <https://cs.uwaterloo.ca/~cleve/courses/F07CS667/index.html>
- [14] I. D. Kivlichan, C. Gidney, D. W. Berry, N. Wiebe, J. McClean, W. Sun, Z. Jiang, N. Rubin, A. Fowler, A. Aspuru-Guzik, H. Neven, and R. Babbush, “Improved Fault-Tolerant Quantum Simulation of Condensed-Phase Correlated Electrons via Trotterization,” *arXiv:1902.10673 [physics, physics:quant-ph]*, Aug. 2019. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/1902.10673>
- [15] E. Pednault, J. A. Gunnels, G. Nannicini, L. Horesh, T. Magerlein, E. Solomonik, E. W. Draeger, E. T. Holland, and R. Wisnieff, “Breaking the 49-Qubit Barrier in the Simulation of Quantum Circuits,” *arXiv:1710.05867 [quant-ph]*, Dec. 2018. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/1710.05867>

- [16] S. Endo, Q. Zhao, Y. Li, S. Benjamin, and X. Yuan, “Mitigating algorithmic errors in Hamiltonian simulation,” *Physical Review A*, vol. 99, no. 1, p. 012334, Jan. 2019. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/1808.03623>
- [17] S. Endo, S. C. Benjamin, and Y. Li, “Practical Quantum Error Mitigation for Near-Future Applications,” *Physical Review X*, vol. 8, no. 3, p. 031027, Jul. 2018. [Online]. Available: <https://link.aps.org/doi/10.1103/PhysRevX.8.031027>
- [18] A. Kandala, K. Temme, A. D. Córcoles, A. Mezzacapo, J. M. Chow, and J. M. Gambetta, “Error mitigation extends the computational reach of a noisy quantum processor,” *Nature*, vol. 567, no. 7749, pp. 491–495, Mar. 2019. [Online]. Available: <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41586-019-1040-7>
- [19] A. Y. Kitaev, A. Shen, M. N. Vyalyi, and M. N. Vyalyi, *Classical and Quantum Computation*. American Mathematical Society, 2002.
- [20] A. W. Harrow and A. Montanaro, “Quantum computational supremacy,” *Nature*, vol. 549, no. 7671, pp. 203–209, Sep. 2017. [Online]. Available: <https://www.nature.com/articles/nature23458>
- [21] S. Boixo, S. V. Isakov, V. N. Smelyanskiy, R. Babbush, N. Ding, Z. Jiang, M. J. Bremner, J. M. Martinis, and H. Neven, “Characterizing Quantum Supremacy in Near-Term Devices,” *Nature Physics*, vol. 14, no. 6, pp. 595–600, Jun. 2018. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/1608.00263>
- [22] M. Sisodia, A. Shukla, A. A. A. de Almeida, G. W. Dueck, and A. Pathak, “Circuit optimization for IBM processors: A way to get higher fidelity and higher values of nonclassicality witnesses,” *arXiv:1812.11602 [quant-ph]*, Dec. 2018. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/1812.11602>
- [23] C. L. Edmunds, C. Hempel, R. Harris, H. Ball, V. Frey, T. M. Stace, and M. J. Biercuk, “Measuring and Suppressing Error Correlations in Quantum Circuits,” *arXiv:1712.04954 [quant-ph]*, Dec. 2017. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/1712.04954>
- [24] K. Setia, S. Bravyi, A. Mezzacapo, and J. D. Whitfield, “Superfast encodings for fermionic quantum simulation,” *Physical Review Research*, vol. 1, no. 3, p. 033033, Oct. 2019. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/1810.05274>
- [25] C. C. McGeoch, “Principles and Guidelines for Quantum Performance Analysis,” in *Quantum Technology and Optimization Problems*, ser. Lecture Notes in Computer Science, S. Feld and C. Linnhoff-Popien, Eds. Cham: Springer International Publishing, 2019, pp. 36–48.
- [26] C. C. McGeoch, R. Harris, S. P. Reinhardt, and P. I. Bunyk, “Practical Annealing-Based Quantum Computing,” *Computer*, vol. 52, no. 6, pp. 38–46, Jun. 2019.
- [27] J. J. Wallman and J. Emerson, “Noise tailoring for scalable quantum computation via randomized compiling,” *Physical Review A*, vol. 94, no. 5, p. 052325, Nov. 2016. [Online]. Available: <https://link.aps.org/doi/10.1103/PhysRevA.94.052325>
- [28] M. Laforest, *the mathematics of quantum mechanics*. [Online]. Available: https://uwaterloo.ca/institute-for-quantum-computing/sites/ca.institute-for-quantum-computing/files/uploads/files/mathematics_qm_v21.pdf

- [29] D. Litinski, “A Game of Surface Codes: Large-Scale Quantum Computing with Lattice Surgery,” *Quantum*, vol. 3, p. 128, Mar. 2019. [Online]. Available: <https://quantum-journal.org/papers/q-2019-03-05-128/>
- [30] E. Farhi, J. Goldstone, S. Gutmann, and M. Sipser, “A Limit on the Speed of Quantum Computation in Determining Parity,” *Physical Review Letters*, vol. 81, no. 24, pp. 5442–5444, Dec. 1998. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/quant-ph/9802045>
- [31] D. Gottesman, “Stabilizer Codes and Quantum Error Correction,” *arXiv:quant-ph/9705052*, May 1997. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/quant-ph/9705052>
- [32] R. Orus, “A Practical Introduction to Tensor Networks: Matrix Product States and Projected Entangled Pair States,” *Annals of Physics*, vol. 349, pp. 117–158, Oct. 2014. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/1306.2164>
- [33] N. D. Mermin, *Quantum Computer Science: An Introduction*, Aug. 2007. [Online]. Available: [/core/books/quantum-computer-science/66462590D10C8010017CF1D7C45708D7](https://core/books/quantum-computer-science/66462590D10C8010017CF1D7C45708D7)
- [34] E. National Academies of Sciences, *Quantum Computing: Progress and Prospects*, Dec. 2018. [Online]. Available: <https://www.nap.edu/catalog/25196/quantum-computing-progress-and-prospects>
- [35] E. Kapit, “A Very Small Logical Qubit,” *Physical Review Letters*, vol. 116, no. 15, p. 150501, Apr. 2016. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/1510.06117>
- [36] P. A. M. Dirac and R. H. Fowler, “The fundamental equations of quantum mechanics,” *Proceedings of the Royal Society of London. Series A, Containing Papers of a Mathematical and Physical Character*, vol. 109, no. 752, pp. 642–653, Dec. 1925. [Online]. Available: <https://royalsocietypublishing.org/doi/abs/10.1098/rspa.1925.0150>
- [37] P. a. M. Dirac, “On Quantum Algebra,” *Mathematical Proceedings of the Cambridge Philosophical Society*, vol. 23, no. 4, pp. 412–418, Oct. 1926. [Online]. Available: <https://www.cambridge.org/core/journals/mathematical-proceedings-of-the-cambridge-philosophical-society/article/on-quantum-algebra/EDEC0A7C8B907C6720C0AAF51BBF68A5>
- [38] P. A. M. Dirac, “THE MATHEMATICAL FOUNDATIONS OF QUANTUM THEORY,” in *Mathematical Foundations of Quantum Theory*, A. R. Marlow, Ed. Academic Press, Jan. 1978, pp. 1–8. [Online]. Available: <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/B9780124732506500054>
- [39] P. a. M. Dirac, “The basis of statistical quantum mechanics,” *Mathematical Proceedings of the Cambridge Philosophical Society*, vol. 25, no. 1, pp. 62–66, Jan. 1929. [Online]. Available: <https://www.cambridge.org/core/journals/mathematical-proceedings-of-the-cambridge-philosophical-society/article/basis-of-statistical-quantum-mechanics/91CE79926CED070AE10A45EF224CC2BB>
- [40] P. A. M. Dirac and R. H. Fowler, “Quantum mechanics of many-electron systems,” *Proceedings of the Royal Society of London. Series A, Containing Papers of a Mathematical and Physical Character*, vol. 123, no. 792, pp. 714–733, Apr. 1929. [Online]. Available: <https://royalsocietypublishing.org/doi/abs/10.1098/rspa.1929.0094>

- [41] —, “On the theory of quantum mechanics,” *Proceedings of the Royal Society of London. Series A, Containing Papers of a Mathematical and Physical Character*, vol. 112, no. 762, pp. 661–677, Oct. 1926. [Online]. Available: <https://royalsocietypublishing.org/doi/abs/10.1098/rspa.1926.0133>
- [42] J. Chen, J. B. Altepeter, M. Medic, K. F. Lee, B. Gokden, R. H. Hadfield, S. W. Nam, and P. Kumar, “Demonstration of a Quantum Controlled-NOT Gate in the Telecommunications Band,” *Physical Review Letters*, vol. 100, no. 13, p. 133603, Apr. 2008. [Online]. Available: <https://link.aps.org/doi/10.1103/PhysRevLett.100.133603>
- [43] E. F. Dumitrescu, A. J. McCaskey, G. Hagen, G. R. Jansen, T. D. Morris, T. Papenbrock, R. C. Pooser, D. J. Dean, and P. Lougovski, “Cloud Quantum Computing of an Atomic Nucleus,” *Physical Review Letters*, vol. 120, no. 21, p. 210501, May 2018. [Online]. Available: <https://link.aps.org/doi/10.1103/PhysRevLett.120.210501>
- [44] J. R. McClean, K. J. Sung, I. D. Kivlichan, Y. Cao, C. Dai, E. S. Fried, C. Gidney, B. Gimby, P. Gokhale, T. Häner, T. Hardikar, V. Havlíček, O. Higgott, C. Huang, J. Izaac, Z. Jiang, X. Liu, S. McArdle, M. Neeley, T. O’Brien, B. O’Gorman, I. Ozfidan, M. D. Radin, J. Romero, N. Rubin, N. P. D. Sawaya, K. Setia, S. Sim, D. S. Steiger, M. Steudtner, Q. Sun, W. Sun, D. Wang, F. Zhang, and R. Babbush, “OpenFermion: The Electronic Structure Package for Quantum Computers,” *arXiv:1710.07629 [physics, physics:quant-ph]*, Feb. 2019. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/1710.07629>
- [45] J. M. Chow, J. M. Gambetta, E. Magesan, D. W. Abraham, A. W. Cross, B. R. Johnson, N. A. Masluk, C. A. Ryan, J. A. Smolin, S. J. Srinivasan, and M. Steffen, “Implementing a strand of a scalable fault-tolerant quantum computing fabric,” *Nature Communications*, vol. 5, no. 1, p. 4015, Jun. 2014. [Online]. Available: <https://www.nature.com/articles/ncomms5015>
- [46] A. D. Córcoles, E. Magesan, S. J. Srinivasan, A. W. Cross, M. Steffen, J. M. Gambetta, and J. M. Chow, “Demonstration of a quantum error detection code using a square lattice of four superconducting qubits,” *Nature Communications*, vol. 6, no. 1, p. 6979, Apr. 2015. [Online]. Available: <https://www.nature.com/articles/ncomms7979>
- [47] J. I. Colless, V. V. Ramasesh, D. Dahlen, M. S. Blok, M. E. Kimchi-Schwartz, J. R. McClean, J. Carter, W. A. de Jong, and I. Siddiqi, “Computation of Molecular Spectra on a Quantum Processor with an Error-Resilient Algorithm,” *Physical Review X*, vol. 8, no. 1, p. 011021, Feb. 2018. [Online]. Available: <https://link.aps.org/doi/10.1103/PhysRevX.8.011021>
- [48] M. Langione, *Where Will Quantum Computers Create Value—and When?* [Online]. Available: <https://www.bcg.com/publications/2019/quantum-computers-create-value-when.aspx>
- [49] S. E. Smart, D. I. Schuster, and D. A. Mazziotti, “Experimental data from a quantum computer verifies the generalized Pauli exclusion principle,” *Communications Physics*, vol. 2, no. 1, pp. 1–6, Jan. 2019. [Online]. Available: <https://www.nature.com/articles/s42005-019-0110-3>
- [50] J. Rué and S. Xambó, *MATHEMATICAL ESSENTIALS OF QUANTUM COMPUTING*. [Online]. Available: <https://mat-web.upc.edu/people/sebastia.xambo/QC/qc.pdf>

- [51] H. Goto, “Universal quantum computation with a nonlinear oscillator network,” *Physical Review A*, vol. 93, no. 5, p. 050301, May 2016. [Online]. Available: <https://link.aps.org/doi/10.1103/PhysRevA.93.050301>
- [52] S. A. Podoshvedov, “Efficient Quantum Teleportation of Unknown Qubit Based on DV-CV Interaction Mechanism,” *Entropy*, vol. 21, no. 2, p. 150, Feb. 2019. [Online]. Available: <https://www.mdpi.com/1099-4300/21/2/150>
- [53] A. M. Steane, “Error Correcting Codes in Quantum Theory,” *Physical Review Letters*, vol. 77, no. 5, pp. 793–797, Jul. 1996, publisher: American Physical Society. [Online]. Available: <https://link.aps.org/doi/10.1103/PhysRevLett.77.793>
- [54] P. W. Shor, “Polynomial-Time Algorithms for Prime Factorization and Discrete Logarithms on a Quantum Computer,” *SIAM Journal on Computing*, vol. 26, no. 5, pp. 1484–1509, Oct. 1997. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/quant-ph/9508027>
- [55] R. S. Smith, M. J. Curtis, and W. J. Zeng, “A Practical Quantum Instruction Set Architecture,” *arXiv:1608.03355 [quant-ph]*, Feb. 2017. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/1608.03355>
- [56] F. de Ridder, N. Neumann, T. Veugen, and R. Kooij, “A Quantum Algorithm for Minimising the Effective Graph Resistance upon Edge Addition,” in *Quantum Technology and Optimization Problems*, ser. Lecture Notes in Computer Science, S. Feld and C. Linnhoff-Popien, Eds. Cham: Springer International Publishing, 2019, pp. 63–73.
- [57] J. C. Bardin, E. Jeffrey, E. Lucero, T. Huang, O. Naaman, R. Barends, T. White, M. Giustina, D. Sank, P. Roushan, K. Arya, B. Chiaro, J. Kelly, J. Chen, B. Burkett, Y. Chen, A. Dunsworth, A. Fowler, B. Foxen, C. Gidney, R. Graff, P. Klimov, J. Mutus, M. McEwen, A. Megrant, M. Neeley, C. Neill, C. Quintana, A. Vainsencher, H. Neven, and J. Martinis, “A 28nm Bulk-CMOS 4-to-8GHz ~ 2 mW Cryogenic Pulse Modulator for Scalable Quantum Computing,” *2019 IEEE International Solid-State Circuits Conference - (ISSCC)*, pp. 456–458, Feb. 2019. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/1902.10864>
- [58] S. Bravyi, J. M. Gambetta, A. Mezzacapo, and K. Temme, “Tapering off qubits to simulate fermionic Hamiltonians,” *arXiv:1701.08213 [quant-ph]*, Jan. 2017. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/1701.08213>
- [59] T. P. Harty, D. T. C. Allcock, C. J. Ballance, L. Guidoni, H. A. Janacek, N. M. Linke, D. N. Stacey, and D. M. Lucas, “High-Fidelity Preparation, Gates, Memory, and Readout of a Trapped-Ion Quantum Bit,” *Physical Review Letters*, vol. 113, no. 22, p. 220501, Nov. 2014. [Online]. Available: <https://link.aps.org/doi/10.1103/PhysRevLett.113.220501>
- [60] C. J. Ballance, T. P. Harty, N. M. Linke, M. A. Sepiol, and D. M. Lucas, “High-Fidelity Quantum Logic Gates Using Trapped-Ion Hyperfine Qubits,” *Physical Review Letters*, vol. 117, no. 6, p. 060504, Aug. 2016. [Online]. Available: <https://link.aps.org/doi/10.1103/PhysRevLett.117.060504>
- [61] Y. Wang, S. Crain, C. Fang, B. Zhang, S. Huang, Q. Liang, P. H. Leung, K. R. Brown, and J. Kim, “High-fidelity Two-qubit Gates Using a MEMS-based Beam Steering System for Individual Qubit Addressing,” *arXiv:2003.12430 [physics, physics:quant-ph]*, Apr. 2020. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/2003.12430>

- [62] J. P. Gaebler, T. R. Tan, Y. Lin, Y. Wan, R. Bowler, A. C. Keith, S. Glancy, K. Coakley, E. Knill, D. Leibfried, and D. J. Wineland, “High-Fidelity Universal Gate Set for ${}^9\text{Be}^+$ Ion Qubits,” *Physical Review Letters*, vol. 117, no. 6, p. 060505, Aug. 2016. [Online]. Available: <https://link.aps.org/doi/10.1103/PhysRevLett.117.060505>
- [63] P. V. Klimov, J. Kelly, Z. Chen, M. Neeley, A. Megrant, B. Burkett, R. Barends, K. Arya, B. Chiaro, Y. Chen, A. Dunsworth, A. Fowler, B. Foxen, C. Gidney, M. Giustina, R. Graff, T. Huang, E. Jeffrey, E. Lucero, J. Y. Mutus, O. Naaman, C. Neill, C. Quintana, P. Roushan, D. Sank, A. Vainsencher, J. Wenner, T. C. White, S. Boixo, R. Babbush, V. N. Smelyanskiy, H. Neven, and J. M. Martinis, “Fluctuations of Energy-Relaxation Times in Superconducting Qubits,” *Physical Review Letters*, vol. 121, no. 9, p. 090502, Aug. 2018. [Online]. Available: <https://link.aps.org/doi/10.1103/PhysRevLett.121.090502>
- [64] H. K. Xu, C. Song, W. Y. Liu, G. M. Xue, F. F. Su, H. Deng, Y. Tian, D. N. Zheng, S. Han, Y. P. Zhong, H. Wang, Y.-x. Liu, and S. P. Zhao, “Coherent population transfer between uncoupled or weakly coupled states in ladder-type superconducting qubits,” *Nature Communications*, vol. 7, no. 1, pp. 1–6, Mar. 2016. [Online]. Available: <https://www.nature.com/articles/ncomms11018>
- [65] B. Abdo, N. T. Bronn, O. Jinka, S. Olivadese, A. D. Corcoles, V. P. Adiga, M. Brink, R. E. Lake, X. Wu, D. P. Pappas, and J. M. Chow, “Active protection of a superconducting qubit with an interferometric Josephson isolator,” *Nature Communications*, vol. 10, no. 1, p. 3154, Dec. 2019. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/1810.07234>
- [66] N. Bergeal, R. Vijay, V. E. Manucharyan, I. Siddiqi, R. J. Schoelkopf, S. M. Girvin, and M. H. Devoret, “Analog information processing at the quantum limit with a Josephson ring modulator,” *Nature Physics*, vol. 6, no. 4, pp. 296–302, Apr. 2010. [Online]. Available: <https://www.nature.com/articles/nphys1516>
- [67] B. Abdo, F. Schackert, M. Hatridge, C. Rigetti, and M. Devoret, “Josephson amplifier for qubit readout,” *Applied Physics Letters*, vol. 99, no. 16, p. 162506, Oct. 2011. [Online]. Available: <https://aip.scitation.org/doi/10.1063/1.3653473>
- [68] F. Yan, S. Gustavsson, A. Kamal, J. Birenbaum, A. P. Sears, D. Hover, T. J. Gudmundsen, D. Rosenberg, G. Samach, S. Weber, J. L. Yoder, T. P. Orlando, J. Clarke, A. J. Kerman, and W. D. Oliver, “The flux qubit revisited to enhance coherence and reproducibility,” *Nature Communications*, vol. 7, no. 1, pp. 1–9, Nov. 2016. [Online]. Available: <https://www.nature.com/articles/ncomms12964>
- [69] J. M. Gambetta, J. M. Chow, and M. Steffen, “Building logical qubits in a superconducting quantum computing system,” *npj Quantum Information*, vol. 3, no. 1, pp. 1–7, Jan. 2017. [Online]. Available: <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41534-016-0004-0>
- [70] N. C. Jones, R. Van Meter, A. G. Fowler, P. L. McMahon, J. Kim, T. D. Ladd, and Y. Yamamoto, “Layered Architecture for Quantum Computing,” *Physical Review X*, vol. 2, no. 3, p. 031007, Jul. 2012. [Online]. Available: <https://link.aps.org/doi/10.1103/PhysRevX.2.031007>
- [71] F. Motzoi, J. M. Gambetta, P. Rebentrost, and F. K. Wilhelm, “Simple Pulses for Elimination of Leakage in Weakly Nonlinear Qubits,” *Physical Review Letters*, vol. 103, no. 11, p. 110501, Sep. 2009. [Online]. Available: <https://link.aps.org/doi/10.1103/PhysRevLett.103.110501>

- [72] C. Müller, J. Lisenfeld, A. Shnirman, and S. Poletto, “Interacting two-level defects as sources of fluctuating high-frequency noise in superconducting circuits,” *Physical Review B*, vol. 92, no. 3, p. 035442, Jul. 2015. [Online]. Available: <https://link.aps.org/doi/10.1103/PhysRevB.92.035442>
- [73] M. Reiher, N. Wiebe, K. M. Svore, D. Wecker, and M. Troyer, “Elucidating reaction mechanisms on quantum computers,” *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, vol. 114, no. 29, pp. 7555–7560, Jul. 2017. [Online]. Available: <https://www.pnas.org/content/114/29/7555>
- [74] C. Hempel, C. Maier, J. Romero, J. McClean, T. Monz, H. Shen, P. Jurcevic, B. Lanyon, P. Love, R. Babbush, A. Aspuru-Guzik, R. Blatt, and C. Roos, “Quantum chemistry calculations on a trapped-ion quantum simulator,” *Physical Review X*, vol. 8, no. 3, p. 031022, Jul. 2018. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/1803.10238>
- [75] L. Bassman, K. Liu, A. Krishnamoorthy, T. Linker, Y. Geng, D. Shebib, S. Fukushima, F. Shimojo, R. K. Kalia, A. Nakano, and P. Vashishta, “Towards simulation of the dynamics of materials on quantum computers,” *Physical Review B*, vol. 101, no. 18, p. 184305, May 2020. [Online]. Available: <https://link.aps.org/doi/10.1103/PhysRevB.101.184305>
- [76] M. Pains and A. Kaley, “An approximate description of quantum states,” *arXiv:1910.10543 [quant-ph]*, Nov. 2019. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/1910.10543>
- [77] J. Chen, L. Wang, and B. Wang, “Quantum FPGA architecture design,” in *2013 International Conference on Field-Programmable Technology (FPT)*, Dec. 2013, pp. 354–357.
- [78] M. Motta, E. Ye, J. R. McClean, Z. Li, A. J. Minnich, R. Babbush, and G. K.-L. Chan, “Low rank representations for quantum simulation of electronic structure,” *arXiv:1808.02625 [physics, physics:quant-ph]*, Aug. 2018. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/1808.02625>
- [79] R. Babbush, N. Wiebe, J. McClean, J. McClain, H. Neven, and G. K.-L. Chan, “Low-Depth Quantum Simulation of Materials,” *Physical Review X*, vol. 8, no. 1, p. 011044, Mar. 2018. [Online]. Available: <https://link.aps.org/doi/10.1103/PhysRevX.8.011044>
- [80] A. J. McCaskey, Z. P. Parks, J. Jakowski, S. V. Moore, T. Morris, T. S. Humble, and R. C. Pooser, “Quantum Chemistry as a Benchmark for Near-Term Quantum Computers,” *arXiv:1905.01534 [physics, physics:quant-ph]*, May 2019. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/1905.01534>
- [81] B. P. Lanyon, J. D. Whitfield, G. G. Gillett, M. E. Goggin, M. P. Almeida, I. Kassal, J. D. Biamonte, M. Mohseni, B. J. Powell, M. Barbieri, A. Aspuru-Guzik, and A. G. White, “Towards quantum chemistry on a quantum computer,” *Nature Chemistry*, vol. 2, no. 2, pp. 106–111, Feb. 2010. [Online]. Available: <https://www.nature.com/articles/nchem.483>
- [82] Y. Li and S. C. Benjamin, “Efficient Variational Quantum Simulator Incorporating Active Error Minimization,” *Physical Review X*, vol. 7, no. 2, p. 021050, Jun. 2017. [Online]. Available: <https://link.aps.org/doi/10.1103/PhysRevX.7.021050>
- [83] R. LaRose, “Overview and Comparison of Gate Level Quantum Software Platforms,” *Quantum*, vol. 3, p. 130, Mar. 2019. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/1807.02500>

- [84] M. DeLahaye and C. Lacroûte, “Single-ion, transportable optical atomic clocks,” *Journal of Modern Optics*, vol. 65, no. 5-6, pp. 622–639, Mar. 2018. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/1804.02168>
- [85] N. Huntemann, C. Sanner, B. Lipphardt, C. Tamm, and E. Peik, “Single-ion atomic clock with 3×10^{-18} systematic uncertainty,” *Physical Review Letters*, vol. 116, no. 6, p. 063001, Feb. 2016. [Online]. Available: <https://link.aps.org/doi/10.1103/PhysRevLett.116.063001>
- [86] E. Bernstein and U. Vazirani, “Quantum complexity theory,” in *in Proc. 25th Annual ACM Symposium on Theory of Computing, ACM*, 1993, pp. 11–20.
- [87] J. D. Franson and R. A. Brewster, “Limitations on the use of the Heisenberg picture,” *arXiv:1811.06517 [quant-ph]*, Dec. 2018. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/1811.06517>
- [88] M. J. Bremner, R. Jozsa, and D. J. Shepherd, “Classical simulation of commuting quantum computations implies collapse of the polynomial hierarchy,” *Proceedings of the Royal Society A: Mathematical, Physical and Engineering Sciences*, vol. 467, no. 2126, pp. 459–472, Feb. 2011. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/1005.1407>
- [89] S. Aaronson and A. Arkhipov, “The Computational Complexity of Linear Optics,” *arXiv:1011.3245 [quant-ph]*, Nov. 2010. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/1011.3245>
- [90] R. Orús, “Tensor networks for complex quantum systems,” *Nature Reviews Physics*, vol. 1, no. 9, pp. 538–550, Sep. 2019. [Online]. Available: <https://www.nature.com/articles/s42254-019-0086-7>
- [91] J. A. Smolin, G. Smith, and A. Vargo, “Pretending to factor large numbers on a quantum computer,” *Nature*, vol. 499, no. 7457, pp. 163–165, Jul. 2013. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/1301.7007>
- [92] A. Botea, A. Kishimoto, and R. Marinescu, “On the Complexity of Quantum Circuit Compilation,” in *Eleventh Annual Symposium on Combinatorial Search*, Jul. 2018. [Online]. Available: <https://aaai.org/ocs/index.php/SOCS/SOCS18/paper/view/17959>
- [93] A. Lucas, “Ising formulations of many NP problems,” *Frontiers in Physics*, vol. 2, 2014. [Online]. Available: <https://www.readcube.com/articles/10.3389%2Ffphy.2014.00005>
- [94] S. Aaronson, “BQP and the Polynomial Hierarchy,” *arXiv:0910.4698 [quant-ph]*, Oct. 2009. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/0910.4698>
- [95] S. Aaronson and A. Ambainis, “Forrelation: A Problem that Optimally Separates Quantum from Classical Computing,” *arXiv:1411.5729 [quant-ph]*, Nov. 2014. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/1411.5729>
- [96] R. Raz and A. Tal, “Oracle separation of BQP and PH,” in *Proceedings of the 51st Annual ACM SIGACT Symposium on Theory of Computing*, ser. STOC 2019. Phoenix, AZ, USA: Association for Computing Machinery, Jun. 2019, pp. 13–23. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1145/3313276.3316315>
- [97] B. M. Terhal and D. P. DiVincenzo, “Adaptive Quantum Computation, Constant Depth Quantum Circuits and Arthur-Merlin Games,” *arXiv:quant-ph/0205133*, Mar. 2004. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/quant-ph/0205133>

- [98] T. Vyskočil, S. Pakin, and H. N. Djidjev, “Embedding Inequality Constraints for Quantum Annealing Optimization,” in *Quantum Technology and Optimization Problems*, ser. Lecture Notes in Computer Science, S. Feld and C. Linnhoff-Popien, Eds. Cham: Springer International Publishing, 2019, pp. 11–22.
- [99] L. K. Grover, “A fast quantum mechanical algorithm for database search,” *arXiv:quant-ph/9605043*, Nov. 1996. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/quant-ph/9605043>
- [100] C. Moussa, H. Calandra, and T. S. Humble, “Function Maximization with Dynamic Quantum Search,” in *Quantum Technology and Optimization Problems*, ser. Lecture Notes in Computer Science, S. Feld and C. Linnhoff-Popien, Eds. Cham: Springer International Publishing, 2019, pp. 86–95.
- [101] E. Tang, “A quantum-inspired classical algorithm for recommendation systems,” in *Proceedings of the 51st Annual ACM SIGACT Symposium on Theory of Computing*, ser. STOC 2019. Phoenix, AZ, USA: Association for Computing Machinery, Jun. 2019, pp. 217–228. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1145/3313276.3316310>
- [102] P. R. Giri and V. E. Korepin, “A Review on Quantum Search Algorithms,” *Quantum Information Processing*, vol. 16, no. 12, p. 315, Dec. 2017. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/1602.02730>
- [103] F. Arute, K. Arya, R. Babbush, D. Bacon, J. C. Bardin, R. Barends, R. Biswas, S. Boixo, F. G. S. L. Brandao, D. A. Buell, B. Burkett, Y. Chen, Z. Chen, B. Chiaro, R. Collins, W. Courtney, A. Dunsworth, E. Farhi, B. Foxen, A. Fowler, C. Gidney, M. Giustina, R. Graff, K. Guerin, S. Habegger, M. P. Harrigan, M. J. Hartmann, A. Ho, M. Hoffmann, T. Huang, T. S. Humble, S. V. Isakov, E. Jeffrey, Z. Jiang, D. Kafri, K. Kechedzhi, J. Kelly, P. V. Klimov, S. Knysh, A. Korotkov, F. Kostritsa, D. Landhuis, M. Lindmark, E. Lucero, D. Lyakh, S. Mandrà, J. R. McClean, M. McEwen, A. Megrant, X. Mi, K. Michielsen, M. Mohseni, J. Mutus, O. Naaman, M. Neeley, C. Neill, M. Y. Niu, E. Ostby, A. Petukhov, J. C. Platt, C. Quintana, E. G. Rieffel, P. Roushan, N. C. Rubin, D. Sank, K. J. Satzinger, V. Smelyanskiy, K. J. Sung, M. D. Trevithick, A. Vainsencher, B. Villalonga, T. White, Z. J. Yao, P. Yeh, A. Zalcman, H. Neven, and J. M. Martinis, “Quantum supremacy using a programmable superconducting processor,” *Nature*, vol. 574, no. 7779, pp. 505–510, Oct. 2019. [Online]. Available: <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41586-019-1666-5>
- [104] I. L. Markov, A. Fatima, S. V. Isakov, and S. Boixo, “Quantum Supremacy Is Both Closer and Farther than It Appears,” *arXiv:1807.10749 [quant-ph]*, Sep. 2018. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/1807.10749>
- [105] J. Chen, F. Zhang, C. Huang, M. Newman, and Y. Shi, “Classical Simulation of Intermediate-Size Quantum Circuits,” *arXiv:1805.01450 [quant-ph]*, May 2018. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/1805.01450>
- [106] D. Maslov, Y. Nam, and J. Kim, “An Outlook for Quantum Computing [Point of View],” *Proceedings of the IEEE*, vol. 107, no. 1, pp. 5–10, Jan. 2019.
- [107] A. Bouland and S. Aaronson, “Generation of universal linear optics by any beam splitter,” *Physical Review A*, vol. 89, no. 6, p. 062316, Jun. 2014. [Online]. Available: <https://link.aps.org/doi/10.1103/PhysRevA.89.062316>

- [108] A. Neville, C. Sparrow, R. Clifford, E. Johnston, P. M. Birchall, A. Montanaro, and A. Laing, “No imminent quantum supremacy by boson sampling,” *Nature Physics*, vol. 13, no. 12, pp. 1153–1157, Dec. 2017. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/1705.00686>
- [109] N. M. Linke, D. Maslov, M. Roetteler, S. Debnath, C. Figgatt, K. A. Landsman, K. Wright, and C. Monroe, “Experimental Comparison of Two Quantum Computing Architectures,” *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, vol. 114, no. 13, pp. 3305–3310, Mar. 2017. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/1702.01852>
- [110] A. Kirke, “Application of Grover’s Algorithm on the ibmqx4 Quantum Computer to Rule-based Algorithmic Music Composition,” *ArXiv*, 2019.
- [111] B. Villalonga, S. Boixo, B. Nelson, C. Henze, E. Rieffel, R. Biswas, and S. Mandrà, “A flexible high-performance simulator for verifying and benchmarking quantum circuits implemented on real hardware,” *npj Quantum Information*, vol. 5, no. 1, p. 86, Dec. 2019. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/1811.09599>
- [112] M. J. Bremner, A. Montanaro, and D. J. Shepherd, “Achieving quantum supremacy with sparse and noisy commuting quantum computations,” *Quantum*, vol. 1, p. 8, Apr. 2017. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/1610.01808>
- [113] —, “Average-Case Complexity Versus Approximate Simulation of Commuting Quantum Computations,” *Physical Review Letters*, vol. 117, no. 8, p. 080501, Aug. 2016. [Online]. Available: <https://link.aps.org/doi/10.1103/PhysRevLett.117.080501>
- [114] C. S. Calude, “De-quantizing the solution of Deutsch’s problem,” *International Journal of Quantum Information*, vol. 5, no. 03, pp. 409–415, 2007.
- [115] *Qiskit/openqasm*. Qiskit, May 2020. [Online]. Available: <https://github.com/Qiskit/openqasm>
- [116] A. W. Cross, L. S. Bishop, J. A. Smolin, and J. M. Gambetta, “Open Quantum Assembly Language,” *arXiv:1707.03429 [quant-ph]*, Jul. 2017. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/1707.03429>
- [117] J. Randall, S. Weidt, E. D. Standing, K. Lake, S. C. Webster, D. F. Murgia, T. Navickas, K. Roth, and W. K. Hensinger, “Efficient preparation and detection of microwave dressed-state qubits and qutrits with trapped ions,” *Physical Review A*, vol. 91, no. 1, p. 012322, Jan. 2015. [Online]. Available: <https://link.aps.org/doi/10.1103/PhysRevA.91.012322>
- [118] G. S. Paraoanu, “Microwave-induced coupling of superconducting qubits,” *Physical Review B*, vol. 74, no. 14, p. 140504, Oct. 2006. [Online]. Available: <https://link.aps.org/doi/10.1103/PhysRevB.74.140504>
- [119] A. Shukla, M. Sisodia, and A. Pathak, “Complete characterization of the directly implementable quantum gates used in the IBM quantum processors,” *arXiv:1805.07185 [quant-ph]*, Jul. 2018. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/1805.07185>